

GAME-ER

February 2026

D4.3

Historical Development of Clusters

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Grant Agreement no. 101132585

PROJECT DETAILS

Acronym: **GAME-ER**
 Title: Gaming Clusters Across Multiple European Regions
 Coordinator: **INOVA+ - INNOVATION SERVICES, SA** (Portugal)
 Call: HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01
 Type: HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
 Topic-ID: HORIZON-CL2-2023-HERITAGE-01-06
 Start: **1 March 2024**
 End: **28 February 2027**
 Duration: **36 months**
 Website: www.game-er.eu

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Acknowledgements

This deliverable was developed based on collective efforts from all partners of the GAME-ER consortium.

DELIVERABLE DETAILS

Number: **D4.3**
Title: **Historical Development of Clusters**
Lead beneficiary: **UNITO**
Work package: **WP4**

Dissemination level: **Public**

Nature: **Report**

Due date: **31/12/2025**

Submission date: **13/02/2026**

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VERSION HISTORY:

Date	Version No.	Author	Note
24/11/2025	0.1	Nicola Costalunga, UNITO	Document creation and table of contents shared with Authors
30/12/2025	0.2	Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Introductory Sections, Methods
01/12/2025	0.3	Jaroslav Švelch, CUNI Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Integration and first revision of Brno Chapter
02/12/2025	0.4	Luís Leça; Matilde Caria, INOVA+ Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Integration and first revision of Fundação Chapter
06/12/2025	0.5	José David Gómez-Urrego, AU Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Integration and first revision of Dundee Chapter
10/12/2025	0.6	José David Gómez-Urrego, AU Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Integration and first revision of Turin Chapter

12/12/2025	0.7	Jaroslav Švelch, CUNI Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Brno chapter revised and incorporated into the report.
16/12/2025	0.8	José David Gómez-Urrego, AU Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Dundee chapter revised and incorporated into the report
17/12/2025	0.9	Nicola Costalunga, UNITO	Draft conclusion, partial references
22/12/2025	1.0	Matilde Caria, INOVA+ Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Fundão chapter revised and incorporated into the report
22/12/2025	1.1	Nicola Costalunga, UNITO	First version of the deliverable reviewed and formatted
06/01/2026	1.2	Nicola Costalunga, UNITO	Second Revision of the deliverable
07/01/2026	1.3	Chahira Mehouchi; Thomas Paris, CRG Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Integration and first revision of Lyon and Bordeaux Chapters
16/01/2026	1.4	Chahira Mehouchi; Thomas Paris, CRG	Lyon and Bordeaux chapters revised and incorporated into the report

		Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	
16/01/2026	1.5	Nicola Costalunga, UNITO	Third Revision of the deliverable; file sent for internal revision
26/01/2026	1.6	Mariana Salvado, CMF	Internal Revision and inputs provided
02/02/2026	1.7	Matilde Caria, INOVA+	Formatting check
05/02/2026	1.8	All Authors; Nicola Costalunga, UNITO	Integration of inputs
06/02/2026	1.9	Nicola Costalunga; Riccardo Fassone, UNITO	Integration of inputs and final formatting
/01/2026	2.0	Luís Leça, INOVA+ Stefano De Paoli, AU	Final Revision and Submission

GLOSSARY AND ABBREVIATIONS:

Name	Abbreviation
Triple-A (high-budget video game productions)	AAA
Association des Producteurs d'Œuvres Multimédia	APOM
Business to Business	B2B
Business to Consumer	B2C
Brno University of Technology	BUT
Chief Executive Officer	CEO
Cultural and Creative Industries	CCIs
Computer-Generated Imagery	CGI
Comité Interministériel d'Aménagement et de Développement du Territoire	CIADT
Crédit d'Impôt Jeu Vidéo	CIJV
Centre National du Cinéma et de l'image animée	CNC
Coin-Operated	Coin-Op
Délégation interministérielle à l'Aménagement du Territoire et à l'Attractivité Régionale	DATAR
Deliverable	D
Direction Générale des Entreprises	DGE
European Game Developers Federation	EGDF
École Nationale du Jeu et des Médias Interactifs Numériques	ENJMIN

European Commission	EComm
European Community	EC
Ente Italiano per le Audizioni Radiofoniche	EIAR
European Union	EU
Fonds d'Aide à l'Édition Multimédia	FAEM
Fiat Chrysler Automobiles	FCA
Fabbrica Italiana Automobili Torino	FIAT
Fonds National d'Aménagement et de Développement du Territoire	FNADT
Incubator for Innovative Businesses of the Polytechnic University of Turin	I3P
Île-de-France	IDF
International Game Developers Association	IGDA
Intellectual Property	IP
Initial Public Offering	IPO
Live action role playing	LARP
Masaryk University	MUNI
National Cash Register	NCR
Officine Grandi Riparazioni	OGR
Research and Development	R&D
Radiotelevisione Italiana	RAI

Syndicat des Éditeurs de Logiciels de Loisirs	SELL
Small and Medium-sized Enterprises	SMEs
Società in nome collettivo	S.n.c.
Syndicat National du Jeu Vidéo	SNJV
Società a responsabilità limitata	S.r.l.
Système Productif Local	SPL
Telecom Italia Mobile	TIM
Virtual Interactive Emerging World Conference	VIEW Conference
Work Package	WP

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the findings of the *Gaming Clusters Across Multiple European Regions (GAME-ER) project*, with specific reference to Task 4.3, *Historical Development of the Clusters*. The project examines six regional case studies – Dundee (Scotland, UK), Turin (Italy), Brno (Czechia), Lyon and Bordeaux (France), and Fundão (Portugal) – each representing a distinctive context in which the video game sector has developed outside dominant capital-city ecosystems.

The work investigates the historical evolution of local video game industries in order to trace how regional clusters have emerged, consolidated, and transformed over time. By identifying the socio-technical, economic, and cultural conditions underpinning their formation, the study offers robust historical evidence that clarifies the main factors driving the establishment and subsequent growth of these clusters.

The research design comprises two complementary phases, both grounded in established methodologies in media-historical scholarship. The first phase entailed systematic archival and documentary research, carried out across corporate and public repositories with the support of all project partners. This phase established a consolidated historical foundation for each participating cluster. The second phase centred on the collection of oral testimonies through semi-structured interviews with stakeholders identified by local partners. Between 5 and 10 interviews were conducted in each cluster, following a common template developed by the task leader and adapted to local circumstances. The combined outputs of these activities are presented in Deliverable 4.3, which offers a comprehensive historical reconstruction intended to inform broader analyses of European video game-production ecosystems.

The analytical process adopts a thematic analysis approach, following the shared framework developed within **GAME-ER** Working Package 3. This framework ensures consistency across the six case studies and promotes a balanced methodology that incorporates both inductive and deductive analytical reasoning. Such an approach enables detailed, context-specific interpretations while also supporting meaningful cross-case comparisons, thereby revealing broader trends as well as distinctive dynamics that have shaped the formation, development, and evolution of the clusters.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Project Overview

The Gaming Clusters Across Multiple European Regions (**GAME-ER**) project aims to explore the emergence, development, and sustainability of video game clusters, with a specific focus on local and regional clusters. The project will develop a comprehensive Interactive Methodological Toolkit, featuring policy and practical recommendations designed to assist local and national policymakers in establishing or enhancing Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) clusters within their regions or cities. Existing research often focuses on clusters outside Europe or within major metropolitan areas like Helsinki or Hamburg. However, **GAME-ER** addresses a critical gap by studying the dynamics of smaller, regional clusters, which play a significant role in driving innovation, growth, and regional cohesion. The project's core component involves a comparative analysis of six clusters in five European countries – France, the Czech Republic, Italy, Scotland, and Portugal. These clusters were chosen for their diverse levels of maturity and unique characteristics, including concentrations of creative talent and companies. In addition to this comparative study, **GAME-ER** will conduct a Europe-wide analysis of the spatial organisation of the video games industry, specifically focusing on local and regional ecosystems. This research, conducted in collaboration with policymakers and industry stakeholders, will guide the formulation of actionable recommendations using a participatory approach. **GAME-ER** brings together 15 partners from 9 countries, encompassing expertise in social sciences, humanities, policymaking, business, and innovation.

1.2 Introduction to D4.3

This deliverable extends the work initiated within Work Package (WP) 4, *Cluster Ecosystem – Case Studies*, following the activities reported in D4.1 (*Report on Primary Data Collection*)¹ and D4.2 (*Report on Documentary Analysis*)². D4.3 constitutes the next analytical step and shifts the temporal focus backwards, examining developments that largely precede the time frames explored in the earlier deliverables.

From a scholarly perspective, the task builds upon established approaches in media history and game historiography, which emphasise the importance of situating video game production within wider institutional, technological, and cultural contexts. Foundational contributions in the field – such as Lowood and Guins (2016), Swalwell (2021), and regionally oriented studies by Švelch (2023), Alberts and Oldenziel (2014), and Wade (2016) – demonstrate the necessity of historically grounded and locally specific accounts when analysing digital media ecosystems. These works provide the conceptual basis for the methodological design adopted in D4.3, which integrates documentary research, oral-historical methods, and, where pertinent, the examination of historical games and their associated paratexts.

¹ Report D4.1 is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535331>.

² Report D4.2 is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17440712>.

The task was carried out over a period of more than twelve months (M10–M22). Local partners collected, organised, and contextualised historical materials, conducted interviews, and identified the key milestones shaping the emergence of their respective clusters. The task leader (UNITO) coordinated these activities and synthesised the findings into the present report. Although the task was structured around two nominal phases – archival research followed by interviews with key actors – the work notably encouraged iterative feedback between the two, ensuring steady refinement of research questions and greater coherence in the data collected.

A fundamental requirement of the task involved establishing a plausible and collectively acknowledged starting point for the emergence of each cluster in its contemporary configuration. These dates were inferred from evidence gathered in previous work packages (notably D4.1) and subsequently corroborated through additional documentary analysis. As demonstrated in relevant case studies (e.g. Blanchet on France; Fassone and Santagostino on Italy; Picard on Japan), the historical boundaries of video game ecosystems rarely coincide neatly with formal institutional milestones. They must instead be reconstructed through a triangulation of oral testimonies, documents, and material artefacts.

Archival work in D4.3 encompassed both institutional repositories (for example, chambers of commerce and GLAM institutions) and informal or “grey” archives, including private collections and historically significant ephemera. Previous research (e.g., Fassone, 2017; Keogh, 2021) underscores the value of such sources in capturing early or marginal practices that may otherwise leave limited traces. Alongside this, each partner was required to conduct at least five semi-structured historical interviews per cluster. Interviewees were selected for their involvement in or knowledge of early local game-making communities, such as pioneering developers, demosceners, collectors, or amateur historians. A shared interview model was provided by the task leader, covering both biographical reconstruction and the elicitation of an event timeline relevant to the cluster’s early development.

D4.3 aligns with ongoing international initiatives in game-history research, including the *History of Games* conference series and the *GRADE project* (Grassroots of Digital Europe) on early European creative computing, as well as with established scholarly venues such as the *MIT Press Game Histories* book series and *ROMchip: A Journal of Game Histories*. By integrating archival sources, oral testimonies, and historical analysis, this task produces a rigorous and comparative account of the origins and evolution of regional video game clusters. The findings offer evidence-based insights into processes of cluster formation, regional innovation, and the dynamics of local creative ecosystems.

1.3. Deliverable objectives

The principal objective of D4.3 is to reconstruct the diachronic trajectories that led to the emergence and consolidation of each cluster, identifying the socio-technical, economic, and cultural factors that shaped their development. This entails both synthesising historical knowledge gathered thus far and conducting an in-depth examination of the “prehistory” of each cluster. Particular emphasis is placed on identifying the cluster’s “Year Zero” – the moment recognised by local teams as its more

or less institutionalised point of foundation. Following this, the analysis considers the diverse determinants influencing subsequent development: historical events affecting local industry structures; exogenous institutional, economic, cultural, and creative drivers; relationships with adjacent or proto-industries (such as electromechanical amusements or arcade-technology production); enabling or constraining regulatory and technological frameworks; and territorial continuities or disruptions that shaped the cluster's long-term configuration.

The deliverable therefore contributes to:

- Reconstructing the diachronic trajectories of cluster formation, examining their historical evolution.
- Identifying the socio-technical, economic, and cultural conditions that facilitated the emergence of local game-production clusters.
- Producing robust historical datasets that isolate the factors underpinning cluster formation and subsequent development.

This is achieved through:

- Conducting historical research in two phases, drawing on established methods in media-historical inquiry.
- Phase 1 (up to M16): collecting historical evidence through corporate and public archives, and through desk research on relevant publications.
- Phase 2 (from M17 onwards): conducting semi-structured interviews with stakeholders identified by local partners – at least five per cluster – using an interview model developed by the task leader and adapted to local characteristics.

Through this multifaceted historical analysis, D4.3 offers an essential resource for understanding the underlying dynamics of regional video game ecosystems prior to their formal establishment. It thereby illuminates the conditions that shaped their emergence, consolidation, and evolution, and provides insights that may be relevant for fostering similar developments in other contexts, especially beyond major urban centres. Finally, this work aims to elucidate the key historical determinants through which the past continues to inform and shape the future development of regional video game clusters, thereby providing an evidence-based foundation for policy design and the formulation of best practices.

2 HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE CLUSTERS

2.1 Methodology Framework

The methodological framework underpinning D4.3 draws on established approaches in media-historical and game-historiographical research, combining systematic documentary analysis with oral-historical inquiry in order to reconstruct the early development of each local video game-production cluster. The research was conducted over roughly one year and organised into two complementary strands, conceived as mutually reinforcing rather than strictly sequential.

The first strand centred on the identification, collection, and interpretation of historical documentation. Partners examined an extensive range of sources, acknowledging that the material traces of video game history frequently lie beyond formal institutional repositories. Accordingly, the research encompassed corporate and public archives – such as company registration documents, production records, and other institutional materials, alongside informal or “grey” archives. The latter included artefacts held by private collectors, materials preserved within clubs or informal communities, and paratextual objects such as manuals, packaging, promotional items, and historically significant games. This heterogeneous body of sources enabled not only the reconstruction of timelines and organisational structures but also the identification of local specificities that remain invisible in official records.

The second strand involved the collection of oral testimonies through semi-structured interviews with individuals able to illuminate the formative phases of local video game ecosystems. Interviewees were selected on the basis of expertise rather than institutional status and included, among others, early developers, demosceners, hobbyists, collectors, educators, and observers who documented early practices. Each interview combined a biographical component – establishing the interviewee’s position within the local milieu – with an analytical section focused on identifying turning points, sequences of events, and relevant contextual factors.

In D4.3, documentary analysis and interviews were not treated as discrete stages but as interdependent elements within an iterative process. Insights derived from preliminary archival work informed interview design and selection, while oral testimonies often opened new avenues for further documentary investigation or provided essential contextualisation for fragmentary evidence. This interplay between source types was crucial for producing a historically grounded account of cluster emergence, especially in contexts where early documentation is limited or dispersed.

Through this combined methodological approach, the task aims to produce a coherent reconstruction of the origins of each cluster, identifying the formative events, principal actors, and enabling conditions that shaped their development.

2.2 Interview Themes and Topics

The interview script was developed as an exploratory instrument intended to engage informants with knowledge of the early history of the local video game-production cluster. Its primary aim was to elicit information on practices related to game design, development, distribution, and other activities that preceded the formal establishment of the cluster. The script sought to generate a structured understanding of the cluster’s formative processes by reconstructing a timeline of significant events, identifying key actors and their respective roles, and clarifying how early initiatives and practices contributed to the cluster’s later configuration.

To achieve these objectives, the script consisted of broad and adaptable questions that could be tailored to different local contexts and respondent profiles. In short, interviewees were invited to introduce themselves and describe their first involvement in video game production; to report any earlier activities in the area and the actors associated with them; to outline, as far as possible, a chronology of early video game-related events; to identify specific episodes perceived as decisive in shaping the future cluster; and to suggest individuals – such as developers, collectors, or scholars – who might possess substantial historical knowledge of the local video game ecosystem.

The initial question script was as follows:

- Please introduce yourself and describe how and when you got involved in video game production.
- Do you know of any activity that happened around video game production in this area before your involvement? What kinds of activities were performed, and who were the relevant actors?
- To the best of your knowledge, could you produce a timeline of video game-related events that happened in this area, starting from the earliest you know of?
- Is there a specific event that you think contributed decisively to the formation of a video game cluster in this area? And when did it happen?
- Do you know of anyone (developer, collector, academic, etc.) who you think has significant historical knowledge about the history of video game development in this area?

Table 1. Total number of actors interviewed per cluster.

Cluster	Nr. Of Interviewees
Dundee	9
Turin	10
Brno	7
Lyon & Bordeaux	13
Fundão	5

2.3 Data Analysis: Thematic Coding and Comparative Synthesis

Following the completion of the interviews, all recordings were transcribed and subsequently analysed using thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). As in the previous deliverables, this analytical phase was guided by the methodological framework established in WP3 (*Analytical Grid and Comparative Typology of Clusters*), and in particular by the shared analytical grid developed in D3.1 (*Analytical Grid and Interview Script*). Thematic analysis was again selected because it offers a systematic means of identifying, organising, and reporting recurrent patterns – or themes – within qualitative data.

The procedure involved several stages:

- **Familiarisation:** reading and re-reading the interview transcripts to gain a comprehensive understanding of the material.
- **Initial coding:** generating preliminary codes that captured salient features of the data.
- **Theme development:** grouping related codes into provisional themes and assessing their coherence.
- **Refinement and definition:** reviewing, naming, and defining the themes, and selecting illustrative quotations.

Using the shared analytical grid, the emerging themes were adapted to reflect the specific historical characteristics of each cluster. The analytical strategy consisted of producing an initial inductive coding of the transcripts and subsequently aggregating these codes into the main thematic categories of the grid. As in D4.1, the approach combined inductive and deductive qualitative analysis, although in a more flexible manner to accommodate the heterogeneity of the data. This methodology ensures the comparability of findings across clusters and facilitates the synthesis of results by the project partners, thereby contributing directly to the preparation of D3.3 (*Final Comparative Analysis and Typology*).

2.4 Order of Chapters

The remainder of this deliverable is structured into a series of dedicated chapters, each offering an in-depth examination of the local context, developmental trajectory, and key dynamics of the respective cluster. Each chapter was prepared independently by a different project partner; as a result, certain narrative elements and reporting styles vary considerably among each other. In particular, the chapters concerning the Lyon and Bordeaux clusters have been consolidated into a single chapter, as agreed by the authors, thereby avoiding any overlap with previous deliverables. Nonetheless, all contributions follow a shared structure derived from the project’s analytical grid developed for D3.1 (*Analysis Grid and Interview Script*), and from the methodological guidelines provided by the task leader (UNITO).

The chapters are presented in the following order:

- **Dundee (Scotland, UK):** a cluster distinguished by a long and significant history, originating in manufacturing traditions and subsequently experiencing remarkable expansion.
- **Turin (Italy):** a city with a strong industrial and cultural–creative heritage, whose cluster emerged initially through individual initiatives rather than endogenous systemic drivers.
- **Brno (Czechia):** an ecosystem characterised by an important hobbyist culture rooted in the passion of early programmers who later formed highly successful companies.
- **Lyon and Bordeaux (France):** two specific cases which, despite their regional distinctiveness, share fundamental commonalities grounded in national industry dynamics, shared institutional frameworks, and comparable entrepreneurial patterns.
- **Fundão (Portugal):** an example of a recent and comprehensive process of economic reconversion, aimed at revitalising an area traditionally considered rural and marginal.

Finally, to provide additional analytical depth and insight, a cross-cluster historical overview is presented immediately after the sections devoted to the individual case studies, with the aim of highlighting and synthesising the main recurring historical mechanisms observed across the six regional cases. The purpose of this chapter is to further contribute to the consolidation of a shared analytical framework in order to ensure the comparability of the case studies, thereby helping to establish a conceptual link between the empirical historical reconstruction and the project's subsequent comparative analysis and potential policy-oriented actions.

3 THE DUNDEE CLUSTER

3.1 Data collection and analysis

This section describes the results of the historical research conducted on the Dundee cluster, paying particular attention to its historical evolution by investigating the key events, actors, and socioeconomic conditions that led to the emergence and success of the cluster over time. For this task, the Abertay team used multiple methods to capture relevant individual accounts as well as documents of historical significance. This approach included the implementation of semi-structured qualitative interviews, informed by oral history, with relevant stakeholders, as well as the documentary analysis of relevant documents identified from a multiplicity of sources (Chapman, 2016). These sources included the *National Library of Scotland*, the *Social History Archive*, *Dundee's Local History Centre*, the *DC Thomson Archive and photo collections*, *University of Dundee's Archive and local history collections*, *Dundee Heritage Trust*, *Dundee City Archives*, the *McManus Galleries Collection*, and *Abertay University's Archive*, as well as documents offered by interviewees from their own personal collections. The documents identified include local newspaper and magazine articles from the 1970s onwards, photographs, proposals for video games degrees, minutes from Abertay University's council meetings, secondary literature written on the Video Games Industry in Scotland, Dundee's industrial history, and books written on specific video games like *Grand Theft Auto*, as well as digital media sources like a Documentary produced on the history of *Lemmings*, and the personal blogs of key historical actors that shaped Dundee's video games industry over time. Overall, 139 documents were identified, and the team then extracted the text and analysed it using NVivo. This documentary analysis allowed the team to position the emergence of the Dundee cluster embedded in Dundee's longer history and the conditions of the video games industry internationally, too.

For the semi-structured interviews, the team conducted 9 oral history-inspired interviews (Janesick, 2014), which were conducted between January 2025 and November 2025 with actors who had a longitudinal influence and perspective on the cluster, having been part of it since its early days, and having experienced the many transformations it has gone through over time. For the interviews, a flexible script based on the Analytical Grid of the **GAME-ER** project (WP3) was generated to bring to the fore events, actors, and conditions that allowed the Dundee video games cluster to emerge. Interviews in person were prioritised, and virtual interviews were offered as an alternative. For this task, the team used purposeful sampling together with snowball sampling (Parker et al., 2019). The use of purposeful sampling allowed the selection of participants who had a privileged first-hand experience of the trajectory of the Dundee video games industry and could share rich expertise, insights, and recommendations for further interviewees. The codebook used for task 4.1 of the **GAME-ER** project was complemented with new codes that emerged from an inductive approach to the historical interviews (Deterding & Waters, 2021). This new codebook was then used to identify the key characteristics of the historical evolution of the cluster, starting from the identification of the "year zero". To achieve this, the codes were grouped into themes, and the themes were mapped into the most relevant dimensions.

3.2 Cluster general historical information

Dundee's video game industry's emergence and later growth can be understood within the wider trajectory of innovation and commercial growth of the British computing and gaming sectors since the late 1970s. According to Tsang (2021), the UK video game industry developed through a network of regional mini-clusters, where expertise and knowledge circulated more or less freely among key hubs such as London, Cambridge, and Dundee. Over time, some of these clusters attracted greater concentrations of talent and studios, and a more polarised structure would come into place. In the early years, this networked structure was facilitated and reinforced by the widespread rise of computing literacy across the country and the British public's generative engagement with home computing. A major catalyst in this process was the BBC's Computer Literacy Project (CLP) and the nationwide introduction of the BBC Micro in schools and public education initiatives during the 1980s. As Danton (2021) notes, this initiative not only introduced young people throughout the UK to programming and other creative computer uses but also laid the foundation for regional talent pools that would later support creative industries, such as video game development.

Dundee serves as a prime example of this contingent combination of factors: early access to creative computing practices, the local availability and popularity of home computers such as the ZX Spectrum, and the presence of educational programmes and independent computer clubs nurtured a generation of technically ingenious individuals who went on to form pioneering studios like *DMA Design* and *VIS Interactive* (later became VIS Entertainment). Thus, Dundee's rise as a prominent centre of creative computing, extending beyond games, illustrates the long-term influence of Britain's early investments in computer literacy, the synergy between technical and arts-inspired creative innovation, and the distributed, innovation-oriented nature of the UK games industry (Tsang, 2021).

Concerning Dundee as a city itself, in the past century, it has undergone a transformation from a jute-based industrial powerhouse to a more diverse economy, with a strong video game production cluster, showing remarkable economic adaptability while still facing several socioeconomic challenges. Historically, Dundee was synonymous with the jute industry and was known as "*Juteopolis*", with jute mills dominating the employment landscape and employing a significant proportion of the population (Wright, 2011; Tomlinson et al., 2022). During this time, Dundee was popularly known as "*She-town*" because women played a central part in providing for their families and were the motor force behind the jute mills. Even so, women's labour was not recognised or paid as high-skilled; it was men who held power positions both within the factories and more broadly socio-politically in the city as a whole (Bozdog, 2022; Browne & Tomlinson, 2011). The influence of jute on Dundee's social and industrial trajectory cannot be overstated, as it was the backbone for almost 150 years of the Dundonian economy. Yet, the wealth was not distributed across socioeconomic classes but rather accumulated in a few, "*the golden fibre created huge fortunes for those who guided the imperial nexus of jute, but it also brought misery in its train for many who laboured in the killing floors of Camperdown as well as Champdany.*" (Cox, 2013, p.4). However, the skills, industrial manufacturing knowledge, engineering skills, and infrastructures would be

reconfigured to become part of new industries. As an example of this point, years later, this same area of Camperdown in Dundee, which once hosted the biggest jute mill in the world, would also be the site for several new industries like *Timex*, *NCR*, and several video games companies (see Figure 1).

Three important factors inherited from this period were key to future industries in Dundee, including video games development, which are worth mentioning. First, the prevalence of the skilled female workforce in the jute mills and the gendered labour that powered the jute mills would later be readapted to new manufacturing industries. Women in Dundee played an immense role in sustaining both households and dynamising the city's economy. Their comprehensive manufacturing skills were a key factor in the city's attractiveness to multinational companies after WWII (see Figure 2); hence, *"the nimble hands of Dundonian women were offered as an incentive to the 'new' industries"* (Bozdog, 2022, p. 159).

Figure 1. A Photo taken in 1982 of a general view of one of the General Timex Factory's assembly lines in Camperdown, where a great number of women worked in assembling a variety of mechanical and electronic devices, including the ZX81 and the ZX Spectrum home computers.³

Second, the long-term familiarisation of both female and male workers in Dundee with intensive factory-style lines of production allowed for the arrival of multinational manufacturing firms, who would use these factors to their own advantage. Third, the terrible conditions of work present in the jute industry inspired many female and male workers to move into new manufacturing jobs as soon as they were available in Dundee. These three factors would be critical in allowing the city to attract new industries connected to manufacturing, including industries like *NCR* and *Timex*, which would take part in the manufacturing of clocks, computers, and other electronic devices, such as 3D cameras and ATMs. The Jute Industry itself experienced a sustained collapse during the 20th century, and many jobs were lost in the process, while the attraction of multinational manufacturing

³ All the pictures presented in this chapter are reproduced by permission of DC Thomson & Co Ltd, accessed through the DC Thomson Archive in Dundee.

enterprises like Levi’s, Michelin, Timex, and NCR in the post-WWII period would compensate for some of these job losses and improve the working conditions for many Dundonians (DH086)⁴. However, beginning in the post-war period and accelerating in the 1970s and 1980s, the city experienced an industrial decline, marked by the retraction of the multinationals and the eventual final collapse of the jute industry, leading to a period of economic challenges and a widespread perception of scarcity (Tomlinson, 2011). In the midst of this decades-long process of deindustrialisation, the local manufacture of ZX Spectrum computers by Dundee’s Timex factory became an unexpected catalyst for a different economic activity branch (DH104), making these home computers exceptionally accessible and nurturing an even stronger computer culture in the city.

Figure 2. A photo taken in 1977 at Timex shows a woman assembling one of the mechanical clocks that made Timex famous internationally. It was these skills that helped trigger the transition of computers into the home space and made possible the expansion of video games. Dundonian women played a critical role in this shift, making it possible for these computers to reach people of all socioeconomic backgrounds in Dundee.

This widespread access allowed young people to experiment with programming and game development, laying the groundwork for the rise of video game production as a viable career. In the following years, this led to the identification of video games as a potential strategic pillar in Dundee’s ongoing transition to a different economic matrix, symbolised by the city’s initial rebranding as “The City of Discovery” in 1982 (Di Domenico & Di Domenico, 2007; Lloyd et al., 2006).

On this fertile ground, the video game cluster germinated, initially driven by the visionary work of *DMA Design*, a company that acted as the single point of origin or initial nucleus of the industry. The latter global hits of games developed by DMA Design, such as *Lemmings* (1991) and *Grand Theft Auto* (1997), not only put Dundee on the international creative map but also inspired a new

⁴ The documents from the historical collection gathered across Dundee Archives has been logged into a matrix with key data for identification. The documents pertaining to that collection are cited across this chapter as DH001 and so forth. Not all of the documents from the collection could be cited due to extension limitation, but the collection itself constitutes the first in its kind of historical documents important to the history of video games in the city.

generation of developers to become part of the industry through various pathways, both academic and non-professional (DH019, DH20). As a testament to this tendency, a crucial milestone was Abertay University's decision in 1997 to introduce the world's first degree in Computer Games development (DH108, DH109), which became a fertiliser for the industry's growth, attracting lecturers and students from around the world and fuelling numerous startups while also providing specialised talent for the existing companies.

3.2.1 Brief description of the cluster in the contemporary period

Dundee's video game cluster is currently characterised by several distinctive strengths that position it as a stable cluster within the global industry. Central to its vitality is Abertay University, globally recognised for its specialised programmes in game development, which acts as a constant incubator of talent, nurturing the local ecosystem with highly qualified graduates and fostering the creation of new companies. The city is now home to around 45 game companies of multiple sizes (see deliverable D4.2 for the details of each company), a considerable number ranging from established studios such as Rockstar North (part of Take-Two), Tag (recently acquired by Scopely), 4J Studios, Ninja Kiwi, Outplay, and Hyper Luminal Games, to a plethora of smaller, dynamic independent studios and collectives. Nowadays, collectives like *Biome Collective* and *Very Evil Demons* play an important role in the cluster by gathering independent developers and allowing them to work on common projects without having to settle in the shape of a company or work for the larger studios permanently.

This diversity fosters an environment of creativity, informal collaboration, and resilience even when there are multiple challenges, including a lack of sufficient infrastructure, difficulty accessing funding, and struggles generating internationally recognised and locally owned IP (see deliverables D4.1 and D4.2). The community is remarkably cohesive and collaborative, an attribute facilitated by the city's compact size, which allows for fluid interaction and a strong sense of camaraderie among professionals, even at the level of studio directors. Events that are either created locally or have a local adaptation, such as *Hubworld*, *Arcadia*, *Protoplay*, *Drop in and Play*, *Global Game Jam*, and *Games Talks Live*, are crucial platforms for networking and knowledge sharing. Meanwhile, organisations like *Creative Dundee* work to connect the wider creative industries with people working within the video games sector. Furthermore, Dundee offers an affordable quality of life at a relatively low cost compared to other major UK cities, which is beneficial for both students and emerging studios.

Another key point is that there is no formal organisation representing the whole of the industry, in the shape of a formal cluster or via another legal form, and some studios operate in silos due to confidentiality agreements and the competitive nature of the sector. An emblematic case being Rockstar North, which is the biggest employer but has a very low level of involvement in the local community openly. Finally, there is a common agreement among actors in the cluster that Dundee needs a unified organisation and strategy that promotes its current achievements and future opportunities and leverages more strategic and meaningful government support.

3.3 Temporal perimeter: Cluster History

3.3.1 'Year Zero'

The Abertay team has identified the “Year Zero” of the Dundee video games industry as a cluster, as the period after the downfall of *RealTime Worlds* in 2010 (DH059, DH122), one of its largest companies. While on a first look this may seem like a critical moment in the cluster’s history with one of its biggest companies going under, a closer look at the interviews and documents also brings to the light the resiliency the industry showed then, the diversification of economic activities and business models that was already taking place, and how this collapse triggered the emergence of new companies and a strengthened sense of endurance for the video games industry as a whole. The year zero of a video games cluster can be posited to a moment in time in which there was diversification enough that the collapse of a large company could be endured by the cluster, a significant amount of its talent absorbed again into the cluster via new companies or by hiring from other existing companies, and there was a rising wave of startups emerging from Abertay University and other pathways (DH084).

Hence, the “year zero” for the Dundee cluster is not necessarily its most successful year, or most stable year, but the year in which the solidity and diversification of the industry were tested and the industry was able to recover and continue to grow and expand. In the words of one of our interviewees: *“I mean, Realtime Worlds when that crashed, that was huge for the industry, but all that did then led to all of these guys taking up and starting up themselves... there were another six start-ups after Realtime collapsed, that then went on to do their own things. And that’s always going to be the cycle.”* (Dundee video game company CEO 1)

Realtime Worlds was founded in 2002 by Dave Jones, who led DMA Design to success, and the company experienced a collapse and went into administration in August 2010 (DH123). At the time, *Realtime Worlds* had become the biggest employer in Dundee’s digital media sector, employing over 200 staff (Tomlinson, 2011b). At its peak, the company employed approximately 370 people, and it had also attracted substantial investments, including \$80 million in 2008 (House of Commons Scottish Affairs Committee, 2011b). The primary reason for its collapse was far less than anticipated sales of its massively multiplayer online game (MMOG), APB. *Realtime Worlds* had been developing APB as a multi-user online game, akin to GTA, designed for the 64-bit home PC market. However, this market largely failed to materialise as anticipated, and the emergence of the iPad fundamentally changed the gaming landscape towards mobile gaming. As a result, *“The investors got cold feet and pulled out, and the company collapsed kind of overnight. So that kind of disruption was probably the most abrupt break in the games cluster trajectory in Dundee, and there were 200 people, game developers in the city looking for jobs, and, you know, the response was really interesting.”* (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher)

So, the collapse of *Realtime Worlds* had a profound and immediate impact on Dundee’s games scene, but was also a canonical event. The video games development workforce experienced a decline of over 18% in 2010, falling from 798 development staff in April to 651 by September, primarily due to *Realtime Worlds* going into administration (House of Commons Scottish Affairs

Committee, 2011a). This decline had a disproportionate effect on Scotland’s overall workforce figures compared to the rest of the UK, which had a decline of around 4.4% (House of Commons Scottish Affairs Committee, 2011a). As a result, our sources describe that there was *“chaos in the city, and there was a real risk that the industry would just disappear from the city”* (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher), and the historical documents identified from that moment in time confirm it (DH059, DH082, DH084, DH122, DH123). However, the industry did tumble, collapse, and vanish. Some of the valuable talent who had experience working at the highest level and developing ambitious games were hired by other companies, as one of our interviewees describes, *“the experience within that workforce in the city was so valuable that they couldn’t just disappear”* (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher). Various factors at play prevented this from happening. According to the sources the diversity of companies that already existed plus the market possibilities opened by the rapid emergence of mobile gaming, allowed for a significant amount of the talent present in *RealTime Worlds* when it collapsed to be recaptured by the industry: *“there was already a group of smaller companies in the city that were able to hire in some of that talent, but with the advent of the iPhone and the iPad and mobile gaming, then there was a new market for smaller companies to move into, so a lot of smaller studios popped up around about that time.”* (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher)

This mix of both internal capacity building and external technological breakthroughs allowed the industry not only to survive the collapse of one of its main players but also to gain resilience and stability. The timing of the collapse coincided with the advent of the iPhone and iPad, creating a new and accessible market for mobile gaming (DH082, DH084). This new market provided opportunities for smaller companies to emerge, some of them from the by then already established Abertay’s professional video games development degrees, helping to absorb some of the displaced talent and further diversify the industry, giving rise to the cluster. The arrival of *Outplay Entertainment*, a studio specialising in mobile games that moved from the US to Scotland, into the Dundee scene also signalled the rise of the mobile market and the branching out of the local talent who were hired for the company (DH063, DH067).

The local industry then showed not only diversification but also a higher degree of stability, talent absorption, resilience, and openness to market changes. Interestingly, one of the companies that emerged from *RealTime Worlds* was *Ruffian Games*, which spun out to get the *Crackdown 3* contract, after *RealTime Worlds* did *Crackdown 1* and *2*. *Ruffian Games* would later be acquired by Rockstar and become *Rockstar North*, marking the return of Rockstar to Dundee. The recovery of the industry and its vibrancy as a cluster can be evidenced by how, by 2011, less than a year after the collapse of Real Time Worlds, at least 18 companies were operating in Dundee, both directly in video game development as well as providing complementary services (see Table 2). According to a source at the time in 2011, *“Dundee has over 50% of Scotland’s video companies and 60% of Scotland’s development studio employees”* (House of Commons Scottish Affairs Committee, 2011b, evw1).

Table 2. Companies present in Dundee during 2011. Source: House of Commons Scottish Affairs Committee (2011b) and interviews.

Company	Type of work
Ruffian	Traditional Model
Cohort	Traditional Model
Denki	Traditional Model; Xbox Live Development; Self Publishing
Cobra	Mobile Developer; Digital Distribution; Traditional Model
Real-time Worlds	Self-publishing (in administration by then)
Proper	Xbox Live Arcade
Electric Top Hat	Mobile game developer
TPLD	Educational Games developer
Digital Goldfish	Mobile; iPad Developers
Waracle	Application development; iPhone
Play2improve	Educational games; Multi-platform
Tag Games	Publisher and PSP; DSI Mobile Developer
4J	Conversions; Multi-platform
Dynamo Games	Mobile Games
Jack Hoose music	Production of music for Games
Game Ops	Consultancy; Recruitment
BBB Games	Mobile Development
Henderson and Loggie	Accounting Services
Outplay Entertainment	Independent mobile game developer

Importantly, according to several of our sources, the collapse of *RealTime Worlds* was also a breaking point with respect to the kind of business models that local companies were pursuing; *APB* was the last investment of that magnitude that had gone into developing one game, with all the pressure and multiple stressors that are in place when working on a project of that magnitude with such high expectations and levels of demand (DH123). *RealTime Worlds* embodied an ambitious spirit both in vision and in the technical challenges involved in making those games, as well as developing immense games that aimed at becoming world hits and required a budget equivalent to their ambitions. But it was also connected to the AAA style of games, which could become a nest for detrimental work practices. Interestingly, Rockstar North has recently returned to the city and adopted a model of high secrecy while developing GTA VI.

Furthermore, it was not only the business model approach that changed, but also there was a diversification of the labour, communication, and political culture around video game development taking place in the city. There was a growth of the “indie scene” but not only on an artistic level, but also on an organisational one; graduates from Abertay and people moving to Dundee from beyond the city formed collaborative and non-secretive organisations such as the *Biome Collective*. This collective is an independent initiative that has bet since its inception on the creative dimension of video games as experiences beyond purely fun or entertainment, open communication, and collaborative work. It opposes the highly competitive boom and bust dynamic and the crunch culture that became synonymous with large-scale video game production at some point across the industry. This passage notes the shift in business approach and how the gravitational centre of the cluster shifted: *“There are a lot more small companies, which I think 20-odd years ago I would not have predicted. Because it felt like everything was gravitating towards a handful of AAA games being created by the likes of VIS, Visual Science, and Realtime Worlds.”* (Dundee video game company Producer 1). The resilience the industry showed after the collapse of *RealTime Worlds*, was also connected to a sort of learning from past mistakes or at least from past treed paths, and this is noticeable in the testimony of one of our interviewees who describes what happened after the collapse of the company and the diversity of smaller studios that appeared after its going under, *“I think part of that was that graduates from Abertay would see that it was possible to kick something off after they graduated. And see how it worked out. So that’s happened over time– in the period between sort of 2009 to 2019, we saw that a little explosion happened with smaller companies springing up over Dundee.”* (Dundee video game company Producer 3)

3.3.2 Before ‘Year Zero’

Before the Year Zero of the cluster, the seeds of the industry were sown in Dundee almost two decades before, during the 1980s, when the *Timex Factory* in Dundee started manufacturing the *ZX Spectrum* home computer, and as this technology rolled around the city through both formal and informal pathways, it started creating an unparalleled level of accessibility to personal computing in Dundee. This technological availability was coupled with the resourcefulness of local kids and a rising interest in computers and video games generally, which led to the emergence of a subculture amongst mostly young men of programming games at home.

This new subculture coalesced into computing clubs and groups like the *Kingsway Computing Club*, where figures like Dave Jones and Mike Dailly started to build games together, which would eventually lead to Dave Jones deciding to start DMA Design as a studio. While Jones and Dailly were still students, DMA Design developed games that would have significant commercial successes like *Menace (1988)* and *Blood Money (1989)*, which were *“instrumental for both DMA Design and for the video games industry in Dundee in its early days”* (Dundee video game company CEO 3) (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. A photo of David Jones Computer with his game Menace. The picture was taken on the 5th of October 1988, and portrays Jones as a young man proud of his game, the first developed in Dundee, and with wide commercial success. The revenues from this game would allow DMA to continue creating video games even before the wider success of Lemmings and GTA.

The release of *Lemmings* on February 14th, 1991, would become a crucial event in the history of the industry as it was “where the world changed because *Lemmings* went on to be an absolute breakout hit and put DMA on the map” (Scotland video games Senior Producer 1). *Lemmings* marked a significant turning point; it both built on the earlier explorative and creative foundations of the computer clubs while also paving the way for the industry’s growth and formalisation in the city (Dailly, 2006). *Lemmings*’ impact was immense on a global scale and was celebrated as a local victory for Dundee (DH14, DH15, DH52), according to *Amiga User International*, a specialised press from that day and age, “to say that *Lemmings* took the computer gaming world by storm would be like saying that Henry Ford made a slight impact on the car market” (Scotsman, 1996).

Mike Dailly, one of the first members of DMA Design, recalls the unexpected scenes at DMA’s office on the launch day and the impact the game had on a world scale: “On launch day, Psygnosis would phone almost every hour telling Dave the latest sales figures. 10,000! 20,000! 30,000! 35,000! 45,000! In the end, the game would ship over 55,000 copies of the Amiga version in the first day alone.” (Dailly, 2021a)

The tangible impact on Dundee was significant in the following years, and the path was opened to consider video games as a viable career from which people could make a living and even thrive (DH11, DH12). This rising buzz around the video games industry inspired young people and drew attention to the potential of game development in the city (DH19 DH39). Even further, it also triggered a wave of financial and critical acclaim, generating crucial credibility, the capacity to attract

funding, and a buzz that laid the groundwork for the future cluster. We refer to this stage in time as the *foundational era*⁵ (roughly between 1987 and 1993) of the Dundee video games industry. This was happening at a time when video game programming was seen as an entertainment activity, in the words of Dave Jones, game developing for most people “...was a hobby. A lot of developers still had regular day jobs” (Dave Jones in Wallis, 2006). New commercial opportunities arose, and those opportunities brought about a challenge for DMA Design as the studio looked to double its staff to meet new targets. The size of the company was still relatively small, going from 9 to a predicted 18 employees in a single year (DH020) and likely with further growth following on. In 1995, DMA Design’s general manager, Stuart Dell, notes that they had “*exhausted the local talent to some extent*” (DH011), having to expand their recruitment advertising to Glasgow and Edinburgh, and, while ideally keeping recruitment to Scotland, had to accept applications from across Europe.

Even when DMA made it possible to even consider video game development a viable job in Dundee, it was still socially seen with scepticism and with a certain disregard for video games as a medium. This also implied that the entry points to start a career in the industry were not formalised; they were markedly empirical in nature, and talent was not expected to have an official degree from a university, but rather be able to show their programming skills, curiosity, and drive. DMA was formed by really young individuals. By 1995, Dave Jones calculated that the average age of the company employees was 24 years old (Evening Telegraph, 1995). This was intentional, as the sort of expertise required for the company was one in which not many would be experienced, as by then the company was working on cutting-edge technologies. The CEO of the company described it in these words, “*You can’t really get many people with experience in what we are doing, and I don’t want to bring in people who have worked in other companies and perhaps not had a good time. We prefer to get people who are fresh and keen to learn, and we know we can find them here in Dundee. Just about everyone working here is local*” (Dave Jones quoted in Evening Telegraph, 1995)

However, DMA was one company, and then there was no sense that video games were an industry yet; it was still more like isolated specific efforts by daredevil individuals. One of our interviewees describes these conditions through a lively description of how he got a job in DMA by displaying his ingenuity and drive: “*I got my first interview with Dave, and I didn’t get the job, so I was a bit bummed out, but it didn’t put me off; I went away and made a game of my own, a tiny little game of my own. Then DMA advertised again about nine months later. I went back to Dave and I said, “I didn’t get the job first time, in between I’ve made this little game on my own,” and the second time, basically when I walked in, he just says, “You’ve got the job already ‘cause you’ve went away and made a game, and let’s just have a chat about what you’re gonna be doing here*” (Dundee video game company CEO 2).

Furthermore, as just mentioned, the social and cultural context in which this was happening was still averse to perceiving video games as a valid, viable, and respectable job. According to our

⁵ It is worth noting that the different eras or phases we have identified do not relate to one another in a natural progression, hierarchy of levels, or a neat pathway to “success”. We have rather aimed to capture the main characteristics of each period with its particular sociotechnical characteristics, incoming and disappearing players, and key events. It is also worth noting that some of the elements of one period may be present in the next one too, but not as important, so there is no overall narrative of continuous progress or constant improvement.

sources, the people who became part of the early industry were seen as mavericks or slightly strange characters, who could be doing well in a traditional, respectable application of computer science, but decided to take a risky jump into the games development world. On the business side of things, the success of Lemmings and some of its multiple sequels led DMA Design to *“big deals with publishers, funding a period where DMA was wildly creative, and they were willing to try ideas and genres and concepts that I think very few other studios could match”* (Scotland video games Senior Producer 1). Among other deals, DMA Design signed with Nintendo a two-game contract that came with significant investment in the company and would mean DMA Design joined Nintendo’s very small circle of external partners and had early access to the Nintendo 64 technology (Zak, 2021). In the following years, the company would go on to develop several projects at the same time for several important platforms, including a deal with *BMG* to develop games for IBM’s PC (DH002) (see Table 3). Before the establishment of the formal education route created through Abertay in 1997, DMA had already opened a pathway into the video games industry for programmers, artists, and sound designers. DMA’s deal with Nintendo included designing a game for the SNES console, which became *Unirally*, and developing a game for the Nintendo 64 console that had not been launched yet (Telegraph and Post, 1995). Similarly, the deal with Nintendo opened a scale of influence that set DMA in the elite of game companies: *“I am very excited about the material we’ve done for Nintendo; it’s getting launched at a show in Japan in November, where the machine will be shown off for the first time. I think people are going to be very impressed.... We had the man who created Super Mario, Shigeru Miyamoto, over here from Japan for a few days last month to swap some ideas and to let him see what we are doing”* (Dave Jones quoted in Evening Telegraph, 1995).

This expansion and transition to a global reach is also evident from the documentary sources, for instance, a job listing published in 1995 in the *Scotland on a Sunday* newspaper (DH001) shows how DMA Design already described themselves in the job listing as *“one of the foremost developers in the world in the video games market... we offer a unique working environment reflecting the highly creative and rewarding industry in which we lead. Cutting-edge technology and exciting projects are two features we can guarantee”* (DH001). The listing also describes the offices of the company already being located at Discovery House, Dundee Technology Park, illustrating the growth the company had experienced in the previous years since starting as a “bedroom coding” initiative. In fact, a newspaper article from April 1995 describes DMA Design having *“78 employees, which it is hoping to increase to 85 in the next six weeks”* (DH002) after the release of *Unirally* for the Super Nintendo console (for a full list of their games, see Table 3).

Table 3. Key games developed by DMA Design. Source: Wikipedia and Dailly (2006).

Year	Title	Platform	Publisher
1988	<i>Menace</i>	Amiga, Atari ST, Commodore 64, MS-DOS	Psygnosis

1989	<i>Blood Money</i>	Amiga, Atari ST, MS-DOS, Commodore 64	Psygnosis
1989	<i>Shadow of the Beast</i>	Commodore 64, PC Engine	Psygnosis
1991	<i>Lemmings</i>	3DO, Acorn Archimedes, Amiga, Amiga CD32, Amstrad CPC, Atari Lynx, Atari ST, CD-i, CDTV, Commodore 64, FM Towns, Game Boy, Game Gear, J2ME, Mac OS, Master System, Mega Drive, MS-DOS, Nintendo Entertainment System, PC-98, PC Engine, SAM Coupé, Super Nintendo Entertainment System, X68000, ZX Spectrum	Psygnosis
1993	<i>Lemmings 2: The Tribes</i>	Acorn Archimedes, Amiga, Atari ST, FM Towns, Game Boy, Mega Drive, MS-DOS, Super Nintendo Entertainment System	Psygnosis
1994	<i>Unirally</i>	Super Nintendo Entertainment System	Nintendo
1997	<i>Grand Theft Auto</i>	MS-DOS, PlayStation, Windows	BMG Interactive, ASC Games, Take-Two Interactive
1998	<i>Body Harvest</i>	Nintendo 64	Gremlin Interactive, Midway Home Entertainment
1998	<i>Space Station Silicon Valley</i>	Nintendo 64, PlayStation	Take-Two Interactive
1999	<i>Tanktics</i>	Windows	Gremlin Interactive, Interplay Entertainment
1999	<i>Wild Metal Country</i>	Dreamcast, Windows	Gremlin Interactive, Rockstar Games
1999	<i>Grand Theft Auto 2</i>	Dreamcast, PlayStation, Windows	Rockstar Games

2001	<i>Grand Theft Auto III</i>	Android, Fire OS, iOS, macOS, PlayStation 2, Windows, Xbox	Rockstar Games
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This period of expansion for DMA continued, and the company grew *“quite rapidly by that point to over 100, 120 maybe, staff, which brought a huge change of culture, and teams were struggling to get the projects finished”* (Dundee video game company Producer 2). The growth of the company experienced was also accompanied by an increasing degree of specialisation in the workforce hired for the company, as well as a more complex labour distribution, teamwork, and organisation within DMA. This was at a point in time when the talent at DMA was working in 3D graphics for the *Nintendo 64* and *PlayStation* consoles, which implied a higher degree of complexity and intensive labour. In the early days, a more general knowledge of programming, coding, or artistic interest in game development would suffice, but by this point, the company required more specialised know-how, and the job listing from 1995 previously mentioned illustrates how they were looking for software engineers with the following skills: *“be educated to degree level; be fluent in C++; produce high performance yet compact code; devise optimal algorithmic solutions; have experience of, or considerable understanding of, 3D geometry and graphics; have the ability to work closely in a team; show endless enthusiasm and imagination”* (DH001). The listing makes evident the higher degree of specialisation required from applicants, including having formal training and an official degree, making it evident that the sort of talent the company needed would require an institutional pipeline that was not fully present at that point in time (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. A photo of the DMA team taken on the 28th of May 1997 at Discovery House. Dave Jones is in the centre, and the team celebrates the wide success of their games. Source: Reproduced by permission of DC Thomson & Co Ltd, accessed through the DC Thomson Archive.

Furthermore, the impact of the early actors leading DMA Design would not only be an economic one for the whole industry, but DMA also became a sort of unofficial training school for the people working there and would shape the local talent’ approach to developing video games moving

forward: “So I think a lot of us who worked at DMA Design at that time kind of viewed it as the best video game training school that was ever invented. Although there wasn’t a lot of experience and lecturers there to guide, there was certainly a lot of creating the environment to play, pioneer, and try things out for the first time. And there was a lot of encouragement.” (Dundee video game company CEO 3)

Another factor that played into this dynamic, which we also need to highlight, is the role of the leaders of DMA Design and how their vision inspired the people working in the company who would later branch out into their own projects (see Table 4 for a list of key actors during the early years of the industry). Many of our interviewees have highlighted how the vision and wild creativity that Dave Jones engraved in the development dynamic of DMA would become a core value of Dundee’s video games scene and their own professional careers. The collective creative dynamics present in DMA Design, which did not entail the absence of conflict or managerial challenges, would fuel the industry across time: “Like Dave Jones, who ran the studio, he to this day I’d regard as a proper visionary kind of guy who just has no regard for what’s been done before. He sees things and goes after them, and he’s utterly fearless in how he does it as well. So, having that as a kind of direction from the business just encouraged everyone else in the business to do that... ..you know, you were breathing rarified air going to work every day in DMA Design, that’s for sure.” (Dundee video game company CEO 3)

Table 4. Key Actors before the “Year Zero” of the cluster.

Key Actor	Organisation	Role
David Jones	DMA Design / Real Time Worlds	Programmer/General Manager
Mike Dailly	DMA Design	Programmer/Creative
Russel Kay	DMA Design / Visual Sciences	Lead Programmer / Designer
Steve Hammond	DMA Design	Graphic Artist and Graphic conversion / Writer
Paddy Burns	VIS Entertainment / 4J Studios / Chroma Ventures	Founder/Executive/Technical Leadership
Chris Van der Kuyle	VIS Entertainment / 4J Studios / Chroma Ventures	Founder/CEO
Colin MacDonald	DMA / Games Talk Live	Producer / Games Consultant and event organiser
Colin Anderson	DMA / Denki / Reforged Studios	Audio Designer; Audio Manager; Managing Director (Denki)
Bernard King	Abertay University	Founding Principal
John Sutherland	Abertay University	Project leader for developing the Video Games portfolio at Abertay

Joyce Mathews	Scottish Enterprise	Bridge between the companies and funding opportunities, government authorities and wider industrial collaboration
Belinda Langlands	Abertay University	Project leader for developing the Computer Arts degree at Abertay

Hence, the success of DMA Design and its operating as a sort of “practical training ground” for local talent, would foster an environment where other studios could emerge, engraving certain values and preferences in the style of creative outputs of the talent working for DMA, and eventually providing access to new technologies for developers in the city. The imprint that the particular combination of pursuing a vision for something that had not been done before and at the same time creating a specific technical IP device for it, would characterise the legacy of DMA and particularly Dave Jones: *“his products tend to be based around some technical IP as well. It’s not just a vision; it’s coupled with technical IP. So, for example, when we made Crackdown, it was like, “I want to make a game where there are no limiting conditions, and you can go anywhere in the city.” So now, climbing to the tops of buildings in a streaming environment is pretty common. Back then, we were breaking new ground.”* (Dundee video game company Producer 1)

When GTA came out in 1997, DMA was cemented as a creative force, as the *“scale and the success of Grand Theft Auto was a head-turner”* (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher), for both public and private institutions at the national and international level (DH086, DH087). This global success transformed the perception of the local industry from individual efforts to a recognised sector, and in the words of one of our sources, the industry started becoming “institutional,” attracting formal support and investment from bodies like *Scottish Enterprise*. We refer to this stage in time as the *Institutionalisation period* of Dundee’s video games industry, which coincided with the emergence of a professionalisation pathway offered by Abertay University (starting in 1997), as well as a generalised growing interest in the industry surrounding the success of GTA. An interviewee who has a long-term view of the cluster in Dundee describes the process that was taking place by noting that, *“Then it became institutional, so Scottish Enterprise as an agency started to support the industry, and it became more formalised, and more investment was put in. And things started to happen around it; they had conferences, and they had exhibitions and festivals. So, the sort of cultural scaffolding around that industry started to take shape in the city and build that kind of level of sustainability and scale and volume that took it to the next level.”* (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher)

Critically, the growth and subsequent transitions within DMA Design and other early companies led to a significant diaspora of talent, resulting in the formation of new studios. This was vital in diversifying the industry and creating a sense of formalisation of game development in Dundee, as it no longer depended on one or two large companies, but on a larger number of companies with a diverse array of focus on video game development. This increasing formalisation was part of the

institutionalisation period of the industry, and it would change several features of its composition, especially the pathways through which people could enter the industry, the demands for professionalisation, and what that implied on a creative level, too. This is evident from how two of our interviewees describe the transition the industry was going through when comparing the early days with the new arrangement experienced during the institutionalisation period and after. We start with a description of how part of the creativity displayed in DMA in its early days was made possible by the loosely coupled arrangements and free flow of roles with which the company operated: *“I think the creativity came from a very loose company culture. The design team was a central resource, so they were a central resource that all of the projects could draw upon.... So, I think the company attracted and rewarded creative free thinkers. You know, it wasn’t necessarily for the people who just wanted to come in at nine, go home at five, and switch off. It was a really fabulously creative place.”* (Scotland video games Senior Producer 1)

As the industry grew in size, professionalisation expectations, diversity of types of games that were being developed, scale of the games, and the skills for 3D programming became higher; these initial arrangements changed. As teams within companies became more strictly specialised and roles became more stable, the training of talent was not taking place within the companies alone, as is evident from the fact that, in the early DMA job listings, training for video games was offered as part of the package for new trainees, but rather in the classrooms as well. This had a homogenising effect, as one of the interviewees describes as he reflects on this transition: *“I think it was, you know, part of that kind of onward march of the industry was to professionalise it to a degree...I think it does come with a kind of homogenising effect, and on-board games graduates like in a kind of similar experiences and shapes how they operate within the industry going forward. So, it certainly became a less eclectic mix of people in games studios...”* (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher).

3.3.3 Institutional support before the cluster

The strength of DMA Design’s international recognition and the growing cultural scaffolding around it, including the entrepreneurial spirit, meant that when DMA Design experienced transitions, many individuals had to go and find new paths, leading to the formation of new companies. This ethos of innovation and self-starting was further supported by institutions like Abertay University. Abertay started offering computer games development programmes in 1997 (DH108, DH115), following a long tradition of offering computer science education and incorporating it into other disciplines like Nursing and Psychology. The University played a crucial role in providing consistency that helped build respectability for the games industry and for video games as a career choice, in a time when career prospects in video games were still perceived with high social scepticism. This institutional support, combined with the efforts of public organisations, the Dundee City Council, and Scottish Enterprise, which *“aligned around about supporting this young industry”* (Dundee video game company Producer 2), transformed individual efforts into a more formalised and sustainable industry, which included not only market-oriented companies but also educational institutions and public scaffolding.

One of our interviewees describes how the vision for an interconnected ecosystem started emerging from the interactions of these key players in Dundee: *“Then obviously Abertay’s built on that narrative to kind of say, “Oh, we’ve got universities here, we’ve got graduates, and we’ve got companies,” and it almost comes to this ecosystem. You know, they were probably talking about it being an ecosystem before it actually really was officially a proper self-sustaining one. You know, they’ve had this vision for it, I suspect, and it kind of came true and worked out.”* (Dundee video game company CEO 2)

Figure 5. A photo of David Jones receiving an honorary degree from Abertay Uni in 1996, almost a decade after having left his studies at the University to pursue a full-time career as a video games developer. The picture was taken on the 15th of November 1996. The honorary degree showed not only the recognition Jones received from Abertay, but also the closeness of the relationship.

With respect to education before the emergence of the cluster, two of the main relevant sources of education were provided by *Abertay University* and the *University of Dundee*. On the side of Abertay University, our archival research identified that in 1997, the University launched the first Master’s Degree in the world that referred directly to video games in its title. This was the *MSc in Computer Games Technology* launched in September 1997 (Sutherland, 2018; addendum, 2019). In 1998, Abertay introduced the four-year *BSc (Honours) in Computer Games Technology*, which quickly gained national recognition and proved even more popular than expected among students. According to the University’s reports from that period the prospective number of students planned to be starting the course in 1998 was doubled in practice and put significant strain on the available lecturing staff: *“The requirement for further staffing investment is more sharply evident by the further increase in take of highly qualified students for the new BSc (Hons) in Computer Games and Virtual Environments. From a planned intake of 20 student numbers starting in 1998 are likely to be in excess of forty”* (McGoldrick, 1998, p. 5). The development team had intentionally set high entry standards, and reflecting the university’s strong roots in Computer Science, Mathematics was made the sole required subject for admission. As mentioned, the degree proved more popular than expected, and it was this popularity that led to the university having to invest in both talent for

lecturing purposes, and also in infrastructure to meet the technological needs of the course in mention: *“The key advantage that the University has in the area of computer games and virtual environments could be lost if staff investment are not made quickly. Indeed, the opportunity cost of not investing in the areas of real development and buoyant demand is potentially disastrous for the University. To capitalise on the greater than expected interest in the new courses, the University needs to designate and equip a suite of software development studios to industry standard.”* (McGoldrick, 1998, p. 5). The development of these degrees was possible because of the close relationship of the University with the local industry, including NCR and the local video games industry, whose biggest players back then were *DMA Design* and *Visual Sciences*. When we examined the proposal documents for the 1998 *BSc (Honours) in Computer Games Technology* degree, we found that the proposal itself contained direct references to the interest of these companies in the students who would take the degree, as well as the willingness of the companies to share their infrastructure for the training of the students (University of Abertay Dundee, 1998a). The analysis of the proposal in the light of Abertay’s history and trajectory as an educational institution also makes it clear that the video games degrees were a sort of natural progression from previous institutional focus and training offered in Software Engineering and Computer Science.

A year later, in 1999, Abertay University would develop the *BA (hons) in Computer Arts* with Belinda Langlands as Project Leader. She was an artist and designer involved in the teaching of the Computer Games Technology Degree who would influence deeply the teaching of both degrees by introducing an approach unfamiliar for traditional computer sciences and software engineering students: *“Her approach was to enable the tech/game design students to develop knowledge, understanding and consideration of the look and visual creativity around their ideas in the realisation of their games. Ideas around visual creativity and communication were introduced, as well as elements of art education such as critiquing sessions, which were new and even alien to the students at the then Maths and Computing School”* (Addendum, 2019, p. 1). This degree was also developed with strong influence from the nascent local video games industry, both their specific needs and through an interpretation of what the industry would be needing in the coming years in terms of skills and talents. The Abertay team conducted an interview with one of the key actors involved in the design and implementation of this degree, and the actor in mentioned described spending a significant amount of time in local video games companies to identify what they did in practice, how those practices could be reflected in formal education, and what skills could be added in addition to those already present. In her own words, *“Before it started, I think I spent two or three weeks in a games company to find out what they did, from an art perspective, it was DMA, when it was in Dundee. So, I spent a bit of time there figuring out what the artist’s role was, so we could design the computer arts degree.”* (Local University ex-Lecturer and Researcher)

One of the important elements highlighted by this actor in their experience at DMA Design offices was the creativity embodied in their practices, and the feeling of being part of and actively contributing to the state-of-the-art development of a new educational discipline and the nascent stages of an industry (see Figure 6). These two elements are quite clear in the description this actor shared about their time at DMA, taking inspiration for the *Computer Arts Degree*: *“Well, probably it*

was not that big compared to what it is now, but I remember it had a sound department, and it was like a garage area, and they were making all these noises, kind of physically, that was pretty cool. ...But it was very exciting. It felt very like a kind of new area that was being explored, and it was happening in Dundee." (Local University ex-Lecturer and Researcher). Through the development of the *Computer Arts Degree*, and the inclusion of artistic and design principles in the other degrees from Abertay's video games development portfolio, Abertay would influence not only the educational pathway into the industry, but also influence the industry itself and the development of video games. Abertay achieved this by integrating a wider range of abilities and aesthetic sensibilities that were not present in the earlier days when the technical challenge and technically-minded curiosity drove the development of video games. This contribution is described as follows by one of our interviewees: *"There just seemed to be, there was this massive gap in considering anything aesthetic in the development of games."* (Local University ex-Lecturer and Researcher)

Figure 6. A photo taken in 1999 at Abertay University showing David Jones (corner left) and Chris Van der Kuyle (right corner) surrounded by a group of students and lecturers from the Abertay video games degrees.

Overall, the approach developed across the three degrees, which combined the technical and artistic dimensions of game development, replicating the team dynamics that took place in the video games studios in practice, was innovative for Abertay, for Dundee, and for the UK as a whole. In fact, it would have a long-lasting influence on the way video games-focused degrees were developed internationally till the present day. In the words of one of the designers and founding members of the *MSc in Computer Games Technology*: *"the Abertay degree stands out as a genuine innovation which broke new ground and set the direction of travel for today's hundreds of study programs in many countries"* (Sutherland, 2018, p. 151). One of the critical points to take from this history is how the development of the video games portfolio at Abertay was influenced by representatives and ex-members of the local video games industry, as Professor Sutherland who was involved in the process explained: *"Abertay University asked me to head up the development of a video games development degree portfolio, together with Professor Iain Marshall, Professor Peter Astheimer and Dr James TerKeurst... This team was supplemented by local computer games industry*

representatives and national 3D graphics developers led by David Jones.” (Sutherland, 2018, p. 150). The possibility of this direct influence taking place is cemented in the history of Abertay as an institution, and its orientation since day one, back in 1888, to coevolving hand in hand with the local industry. In the minutes of the senate of Abertay University back in October 1996, we can see that the University is described as a “modern industrial university” and a “provider of vocationally relevant higher education” (Abertay University, 1996, p2); an institution that ensures that its courses remain relevant, secure employability for students, and maintains a close connection with the local industry and community. In this document, the mission of the University and its projected evolution in the coming years was defined as “emphasis on the needs of industry, locally, nationally, and internationally”, while also “fostering creativity, enterprise and vision” in order to “produce graduates who are at the backbone of industry” (Abertay University, 1996, p.4). As Abertay had historically done, the institution was adapting to the transforming landscape of the local industry and was paying focused attention to the developments in the field of video game development.

We can also highlight how Abertay, since its inception, was connected to local industry, and those connections evolved as the industrial composition of the city changed over time. At its inception, the Technical Institute was funded by local business owners and industrialists, involved in the jute industry, among other economic activities. In fact, in the 1980’s textile firms donated textile machines to the institute’s textiles department so the students could develop the skills that would prepare them to join the industry upon finalising their studies. Furthermore, before WWI, jute companies located in the British Imperial territories in Calcutta, India, eagerly recruited managers who had been trained at Dundee Technical Institute (Abertay University, n.d). As the industry in Dundee tended towards electronics, manufacturing, and other assembling industries like Levi’s, NCR, Timex, etc., the offered training also diversified: *“In 1956, we offered degree courses for the first time. Changes in business and industry after the Second World War meant new courses were developed, such as production engineering, computing, business, and management. Advances in science in the 1950s to 1980s led to new disciplines emerging, and new courses were developed to meet the needs of these growing industries, such as nursing and computing studies.”* (Abertay University, n.d, p. 1). To pinpoint one case of this direct collaboration and influence, we have found evidence that Mr. David Jones, founder of DMA Design, was part of the validation committee for the *BSc (Hons) in Computer Games Technology*, launched in 1998. As part of the validation committee, he revised the original proposal, commented on specific themes, topics, and skills covered in the proposed degree, engaged in critical conversation with the development teams, and ended up supporting the approval of the degree, commending its innovativeness and the effort to put it together (University of Abertay Dundee, 1998b).

Table 5. The historical evolution of Abertay University as an institution and its connections with local industry. Source: Abertay University Archives.

Year	Event	Name
1872	Sir David Baxter, a textile industrialist from Dundee, leaves a legacy with the objective of founding a Mechanics Institute.	/
1888	The Dundee Technical Institute was founded and opened on 15 October 1888, occupying the Technical Institute building on Smalls Wynd in the grounds of University College Dundee (nowadays University of Dundee).	Dundee Technical Institute
1911	The Technical Institute relocates to newly built premises in Bell Street and is renamed in the process.	Dundee Technical College and School of Art
1933	After the passage of the Educational Endowments Scotland Act in 1928, the Dundee Technical College and School of Art endowment was combined with the Duncan of Jordanstone bequest (granted in 1909 by Mr. James Duncan of Jordanstone), and the Dundee Institute of Art and Technology was constituted as a single central organisation containing two committees of governors (one for the College of Technology, and one for the Art College).	Dundee Institute of Art and Technology
1955	The College of Art relocates to new premises at Perth Road, and is renamed Duncan of Jordanstone College of Art. The College of Technology remains at the Bell Street site.	Dundee Institute of Art and Technology
1975	Dundee Institute of Art and Technology is formally dissolved. The Dundee College of Technology and the Duncan of Jordanstone College of Art were formally designated as separate institutions.	The Dundee College of Technology
1988	The Dundee College of Technology expands, and it is renamed the Dundee Institute of Technology	Dundee Institute of Technology
1994	The Privy Council agrees that the institution could adopt a University title, and on 17th of August 1994, the University was formally established as the University of Abertay Dundee	University of Abertay Dundee
2019	The institution decides to simplify the name, differentiate more clearly from the University of Dundee, and adopt "Abertay University."	Abertay University

Interestingly, this combination of artistic and technical expertise and practices around computers and arts was not only taking place in Abertay University. The University of Dundee's *Duncan of Jordanston College of Art and Design* (DJCAD) had, during the 1980s, assembled a degree that drew on creative computing and would be highly relevant to the training and education offered in the city: the degree was the *Postgraduate Diploma in Electronic Imaging*. This degree was launched in 1986, and it is widely considered a pioneer in the UK in terms of its specific combination of “*art, technology and commerce*” (University of Dundee, 1999, p. 4), being considered also, as Abertay's portfolio of computer games degrees, pathbreaking in its own terms and disciplines of interest. For this historical report, the Abertay team interviewed one of the founding members and designers of the programme, who combined in his professional career training in Fine Arts with an incremental engagement with computing, artificial intelligence, and multiple technologies used for imaging and broadcasting.⁶

The programme would later be offered also as MSc in Electronic Imaging, starting in 2000, and being described as “*the Master's in Science in Electronic Imaging Programme brings together art, design and science, through the combinations of research into technology, ideas, culture and creativity. It is predicated upon the idea of producing challenging and creative skilled practitioners.*” (DJCAD, 2000, p. 3) By the late 1990's University of Dundee was also offering the BDse (Hons) in Animation & Electronic Media, which was described in 2000 as “*the only full-time animation programme in the UK that offers students the creative challenge, training and skills in both traditional and computer animation*” (DJCAD, 2000, p. 2) and “*computer games design, digital simulation and virtual environments*” are all described as areas of opportunity for creative animators.

Importantly, students from these degrees offered by DJCAD would find their way into the video games industry in Dundee, Scotland, and beyond. A particular case of interest is that of *Aaron Garbut*, who would join DMA Design in 1996 as an artist and would later become head of Development of Rockstar North, playing a key role in the development of the GTA Franchise across time, being named Art Director from GTA 3 onwards. Garbut currently co-leads Rockstar North.

3.4 Determining factors in the history of the cluster

3.4.1 Historical circumstances and events surrounding the local industry

The period previous to the Year Zero was shaped by Dundee's socio-economic context of the late 20th century. Then, the city was navigating a challenging socio-economic landscape, characterised by a significant post-industrial decline, “*So, after manufacturing started to decline, Dundee was quite a difficult place to be for career opportunities, employment opportunities.*” (Dundee-based University Lecturer and Researcher) The video games industry emerged in this context and became a potential line of work for new generations in a way that would have been impossible to foresee a decade before. As one of our interviewees, who has been in Dundee since the beginning stated, the video games industry in the 1990s was gaining momentum and in a context of deindustrialisation

⁶ An overview of his work is available here: <https://www.nigel-johnson.com/projects>.

this felt like a lifeline towards a different but also technically-minded economic future: *“I think the fact that DMA was here, and DMA were successful – like very successful – and then Chris van der Kuyle started VIS, and VIS became successful as well. We ended up with a very small city with two relatively big game companies, you know, a hundred plus staff.”* (Dundee video game company CEO 2)

On the technological and technical side of things, the early success of DMA and VIS would also open the door for the local industry to gain early access to technologies that were being developed, allowing creators to work on the frontier of both video games technology as well as the experiential side of video games: *“And then they gave people access to stuff they wouldn’t be able to get access to, so the consoles... Nintendo came over to visit, so obviously, Dave managed to get Nintendo interested because of Lemmings, and so we were getting access to this new technology. And then the PS1 came out, and it was the same with VIS. They had early kits for like PS2s and all the rest of it. ...I think that kept the staff interested. And we were all working on the latest tech, and working on the latest thing, and working on the latest game...”* (Dundee video game company CEO 2)

This also implied that the talent working at these companies would have developed state-of-the-art skills and knowledge that they would take with them through their careers, even when the companies they were working for at that point in time went under or were bought by an international conglomerate. This meant that the know-how was sedimenting in the talent of the city and would make it possible that even when the companies disappeared the local industry would not lose that know-how, and would be able to sustain it over time and diversify it: *“those companies unfortunately, go boom or bust, people there are able to take those skills elsewhere, skills they wouldn’t have got.”* (Dundee video game company CEO 2)

One of the key transformations in the industry was the creation, distribution, and popularity of the 3D animation capabilities of the *PlayStation* and *Nintendo 64*. The intricacies and levels of complexity of 3D animation would not only intensify the work that had to be done in studios to assemble games for these consoles, but it would also open the door into the industry for people taking formal channels of training, such as computer arts training at Abertay.

3.4.2 Exogenous factors and the role of neighbouring industries

From the postwar period through to the 1980s, Dundee’s industrial landscape was partly sustained by new employment opportunities created through regional policy and the attraction of multinational manufacturers such as NCR, Michelin, Levi’s, and Timex (DH90, DH91, DH104). The city benefited from government incentives that encouraged these firms to expand locally, offsetting job losses in declining sectors like jute. This approach, grounded in the *Distribution of Industry Act* (1945), reflected a broader policy effort to stabilise employment in areas facing structural decline, which proved effective in Dundee at least for the first couple of decades. These incoming industries provided higher wages and improved working conditions, prompting many Dundee workers, particularly women, to leave the traditional jute mills for cleaner and better-paid factory jobs (Tomlinson, Phillips & Wright, 2019).

NCR Corporation (commonly known as NCR) established its presence in Dundee shortly after the Second World War as part of governmental efforts to attract international investment and industrial manufacturing into many UK cities (DH102). This happened in the context of spreading waves of deindustrialisation across the UK, which in Dundee was expressed prominently through the slow decline in jute production, which had been the heart and soul of the local industry for the previous century. This is evident in the sharp decrease in the number of people employed in Jute during the 1940s onwards. According to its own official annual report, NCR was one of the first US-based companies to manufacture its products internationally. In the years leading to WWII, Timex had already had three factories outside of the US, and by 1970, that number had grown 400%, reaching 12 factories internationally, including several located in Dundee (NCR, 1970). NCR's Camperdown factory was officially inaugurated on 11 June 1947, and the facility grew rapidly, eventually becoming one of the city's major employers, peaking at over 6,000 staff by the early 1970s (Tomlinson, Phillips & Wright, 2019). Initially, manufacturing cash registers and accounting machines, the company shifted its focus in the 1960s and onward to electronic systems and automated teller machines (ATMs), with much of the design, engineering, and production being based in Dundee (see Figure 8). The city's Chamber of Commerce describes, *"It was here that NCR's first ever ATM was designed and built over 40 years ago, and millions of machines have since been shipped from Dundee and other NCR locations to financial institutions all across the world."* (Dundee & Angus Chamber of Commerce, 2017).

Importantly, as NCR expanded its commercial horizons, it also started manufacturing computers, and the Dundee plant was involved in the production of the Century Series family of computers from 1968 onwards (NCR, 1970). These computers were business-oriented, and a significant amount of the commercial benefits of the computer were made through renting it to businesses, as the costs involved in buying one were still very high, and they required significant space (Datapro, 1970). Connected to the manufacturing of these machines and the incremental interest of NCR in digital technologies, the company established the Scottish Computer Lab in Dundee. However, the impact of NCR in Dundee went beyond industrial employment: it helped establish the city as a centre of advanced manufacturing and technology, at a time when the local jute and ship-repair industries were in decline (The Courier, 2022).

Figure 7. A photo of a Dundonian woman working at NCR, assembling an electronic board. The picture was taken on the 28th of August 1996.

The factory's transformation from mechanical devices to electronics and ATM development required high-skill engineering, software design, and international export experience, which was ingrained into the local workforce. Over time, NCR in Dundee manufactured a great amount of machinery and increasingly sophisticated electronic equipment, with the 5070 ATM model becoming its most famous local invention, a product that would become NCR's biggest-selling product worldwide (The Courier, 2021). NCR became part of AT&T in 1991, in an operation worth 7.4 billion USD, and in 2009, the company manufactured its last ATM in Dundee, and ceased manufacturing activities fully in 2012. Nowadays, it maintains an important R&D facility in the city (see Figure 8). A key point worth mentioning is that one of the biggest names in game development in Dundee, Chris Van der Kuyle, had a summer job at NCR in Dundee in his early youth, pursuing an interest in multimedia technology (Chris Van der Kuyle, Dundee University Interview, 2016).

Figure 8. A photo of the workers at NCR Dundee receiving the “flag of excellence” after celebrating having manufactured the 50,000th ATM. The picture was taken on the 8th of July 1988.

According to his account of that time, it was at NCR that the sparkle of technical creativity around computers that would characterise his whole career was nurtured. His time at NCR allowed him to

meet similarly minded people, in a time when computer talk around Dundee was uncommon, and through NCR, he was even able to travel to California, to Silicon Valley, where he continued to develop his interest in computers and learnt about the potentialities of software development as a business (Dundee University Archive, 2022). In an oral history interview, he describes the significance of his experience at NCR and travelling to Silicon Valley as follows: *“Two things happened to me in Silicon Valley. One thing was, I met loads of great people but didn’t think any of them were any smarter than any of the people I knew in Scotland. [...] They just have a critical mass and have got access to things. Why can’t we do that in Scotland? And that’s been a guiding principle for me ever since. But the other thing was I landed in a place where it wasn’t weird to only want to talk about computers and technology. [...] But even in NCR, most of those guys were mechanical engineers of hardware and things like that. Software was still kind of a weird thing.”* (Chris Van der Kuyle, Dundee University Interview, 2016).

It is interesting to note how two of the biggest foundational actors of Dundee’s video game ecosystem were connected to the two biggest companies in Dundee in the last 75 years. David Jones worked at Timex, and Chris Van der Kuyle had a summer job at NCR that would shape his future.

3.4.3 Role of other/proto industries concerning the current cluster

Video games represent the earliest form of gaming to emerge directly from developments in information technology, as in most clusters that emerged during the 1980s, Dundee too has had to adapt over time to these waves of change and also shape this evolving landscape through its productions. Over the years, local developers have been required to adapt to successive shifts in hardware architectures and digital infrastructures, spanning platforms such as arcade systems, personal computers, online environments, specialised gaming consoles, and mobile devices, including smartphones and tablets (Tsang, 2021). Historically, one of the first incarnations of publicly available video games-related expressions was arcade machines, pinball machines, and similar amusement machines that became common across the UK during the 1970s onwards. The few sources concerning arcade cabinets, arcade games, pinball machines, and jukeboxes in Dundee itself signal that there was a local manufacturer of *“gaming machines”* under the name *Bordermatics LTD*, who supplied all sorts of equipment to local clubs, pubs, hotels, and local arcade stores. This equipment included gaming machines, jukeboxes, pool tables, and video interactive equipment (Retro Dundee, 2011). There is also evidence of a multiplicity of *“video game arcades”* having existed across the city, with *Hynd Bros Entertainment*, which was located in the centre of town, being particularly popular and operating throughout the 1970s and 1980s (Retro Dundee, 2011).

The Abertay team located a source in the *Dundee University Archive* that summarised the applications filed between 1983 and 1991 to the Dundee City Council concerning amusement arcades in the city. These were concerned with *“change of use, renewal or deletion of imposed conditions pertaining to Amusement arcades”* (Dundee City Council, 1990, p. 1) from different individuals and companies who wanted to build, expand, or readapt amusement arcade businesses across different areas of the city. It is quite interesting to note that the document describes 22

applications being submitted in that period, and only 4 of them were approved, with several of them being appealed afterwards. This evidence signals that there was a market and demand in Dundee for amusement arcades, even when the authorities at the time were actively trying to limit the number of them across the city, even when there was a growing recognition that *“it has to be recognised that new forms of leisure facilities such as amusement arcades are serious forms of commercial enterprise, which need to be satisfactorily accommodated”* (Dundee City Council, 1990, p. 3).

Another key point to note is that one of the historical sources (Stewart, 2017) describes Dave Jones and his colleagues deciding to start DMA Design, inspired by their escapades to Dundee’s Arcades. There, they would be able to try several games, experiment with multiple gameplay styles, and get inspiration for their own projects. Mike Dailly recalls the inspiration they took from their arcade passion: *“Steve, Dave, and I were all avid arcade players, and the current games of choice in our local arcade were Alien Syndrome, Quartet, and Mr. Heli. Dave loved the cuteness of Mr. Heli, and the scrolling system it used, and so this became the inspiration of Blood Money.”* (Dailly, 2021c) Dailly also recounts having used one of the local arcades, the one located in Reform Street, as a resource for some of the sound recordings required for their very early games: *“Proto-Menace naturally needed sound effects to complement the graphics... we went to the arcade in Dundee’s Reform Street armed with a tape recorder. Steve and I played the game, and with Dave nonchalantly leaning on the unit and holding the microphone discreetly to the cabinet’s speaker...”* (Dailly, 2021b). Overall, there was a significant impact of arcades on the Dundonian games development scene.

Additionally, there is a relevant UK-wide history related to these elements that may prove useful for understanding the dynamics of video games in Scotland and Dundee itself, predating the rise of the video games industry. Historically, the UK has had a privileged position in terms of both arcade equipment production and arcade games development. Concerning the technologies themselves, early manufacturing in the UK focused on mechanical and electromechanical devices, such as the Pintable and the bagatelle-style Pickwick machine,⁷ which implemented elements of skill to circumvent the governing gambling laws. Key British manufacturers, such as *Alf Crompton (Amusements) Ltd.*, built a reputation for innovation, producing large, multiplayer games like the *Derby Racer*. Arcade game content followed global trends, echoing the *Pong* wave of the early 1970s and the popularity of Taito’s *Space Invaders* later that same decade. This wave was characterised by microprocessors and Printed Circuit Boards (PCBs), which could be bought in Japan and fitted into arcade cabinets in the UK. This made games easier to copy by duplicating code on chips, and across the UK and Europe more generally, this led to a huge volume of clones and conversion kits being created by companies like *Competitive Video*, capitalising on the legal ambiguity surrounding video game copyright. This situation drastically changed with the 1982 *Sega versus Trolfame* legal case, which clarified that copyright applied to game code too (Meades, 2022). While video game arcades from the start experienced a fast-paced changing tide, which would characterise the industry across time, the strong investment in home computers, influenced by initiatives like the

⁷ See <https://www.arcade-museum.com/Slot-Machine/improved-pickwick--pessers--1914--3036>.

effectiveness of the BBC Micro promotional and educational campaign in the early 1980s (Blyth, 2012), meant Britain was notably slower to adopt Japanese home videogame consoles compared to other markets. The preference for home computing in Britain shaped the country's relationship with arcade games: while arcade machines offered superior graphical capabilities and processing power, home computers provided different, often deeper and more intimate play experiences (Meades, 2022).

These home computers allowed for arcade clones and copies to be adapted and played in them, and thus cemented the British love for home computing. In the words of one of Dundee's long-lasting video game developers, CEO of the studio *Cobra*, who took part in the arcade and ZX Spectrum scene in Dundee: *"There was a plethora of games you could play from the arcade, but there were also original games... If you came from a background that didn't have a lot of money you could take a tape and copy a game. Copying became a fine art, because you had to have two tape decks wired and cabled in a particular way."* (Mark Eittle in Ogston & Goodwin, 2024). This led to a symbiotic, rather than oppositional, relationship with arcades, where home versions (often of variable quality) were often seen as subordinate to the dominant arcade experience, but were crucial in building public interest, arcade audiences and familiarising young audiences with programming; *"The Spectrum opened up a world of dabbling in computer programming and very basic graphics"* (Mark Eittle, in Ogston & Goodwin, 2024). It must be said that the home versions were supplementing the arcade, rather than replacing it completely. The British home system market was heavily skewed towards computers such as the ZX Spectrum and Commodore 64 well into the early 1990s. The Dundee-made ZX Spectrum was a dominant force in the British home computing market. The sources estimate that between 5 and 6 million ZX Spectrum computers were sold (see Figure 9), with the majority of these sales occurring in Britain alone (Danton, 2021).

Figure 9. A photo of Clive Sinclair, inventor of the Spectrum computers and owner of Sinclair Research, being handed a special edition of the ZX Spectrum in the Timex factory of Dundee. The picture was taken on the 9th of December 1983, and it also shows the predominantly female gendered workforce that characterised the factory. Sinclair and the Spectrum computers are widely credited as major forces in making home computing popular and massively accessible in the UK and Europe.

Among the important effects of this dynamic on the Dundee video games industry, the emergence of DMA Design would not have been possible without it. Mike Dailly, one of the founding figures of DMA Design, recalls, *“The whole of the original DMA Design pretty much started on the Spectrum. That kick-started DMA and the whole of the Dundee industry. So, the whole of the gaming route comes from the Spectrum.”* (Mike Dailly, cited in Ogston & Goodwin, 2024)

Interestingly, the Spectrum as a technology itself had a low threshold for people who were interested in learning to play with it beyond using it to run specific games. Building on initiatives like the BBC Micro, the Spectrum was designed to promote the development of skills beyond mere passive consumption. A testament of this is how the Manual that came with the computer illustrated in detail how users could learn to program in it and create their own little games or programs (DH120, DH119). It is important to mention that the ZX Spectrum and other home computers were also nested within a larger assemblage of technologies, including optional add-ons for the computer, like printing mechanisms, joystick interfaces, or additional memory. Other elements that compounded this assemblage were Spectrum-devoted magazines where a multitude of people shared their knowledge and creations, and computer clubs distributed all across the UK, where people would physically meet to share, learn, compete, and compare. In the McManus Collections Archive in Dundee, we were able to find and read a number of these documents, including an original ZX Spectrum Manual, Home Computer-focused and Spectrum-focused Magazines, and an original ZX Spectrum that was once owned by one of DMA Design’s founders (DH116, DH117, DH118, DH119, DH120, DH121).

3.4.4 Factors that influenced the birth and development of local industry

Interestingly, on the regulatory institutional side of things, during the early 80s, video games were barely appearing on the horizon of policy actors; in fact, one of our sources details that before 1984, the word video games itself did not appear in any statute form: *“U.K. video game policy before the 1980s was simple: There was none. While video games certainly existed before 1980 in both arcades and homes, the term ‘video game’ did not appear in parliamentary records until 1981 and was absent from statute until 1984.”* (Reynolds, 2015, p. 113). This is fascinating when contrasted with the growing public attention, during that same decade, towards home computing and the interest in positioning the UK in the global computing market as both a nation of computer-wise people and an economic powerhouse in terms of computers’ design, development, and manufacturing (Danton, 2021).

It is quite interesting to note that the early video games industry in Dundee emerged during the late 1980s within a policy landscape that was still nascent, with policy actors just starting to become interested in both regulating video games intensively and recognising video games themselves as a potentially significant source of economic gains for the national economy. However, as mentioned above, the social context in the UK regarding the promotion and appreciation of computer literacy was far richer, and a fundamental initiative in this respect was the *BBC Micro*. The *BBC Micro* became a cornerstone of the BBC’s *Computer Literacy Project* (CLP), launched in 1982 in response to growing

anxieties that Britain risked falling behind in the microelectronics revolution. The diagnosis generated by the BBC itself was that *“in 1978/1979 the UK seemed woefully unprepared for the ‘new technology’. In business and industry, the silicon chip was changing ways of working, threatening many jobs and making the UK uncompetitive.”* (BBC, n.d.) As a response, the BBC created the CLP and insisted on the need for UK citizens to learn about computers through a deep knowledge of the technology that could allow them not only to use them passively, but also to understand how they operated and use them creatively. As a result, in 1981, the BBC sought a partner to produce a computer that could be used in its accompanying television series *The Computer Programme* and in schools across the UK. Several companies submitted proposals, but *Acorn Computers* won the commission due to the superior capabilities and expandability of its prototype, the *Acorn Proton* (BBC, n.d.). The resulting machine, officially released as the BBC Microcomputer System (or BBC Micro), became one of the most influential educational computers of its era, widely adopted in schools and instrumental in introducing a generation to programming and computer science (Selwyn, 2002). Through a combination of broadcast television programmes, books, and hands-on experiences with the BBC Micro, the CLP sought to ensure that UK citizens, especially young generations, were not merely passive consumers of new technology but could engage directly with programming and digital literacy (Blyth, 2012).

The BBC Micro’s robustness, expandability, and the inclusion of a tailored programming language, the BBC BASIC (Beginner’s All-purpose Symbolic Instruction Code), made it particularly suited to education, and by the mid-1980s it dominated British classrooms, with Acorn claiming up to 85% of the educational computing market in schools (BBC, n.d.). The reach of the programme far surpassed the initial expectations, and its popularity transcended the direct influence of the BBC: *“the mass appeal of the machine came first and foremost because of the popularity of the various CLP television series. Individual programmes had audiences between 500,000 and 1.2 million late night on BBC One, and the CLP reached 16 per cent of the adult population through one programme or another. The BBC Micro - originally developed to support learning through the TV programmes - quickly became a phenomenon beyond the BBC, and was picked up by national newspapers, new computing magazines and software development companies”* (Blyth, 2012, p. 18).

In Scotland, the uptake of the BBC Micro mirrored wider UK trends but with distinctive local dynamics. Regional education boards, further education colleges, and community education centres integrated the machine into teaching, supported by the BBC’s nationally broadcast content (Gazzard, 2024). The adaptability of the BBC Micro, especially its peripheral support and capacity for laboratory or design applications, helped Scottish institutions tailor its use to local contexts, further embedding computing into everyday educational practices (Gazzard, 2024). In fact, the application of the programme in Scotland was accompanied by referral services that provided specialised support and help build local networks of knowledge sharing as one of sources explains: *“this led to the creation of a referral service through the Broadcasting Support Services (BSS) (and its sister organisations, Network in Scotland and the Educational Guidance Service for Adults in Northern Ireland) which acted as a central information point for the CLP on software, on the computer and on the television programmes, and also put viewers in touch with local classes and*

clubs. Crucially, these bodies identified people and organisations that could become part of a bigger network of local sources of help and advice.” (Blyth, 2012, p. 17). With respect to Dundee, Gazzard notes that the city illustrates the longer-term cultural and industrial impact of this educational foundation (2024). The BBC Micro was used not only in Dundee’s schools but also in community learning contexts, influencing a generation of young programmers who experimented with code, graphics, and games. This grassroots computing culture contributed directly to the rise of Dundee’s games industry in the late 1980s and 1990s, most famously through DMA Design.

3.5 Detailed historical timeline before the birth of the cluster and continuity factors

3.5.1 ‘New’ historical timeline

Table 6. Key periods in the history of the cluster.

Period name	Years	Main Characteristics
Foundational period	1987-1996	The first companies appeared based on the computer clubs and the growing interest in video games. DMA Design is the first company, develop games as Menace and Blood Money, which allowed gathering funds and legitimacy, while international success arrived with Lemmings.
Institutionalisation period	1997-2009	DMA Design has consolidated, and VIS is now also part of the landscape. GTA achieves great commercial success, and Dundee becomes a spotlight in the international scene. Institutional support is granted to the industry through Scottish Enterprise, and Abertay University further institutionalises the industry by providing a professional and educational pathway into it. Several spinoffs appear from the initial companies, and new studios are formed, too.
Clustering Period (Includes “Year Zero”)	2010-2020	Real Time Worlds collapses, and the industry can withstand the effects; the cluster emerges. The industry is now more widely diversified, encompassing console, pc, and mobile games. Startups from Abertay are starting to stabilise and become important players. There is wider open communication between studios, and collectives like Biome play an increasingly important role. Big-money games with external funding are no longer the ideal model.

Ecosystemic push period	2021-present	<p>Research is now applied to the cluster by players in the cluster itself. The cluster has a diversity of companies and collectives, from different sizes and a variety of business models.</p> <p>Attempts to bridge with fellow creative industries appear. Incipient formal organisational attempts appear, too. Video game actors who have accumulated resources from this business start investing in the cluster and in other economic activities too (Chroma Ventures from Chris Van der Kuyle, UMBRA by Marc Williamson, and David Hamilton from Ninja Kiwi, too).</p>
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3.5.2 Continuity factors between before and after the cluster

The main continuity factors for the cluster can be divided into three groups: people from the initial generation of game developers who were part of the original companies (DMA Design, VIS, Visual Sciences); Institutions themselves that have withstood the passage of time and the multiplicity of sociotechnical changes the cluster has gone through; and, the DNA of the cluster understood as certain skills, values and specific approaches to games development that have been sustained over time.

In Table 7, there is a synthesis of the trajectory of some of the key people who were present in the early days and were present after the year zero of the cluster. Noting their trajectories, it becomes evident that even when specific companies or projects may end up closing or disappearing, some of the key people in the local industry have remained connected across time, and their contributions have continued to take different shapes as the cluster changes. It is worth mentioning that the continuity of these actors has both strengths and limitations. On the side of the strengths, their continuity has allowed the local industry to draw on their expertise, visibility, recognition, and networks over time. As the table portrays, several of these actors are still involved in highly relevant initiatives for the local cluster, ranging from networking and knowledge sharing events like Games Talks Live, leading the Scottish Games Network, running local studios, investing in other local studios and local IP through ventures such as Chroma Ventures, sharing expertise formally and informally, among other activities. On the side of the limitations, the presence of these actors may also make it harder for more recent talent and ventures to be visible, as the older generation group may capture more of the public’s attention and be invited to speak to represent the cluster.

Table 7. Key actors and their trajectory before and after the cluster emerged.

Key Actor	Original organisation	Changes over time	Present day role
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David Jones	DMA Design	Denki; Realtime Worlds (founder); Cloudgine (co-founder); Reagent Games	Naemair Ltd - consulting (games/tech)
Mike Dailly	DMA Design	Visual Science; YoYo Games (Head of Dev); Sumo Digital	Principal Programmer at Sumo Digital; runs Ogre Games in Dundee
Russel Kay	DMA Design	Visual Science (founder); RealTime Worlds; YoYo Games	Director at Opera Software – Head of Game Maker
Paddy Burns	VIS	VIS Entertainment; 4J Studios (co-founder); Chroma Ventures (principal)	4J Studios / Chroma Ventures
Chris Van der Kuyle	VIS	VIS Entertainment (co-founder/CEO); 4J Studios (chairman); Chroma Ventures (co-founder)	4J Studios / Chroma Ventures
Colin MacDonald	DMA Design	Rage; RealTime Worlds (Studio Manager); eeGeo; Channel 4; Games Talks Live (organiser); UK Games Talent and Finance Community Interest Company; Games Jobs Live (Director)	Games Talk Live (organiser)/ UK Games Talent and Finance Community Interest Company (Board Member)/ Games Jobs Live (Director)
Colin Anderson	DMA Design	Gremlin Interactive; Rockstar Games; Denki (founder); UK Games Talent and Finance Community Interest Company	Reforged Studios / Scottish Government Creative Industries Leadership Group (Video Games Representative member)
Brian Baglow	DMA Design	Rockstar Games; I Play; Indoctrimat; Denki; Bafta Scotland; Scottish Games Network (founder)	Scottish Games Network (founder)
Gary Penn	DMA Design	Rockstar; Denki Ltd	Head of Development / Product Architect at Denki
Mark Ettle	DMA Design	Visual Science; Simian Industries; Cobra Mobile (founder)	CEO / Managing Director at Cobra Mobile

Frank Arnott	DMA Design	Codemasters; Visual Science; VIS Entertainment (Lead game designer); 4J Studios (Studio Director); Stormcloud Games (founder/MD)	Founder and Managing Director at Stormcloud Games
Ken Fee	DMA Design	Visual Science; Abertay University (Senior lecturer)	Senior Lecturer & Programme Tutor at Abertay University
Paul Farley	DMA Design	VIS Entertainment; I-Play (Head of Design); Tag Games (founder, later acquired by Scopely); ChilliConnect (acquired by Unity3D)	CEO / Founder at Firestroke Games
Aaron Garbut	DMA Design	Rockstar North	Co-Studio Head / Head of Development at Rockstar North
Billy Thomson	DMA Design	Rage (Scotland) Senior Designer; Realtime Worlds Lead Designer (Crackdown); Ruffian Games (co-founder / Creative Director) then acquired and renamed Rockstar Dundee	Co-Studio Director / Studio Design Director at Rockstar Dundee

A potential way of identifying characteristics of a given gaming cluster is to trace the story of key developers within it and how their careers have progressed. One such example in Dundee's case would be David Jones, most notably for founding DMA Design. Jones also played a key role in opening the formal education pathway into the industry in Abertay, was involved in the opening of significant new companies over time (*Denki*, *RealTime Worlds*, *Reagent*), played a crucial role in developing some of the most internationally recognised games developed in Dundee (*Crackdown*, *GTA*, *Lemmings*), is considered a visionary for the local industry who established the creative/technical orientation that would characterise DMA Design and many of the people who worked there, and who is until present day the most recognisable face from the Dundee video games industry. Reflecting this diversity of roles, Jones has been referred to through a multiplicity of names including but not limited to: "Ex-Timex tycoon" (The Herald, 1995), "the Steven Spielberg of the computer games industry" (Press & Journal, 1995), "Scotland's Bill Gates" (Press & Journal, 1995), "Game boy Millionaire" (Fraser, 1997), "Computer Wizard" (Findlay, 1997), "Games Genius" (Simpson, 1997). All these names bring to the fore the status of "local legend" that Jones has harvested, and how his figure would become a sort of mythological father for the whole Dundee video games industry. The representations of Jones in the media have almost always been positive, even when specific games like GTA were openly criticised; the same was not the case with him as a figure (DH014, DH006, DH002, DH131).

On the side of institutions, several organisations have shaped the continuity of the cluster, with Abertay University being a key node in this respect, both enduring as an organisation while also integrating part of the expertise and experience of the cluster in its portfolio of games development degrees, as well as in the lecturers who work for the University. Video game companies have also provided this stability with long-term companies such as 4J Studios, Denki Games, TAG Games, and Cobra Mobile (recently closed), among others. Henderson and Loggie, an accountability firm that has developed a specialisation in Video Game companies, is also a key long-term player, which has witnessed many companies come and go.

3.6 Conclusions

The historical trajectory of Dundee’s video games industry indicates that what made it possible and successful in this region was an interplay among local socio-economic transformations, international sociotechnological shifts, and appropriate institutional scaffolding from both educational institutions and focalised public efforts like Scottish Enterprise. From its roots in the city’s post-industrial context and the ZX Spectrum era to the emergence of DMA Design as a creative nucleus, Dundee’s industry is nested within the manufacturing legacy of the city, as well as in the development of computing literacy supported by public programmes. These factors enabled the emergence of a collaborative network of people, practices, and technologies both in private companies as well as in educational institutions. The foundational and institutionalisation periods were marked by pioneering creativity, informal knowledge exchange, and the gradual formalisation of educational pathways, which then provided a sustainable talent pipeline and legitimised video games as a professional career. These dynamics were reinforced by the city’s capacity to absorb technological change and maintain continuity through key actors and organisations, even amid structural challenges.

The industry’s resilience became evident during the “Year Zero” of the cluster, when the collapse of Real Time Worlds tested the video games community’s diversification and adaptability. Rather than signalling absolute decline, this disruption catalysed a new wave of entrepreneurial activity, fostering smaller studios and collectives that embraced collaborative practices and alternative business models. This was also possible due to the international appearance of the mobile games market, and graduates from local educational institutions starting to form and consolidate their own startups. Today, Dundee’s ecosystem reflects both the legacy of its early innovators and the pressures of global competition, combining strong educational infrastructure expressed nowadays through R&D projects on top of traditional degrees, and the creative orientation of the cluster, with persistent challenges in funding, infrastructure, renovating its public narrative, and enhancing international visibility.

4 THE TURIN CLUSTER

4.1 Introduction and methodology

The history of Turin's video game production cluster began on uncertain grounds. Because this deliverable followed two previous tasks – T4.1 “Primary Data Collection” and T4.2 “Document Analysis” – both centred on the contemporary characteristics of the cluster, it was already possible to outline a reasonably clear overview of its various chronological phases, including its past. In the case of Turin, it immediately became apparent that this was a young and recently constituted cluster (2013–2014), whose origins differed across the actors involved and were not necessarily tied to the territory, at least in professional terms.

Paradoxically, this initial uncertainty proved to be the most compelling aspect of the investigation. It rendered the search for points of continuity with the past – whether from adjacent industrial sectors or from the experiences of individual actors no longer active in the field – a process of continuous discovery. The preliminary hypothesis, namely the possibility of a link between the cluster's semi-institutionalised structure and a history connected to the local electromechanical industry, which had largely disappeared about a decade earlier due to systemic market transformations, was shown to be almost entirely inaccurate. However, it was precisely this divergence between expectations and findings that helped clarify the cluster's origins, the ecosystem present at its formation, and the reasons for the absence of certain actors identified in previous deliverables.

The decision to focus predominantly on historical reconstruction through Turin's electromechanical industry – specifically pinball machines, jukeboxes, arcade cabinets, and arcade game boards – stemmed from two observations: the lack of concrete references to collaborations with neighbouring industries, and the city's deeply rooted industrial character. Regarding the former, aside from a few rare cases highlighted in previous deliverables (Lumiq Studios, VIEW Conference), no indication emerged of any continuity between video game development and other local industries. Despite Turin's rich heritage in the film sector, no substantive cross-pollination with video game production could be identified, except in purely B2B contexts. Regarding the latter, Turin has historically been an industrial city, dominated economically and culturally by the automotive sector. It was therefore reasonable to assume that the city's high level of technical specialisation might have served as an initial foundation for a subsequent video game production industry – an assumption apparently reinforced by the presence of well-known companies engaged in importing, manufacturing, distributing and renting coin-operated electromechanical equipment. Some of these firms remained active until the early 2000s.

The methodology adopted in this chapter centres on historical research conducted in relation to the current Turin cluster. To this end, the events leading to the cluster's present configuration were reconstructed through document analysis and targeted interviews with actors operating within or

adjacent to the cluster's sphere of influence. The work unfolded in two distinct yet interconnected operational phases, which informed each other organically. The first phase involved collecting evidence concerning the history of local industries involved in gaming-related activities that could, in any way, be connected to the current cluster. This evidence was primarily gathered through online sources and specialised databases (N=12). The second phase consisted of fieldwork, namely a series of semi-structured interviews (N=10) with individuals potentially interested in the topic and protagonists, at various levels, of the cluster's historical trajectory, adopting oral historiographical methodologies.

The twelve documentary sources relate to electromechanical companies operating in Turin and the wider Piedmont region, particularly during the 1980s. Databases describing their histories, market developments, interactions with other actors, and the analogue or digital games they produced were consulted. Additional sources include documents produced prior to the "official" emergence of the cluster, mainly concerning future intentions and planning. Broader contextual sources, not limited to Piedmont, were also examined to provide a more accurate reconstruction of the wider environment in which these dynamics unfolded.

The ten interviews were conducted with key figures in the local and national video game industry (see Table 8). The first interview was intentionally carried out with an individual already consulted during D4.1 – Marco Mazzaglia – who served as the starting point and pilot case for this task. The aim was to consolidate the notion of a foundational moment – the cluster's so-called "Year Zero" (2013–2014) – and subsequently proceed backwards in reconstructing its historical development. This interviewee's significance derives from his current and past roles in the cluster and the national industry, as well as his extensive historical knowledge. The remaining nine interviews included both actors directly involved in the local industry – such as programmers active since the 1980s and entrepreneurs from the electromechanical sector – as well as experts and enthusiasts of Italian video game history. This diversity enabled a sufficiently comprehensive reconstruction of events in the Turin area from the late 1970s to the formation of the present-day cluster in the 2010s.

It should be noted that it was not possible to contact all actors involved in the cluster's pre-history. In the case of several electromechanical companies, contact with the children of former owners could not be established due to the absence of reliable contact information. Similarly, for the only company identified in the first half of the 2000s – Impressionware (presumably active from 2003 to 2009) – no response was received from former employees, leaving what is likely the most substantial gap in the reconstruction of the local history.

Interviews were conducted both in person and online. Their duration ranged from 25 minutes to 1 hour and 45 minutes, and all were conducted in Italian. The interview approach followed the principles of "responsive interviewing" (Rubin & Rubin, 2012), allowing considerable flexibility and enabling interviewees to narrate and reconstruct events in their own way. All interviews were transcribed and subsequently coded and analysed using NVivo (ver. 15). The analytical approach was thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006). As in previous deliverables, the aim was to identify relevant themes (Harding, 2013) and patterns of meaning (Braun & Clarke, 2006) from the dataset produced through the historical reconstruction. A discursive approach (Phillips & Hardy, 2002) was

again adopted, proving useful for examining the social reality of an empirical phenomenon that remains underexplored and is therefore lacking in preconceived assumptions.

Table 8. List of interviewees and their roles.

Name	Professional/institutional affiliation	Role in historical analysis
M. M.	Various Development Companies; Professor at the Polytechnic University; Founder of T-Union; Video game Evangelist	Deeply knowledgeable about the cluster, its companies and the history of the ecosystem
P. B.	Former Employee of Elettronolo (FI)	An expert on the history of Italian electromechanical coin-operated entertainment
C. S.	Founder of Retrocampus	History of Italian video games
P. C.	Freelance Programmer	Local Programmer
R. V.	Not Affiliated	Local Coin-op Enthusiast
D. O.	Digital Innovation Hub Open Source Tech Leader at Present Group	Longstanding Local Programmer; Electronic Musician and Soundtrack Composer

F. C.	Former Employee of Simulmondo and Italgiochi	An expert on the history of Italian electromechanical coin-operated entertainment
F. D.	Entrepreneur in the Tech Industry	A programmer from the 1980s, he created the first successful video game in Turin
A. N.	Owner of Arcade Story and co-creator of the television programme Videogame Hunters	An expert on the history of Italian electromechanical coin-operated entertainment
G. M.	Former Employee of Sidam and former Owner of Sipem	An expert on the Italian coin-operated electromechanical entertainment market

4.2 Cluster general historical information

4.2.1 Brief description of the cluster (contemporary period)

The video game production cluster in Turin is a relatively recent development. The ecosystem began to assume a semi-structured configuration only in 2014. It is a small cluster composed of a range of institutional and non-institutional actors who together constitute a sufficiently articulated value chain for video game development and production. At present, there are approximately fifteen development studios of varying sizes (see Table 9 for some selected examples), all of which are small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with an overarching indie orientation in their output. Business-to-business (B2B) production plays a crucial role in ensuring the economic sustainability of these studios. Among them, four companies are considered the cluster’s most representative actors: 34BigThings, Memorable Games, Tiny Bull Studios, and Broken Arms Games. These studios established themselves in the local context in 2013 and have since formed the structural core of the cluster’s production landscape. Some of them also contribute to the development of the local talent pipeline, collaborating with Turin’s two major universities – the University of Turin and the Polytechnic University of Turin.

The value chain further includes several institutional actors: a technology hub that hosts companies and gaming-related events (OGR Tech); a business incubator managed by the Polytechnic University (I3P); and a gaming acceleration programme (Quickload), funded and run by Fondazione OGR, 34BigThings and Microsoft. Public institutions also play a role in promoting cluster visibility and

generating investment opportunities, including the City Council of Turin, the Piedmont Region, and the Chamber of Commerce. Finally, representative associations contribute to the ecosystem, most notably T-Union – a developers’ association created by the founders of the four main Turin-based studios and other key actors in the local scene – which was subsequently incorporated into the local chapter of the International Game Developers Association (IGDA), a non-profit organisation responsible for coordinating themed events and collective participation among developers.

The cluster benefits from a young and highly skilled talent pool trained within local public and private educational institutions. Workers are generally very young, while senior roles are currently held by the founders of the cluster’s principal studios. As will be discussed in more detail later, long-standing members of the ecosystem share diverse educational backgrounds, frequently linked to Turin’s universities, but typically acquired their professional experience in video game development outside the city. A common feature among them is that, during the first decade of the 2000s, they worked for Italy’s two major video game companies in Milan – Ubisoft and, above all, Milestone – commuting daily from Turin to Milan over a period of several years.

Table 9. Main development studios in the cluster, plus a selection of small-scale development studios based in Turin and the Piedmont region.

Studio	Basic Info	Size & Structure	Specialisation
34BigThings	Subsidiary of THQ Nordic (Embracer Group)	Approx. 80-100	Racing games
Broken Arms Games	Independent studio; the team was part of the Australian startup accelerator ANZ Innovyz Start	Approx. 20-30; headquarters in Acqui Terme (AL)	Management games
Dramatic Iceberg	Small independent studio; Small independent studio	Approx. 15	Various indie-type games
Futurats	Small independent studio; participated in the Quickload acceleration programme	Approx. 10	Strategy games
Memorable Games	Purchased by uBroker at 49%; the studio’s former name was MixedBag	Approx. 15	Story-driven games

Novis Games	Independent studio; participated in the Quickload acceleration programme	Approx. 7	Specialising in games for visually impaired people
NewbiX	Small independent studio; born from the bitManiaX computer shop	Approx. 3; headquarters in Asti (AT)	Retro indie games
SEEPProduction	Small independent studio	Approx. 2	Retro indie games
Tiny Bull Studios	Born from the I3P incubator; it owns Game Thinkers, an independent company structure dedicated solely to B2B	Approx. 50-60	Narrative games
Volcanite Games	Independent studio	Approx. 4	Various indie-type games

4.3 Temporal perimeter: Cluster History

4.3.1 'Year Zero'

The short history of the Turin video game production cluster has a date – or rather a brief period – that all its long-standing members recognise: the end of January 2014, when the first Global Game Jam was organised in Turin, widely regarded as the symbolic moment of its “creation”.

The cluster’s history can be summarised as follows, with the Global Game Jam representing only the visible tip of the iceberg. Apart from the earlier local experience of the development studio Impressionware (active approximately between 2003 and 2009, before merging with Studio Idoru in Padua to form Double Jungle, a company that is no longer active), whose former members subsequently dispersed into other companies and activities, the main actors were all employed at the time in the three major video game development companies based in Milan (and Italy): the Italian branch of Ubisoft, Ovosonico, and Milestone. The latter, in particular, employed at one point six people from Turin (Michele Bertolini, Marco Mazzaglia, Emanuele Russo, Giacomo Marchetti, Roberto Tugnolo, and Filippo Vivirito), alongside others working at Ubisoft. This group, together with the five future founders of 34BigThings – who were living and working together in a shared house – began meeting in the evenings at the International School of Comics to design a collective video game, initially inspired by the story of Gulliver. These meetings took place after the evening train journey back from Milan, and were followed by dinner and work sessions that continued until midnight or 1 a.m.

In 2012, Milestone experienced internal difficulties with the Leader Distribuzione group, which had acquired the company in 2002. The new management was widely perceived by employees as unfavourable, generating significant discontent. Many long-standing staff members left to join other studios or to establish their own businesses, including several employees from Turin. Those originating from Turin eventually returned to the city, where they created their own companies. In October 2013, at the conclusion of the annual VIEW Conference, they founded an association – T-Union – which became a platform for bringing people together. The association provided a pretext for companies to meet, collaborate, and consolidate relationships. In mid-November, the same group decided to organise a Global Game Jam, based on the model already used in Northern Europe. Although many members were sceptical, the youngest among them – particularly the 34BigThings team, and especially Giuseppe Enrico Franchi – advocated strongly for the initiative despite pessimistic expectations regarding participation.

The results far exceeded forecasts. Within fifteen days, Marco Mazzaglia secured sponsorship from Microsoft and obtained I3P as the venue. The event, held from 24 to 26 January 2014, registered 120 sign-ups with 91 actual participants. Importantly, the attendees were not limited to students; many were professionals working independently or aspiring to enter the video game sector without having had prior contact with it. This event marked the first true moment of connection and mutual discovery among professionals and enthusiasts within the local territory. It is collectively regarded as the cluster's "Year Zero", from which the current ecosystem began to expand and evolve.

From that moment onwards, the group of actors involved started constructing a sophisticated video game development industry – one capable of interacting on equal terms with companies in Milan and potentially positioning Turin as the second most significant gaming area in Italy. More broadly, the cluster began to function as a production hub intertwined with similar centres in Milan, Bologna and Rome, all cities with established IGDA chapters. In June 2014, a meeting took place between members of T-Union and Matteo Pessione of Fondazione CRT (also a professor at the University of Turin). Over time, discussions continued concerning the possibility of integrating the video game industry into the technological hub of the "new" Officine Grandi Riparazioni (OGR), which reopened in 2017.

Ultimately, a compromise was reached, somewhat more modest than the initial ambitions but nonetheless beneficial for local development studios. OGR – particularly after the opening of OGR Tech and the launch of the Quickload gaming acceleration programme in 2019 – became the multifunctional centre of the cluster's semi-institutionalised structure, and arguably its symbolic hub. For instance, OGR Tech currently hosts Tech&Tonic, a monthly series of themed events dedicated to video game developers.

The contemporary timeline of the cluster, already presented in D4.1, is summarised in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Cluster timeline as presented in D4.1.

4.3.2 Before 'Year Zero'

As outlined in the previous section, 2014 can be considered the cluster's "Year Zero". However, given the sequence of events that led to the Global Game Jam at the end of January, it is more accurate to refer to the two-year period 2013–2014. This was the period in which the first companies were founded in the city and the T-Union association was established, but – above all – a time characterised by dialogue, shared ideas, and creative initiatives projected towards the near future.

What has been identified prior to this "Year Zero" does not take place directly in Turin, but primarily in Milan – the workplace of most of the individuals who would later form the cluster. The unique experience of Impressionware dates back to the early 2000s. Apart from this case, which in any event left no lasting trace in the current context, the city experienced roughly a decade without significant activity in the sector or the presence of specialised actors. The national video game production market remained limited, particularly during a decade in which attention was progressively shifting towards mobile gaming. For structural and market-related reasons, during the years in which physical distribution was essential, Milan was the only city capable of sustaining a substantial level of production and sales, supported by a sufficient pipeline for the design, creation, and distribution of finished products.

At the time, Turin's universities did not offer any dedicated courses in the field. In fact, private institutions such as Event Horizon, iMasterArt and the specialist courses provided by the

International School of Comics emerged only after the arrival of development studios in Turin. The Global Game Jam itself brought visibility to the Polytechnic University, which subsequently created a course in Game Design and Gamification within the Faculty of Cinema Engineering, thereby addressing the field of video games explicitly for the first time.

Everything that precedes the proto-cluster decade (2000s–early 2010s) forms the subject of this section of the report. A national perspective is required to contextualise developments in the Turin area, since – as is still evident today in the video game production market – Italy tends to be perceived and analysed as a single industrial entity, one that is difficult to divide into clearly demarcated regional sectors.

The working hypothesis guiding this reconstruction was that in a highly industrialised environment such as Turin, the origins of the contemporary local video game production industry could be traced, at least in part, to the electromechanical industry of the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s. Particular attention was given to companies producing coin-operated electromechanical entertainment machines, which employed workers with mechanical, electronic and computer engineering competencies, as well as programmers of arcade boards. These decades were also characterised by a considerable number of hobbyists and semi-professionals devoted to programming on home computers, converting games between different home platforms, and contributing to an arcade-game enthusiast culture present in nearly all Italian cities.

The presence of a significant pool of individuals in Turin – much like elsewhere in the country – capable of entering the labour market, led to an initial heuristic assumption that the ecosystem of the period may have generated a (semi-)continuous process leading to the present. This reasoning was formulated notwithstanding the existence of significant objective constraints at the time, most notably the absence of sector-specific educational facilities, which clearly restricted the development of highly specialised skills and the formation of dedicated talent pools. At the same time, the possibility of a clear generational rupture was also considered, although such a discontinuity required explanation in relation to developments in the national context during the decades preceding the 2000s.

From a national standpoint, Italy in the 1980s was a particularly prosperous country with respect to the video game industry. Contrary to common accounts, the country had a substantial market in all its forms during the pre-globalisation era: *“Because, obviously, the mainstream narrative, which is still circulating today, is largely based on the known history of video games, which is mainly American and Japanese. But little is known, in reality, about the history of video games in other countries, even from a market perspective, because, obviously, before 2000, the market was not globalised. So each region, each country had its own markets, different mechanisms, etc., very different from what came after 2000, with globalisation standardising all markets in terms of product offerings.”* (CS)

The issue in Italy was that, unlike in most other European countries, the sector and market remained unregulated. There was no copyright or publishing law protecting intellectual property related to video games. As a result, the industry was dominated by bootlegs – pirated and illegal clones of arcade and home-computer video games. These were typically simple hacked copies in which

graphics were altered (reskinned), texts were translated from English into Italian, and then distributed both commercially (in arcades and video game shops) and through other illegal channels. Production was carried out both by amateurs – the so-called “*cantinari*” (roughly translated as “cellarman”), individuals working in bedrooms or basements – and by actual production and distribution companies. Illegal copies were also distributed via newsagents, through the circulation network of specialist magazines, to which creators of pirated games sent their products directly: *“So we lived through that decade, the famous Golden Age of video games, the one that is referred to as the Golden Age, the 1980s. In Italy, we experienced it in a distorted way. We experienced it where the market, even though very often when people talk about those years, there are many who say, “Oh, but Italy was a market that nobody cared about”, which is not true. Italy was a very strong market, which was already capable of generating billions of lire in the video game market in the 1980s. But it was an unprotected market. And that is why the big distributors did not enter Italy in those years. Because they had no market protection. Yet the market in Italy existed, it grew, it spread, it became very large and important, but it was a completely immoral market based on a lack of recognition of copyright and publishing rights in video games, which brought wealth to some companies that made billions in those years and then disappeared into thin air.”* (CS)

The first law protecting copyright in video games in Italy was passed only in 1992, under pressure from the European Union. Law 518/1992, which implemented EC Directive 250/91, constituted the first regulatory recognition of software in Italy (Tarantino & Tosoni, 2017; 2019). Subsequently, Law 747/1994 implemented the TRIPs agreements by amending articles of the existing Copyright Law (Law 633/1941) concerning software. However, in practice, effective regulation appeared only around a decade later, as the Italian market continued to rely heavily on legally ambiguous copying before transitioning into a “normalised” system. This time lag created a substantial gap in software development, hardware distribution, and professional adaptation, delaying the emergence of a national industry aligned with international standards. Consequently, the formation of a structured industry was postponed by at least a decade, with the exception of sporadic and highly targeted cases. These pioneering experiences – now regarded as milestones in Italian video game history – were concentrated in a few areas, particularly Bologna, Milan and Genoa. Turin, by contrast, continued along a partially autonomous path, with local electromechanical companies and semi-professionals maintaining established practices throughout the 1990s.

The next subsection examines the history preceding the “proto-cluster” phase, with the aim of identifying possible links between the cluster’s prehistory and its eventual formation.

4.3.3 Before ‘Year Zero’

The analysis conducted thus far, both in previous deliverables and up to this point, has focused on the contemporary configuration of Turin’s video game production cluster, tracing it back to the beginning of its “proto” phase in the early 2000s. The previous section offered an overview of the national context and the general conditions experienced by most medium and large Italian cities as they engaged with the video game market during the 1970s, 1980s, and 1990s.

Turin was no exception. The city's long-standing industrial tradition – which fostered specific talent pools, technical expertise, and an advanced, peculiar industrial infrastructure – enabled the presence of several mechanical and electromechanical entertainment companies, including those active in the video game field. Unlike more structured areas such as Bologna and Milan, where companies operated in both the coin-operated electromechanical entertainment and home-computer markets, Turin witnessed development only in the former.

Despite this limitation, Turin-based companies played an important role in the history of Italian video games. One notable example is Fratelli Bertolino, active in the automatic entertainment sector and particularly in electromechanical pinball machines. Although Model Racing, based in Montemarciano (AN), was the first Italian company in the field, Fratelli Bertolino emerged almost immediately after. Already active at the time of Pong's release (1972), it produced Combat in 1975 – of which only an advertisement survives – and UFO in the same year. UFO, produced slightly before Model Racing's equivalent, was sold internationally to Chicago Coins, becoming Super Pinball in the United States. It is considered the first video game ever designed and produced in Italy. Shortly thereafter, in 1976, Fratelli Bertolino became Atari's official Italian distributor, representative, and licensee. For this reason, it no longer made sense for the company to develop its own games internally, as it could directly import the world's most successful titles.

Figure 11. Picture taken from the promotional brochure for the video game Combat (Fratelli Bertolino s.n.c., 1975).

Another Turin-based company was Sidam, which initially manufactured table football machines, outdoor photo booths, and similar products. By 1978, Sidam had shifted towards producing bootlegs – unauthorised copies – mostly of Atari games, which were reproduced almost identically, given new Italian names, and distributed to arcades. As part of Italy's unregulated market, where neither copyright nor publishing rights existed for video games, companies like Sidam could simply

purchase original boards in the United States or Japan, copy them on their return, and distribute them commercially. Sidam closed in 1983 and reopened immediately afterwards as Sipem (1984).

These two companies crossed paths in the early 1980s in what became a pivotal legal moment in Italian video game history (although the owners of the two companies were friends). In 1980, Fratelli Bertolino, on behalf of Atari, filed a major lawsuit against Sidam (Atari Inc. and Fratelli Bertolino s.r.l. v. Sidam s.r.l.). The Turin Court ruled against Sidam on 15 July 1983, a decision upheld repeatedly up to the Court of Cassation. Although the ruling favoured Atari, the decision was based on unfair competition: Sidam was judged to have sold identical copies of games invented by Atari in the United States. Crucially, the court ruled that video games did not possess the qualities required to be considered products of human ingenuity, and therefore, were not entitled to copyright or publisher protection. This legal interpretation caused considerable disruption to the domestic market by confirming that video games could not be recognised as intellectual property.

Figure 12. Arcade cabinet for the video game Asterock (Sidam s.r.l., 1979). This is a bootleg version of the video game Asteroids (Atari, Inc., 1979), which led to Fratelli Bertolino and Atari filing a lawsuit against Sidam.

As a result, and as previously described, the following decade saw the continued production and sale of copied video games. Although an initial legal definition of video games emerged in the 1980s – at a time when they were not yet recognised as software – the Turin Magistrate’s Court stated in a 25 May 1982 judgement that “the game was created to relieve patients from boredom”, thus excluding the applicability of copyright law and limiting itself to unfair competition provisions (Article 2598 of the Italian Civil Code). Only in 1999 did the Court of Cassation recognise video games as “computer programs” consisting of “sequences of moving images”, assimilating them to cinematographic works and protecting them both from unfair competition and as intellectual creations eligible for copyright, provided they met the requirements of creativity and originality

(judgment no. 1204/1999). Specific copyright protection for video games only arrived with Articles 171 ter and 181 bis of the Copyright Law in 2005 (Law no. 43/2005).

Following the Turin ruling, both Sidam and later Sipem became official licensees and distributors for various producers of arcade video games, until Sipem's closure in 2006. Fratelli Bertolino, by contrast, disappeared shortly after the lawsuit. Two further companies were active in the local ecosystem: CDA in Cuneo (CN), mainly renting arcade cabinets to amusement arcades, and Rumiano in the province of Turin. Both produced bootlegs. These companies, rather than relying on IT expertise, possessed considerable knowledge in mechanics and electronics and had the necessary equipment to create arcade cabinets and duplicate boards.

The year 1992 thus marked a turning point for the industry. The introduction of software copyright regulation, the gambling law (formally defined as such only in 2003), and the rise of widely available home consoles such as the PlayStation (released in Italy in September 1995) effectively ended this type of business. Gambling, deregulated in 1992, soon became a fiscal tool for managing public debt, and slot machines became more attractive to venue owners than arcade cabinets, eventually forming an autonomous economic sector managed directly by the state from 2003. Most of the electromechanical companies and their employees were subsequently retrained: some moved into other mechanical or electronic industries, others into the growing gambling sector. There is no evidence that individuals involved in these earlier activities later transitioned into video game production.

A similar pattern can be observed among hobbyists. Most were amateurs programming at home, often copying original games and sending them to specialist magazines sold at newsstands. Turin shared this pattern, though with a few notable exceptions. In rare cases, individuals succeeded in selling their games to major companies, such as Fulvio Dominici Carnino from Grugliasco (TO), whose Specventure for the ZX Spectrum was sold to the British company Mastertronic in 1985, achieving 73,000 sales across Europe, the United States, and Russia. Dominici was part of a local computer club whose members – of all ages and means – produced copied games for resale on the illegal market. He was the only member to gain professional recognition. Only 12 copies of Specventure were sold in Italy, and Dominici continued his career in innovation and technology, with little further involvement in video game creation.

Figure 13. Cover of the *Specventure* video game for ZX Spectrum (Fulvio Domini Carnino, 1985, published by Mastertronic Ltd).

Another example is Dino Olivieri, who worked on video game programming and conversion during the 1990s, becoming a genuine professional. In the mid-1980s, he began by sending demo games to specialist magazines and, in 1988, obtained his first collaboration with Simulmondo in Bologna, where he worked on conversions from the Commodore 64 to the IBM PC. In the early 1990s, he moved to Genias in Castenaso (BO), continuing similar work. By the late 1990s, he shifted entirely to programming in other sectors and, simultaneously, to music production. His involvement in video game creation returned to a purely hobbyist level, largely due to the absence of a fertile local context in which to continue.

As several interviewees emphasised, the region lacked organisations capable of recognising and cultivating the creative potential that existed: *“So, the problem in those years, to put it bluntly, that is, very, very, very quickly, was that, for example, in the 1980s, especially in the 1980s, when I started to develop in a way, that is, I was really stuck there, I was 15 years old, I was already programming in Assembly, basically video games, first I wrote on paper and then I took them. And there were lots of other kids like me. So, at the time, there was a lack of... certainly in the area of people able to grasp this... this idea, to exploit this enormous potential that was there, and it was enormous. I remember I had a lot of friends who were very good at programming; they did some really exceptional things that were absolutely competitive with what the British were doing, with what the Germans were doing, and so on. But no one in the area was able to harness this potential and turn it into a product.”* (DO)

Figure 14. Start screen of the video game *Over the Net*, converted to IBM PC by Dino Olivieri (Genias, 1991, published by Merit Software).

The available evidence indicates that the other individuals involved in video game development during this period likewise left the local area, if not Italy altogether. Moreover, between the late 1990s and the subsequent decade, a considerable number of professionals and semi-professionals – together with their creative interests and energies – were effectively “diverted” from video game production towards the burgeoning web sector following the advent of the internet. As previously noted, these were isolated cases that did not generate any meaningful continuity with the current cluster.

The dynamics described above ultimately shaped everything that followed in Italy: namely, the absence of an official video game market for roughly ten years after the 1983 ruling, coinciding with a period in which the major global actors in the industry were consolidating their positions. By the 1990s, the international video game market had already expanded many times its early-1980s scale and had simultaneously undergone radical technological transformations. Entering the market was therefore no longer as straightforward as it had been in earlier decades.

Another interviewee noted the consequence of the lost decade: *“The point is that, from 1983 to 1993, we lost 10 years of technological innovation in video games. So, to understand this, let’s take an example. In 1983, we went from Donkey Kong 3, if you remember what that is, or Track and Field, to Doom. That is, there was a huge technological leap. And everything in between was completely lost, because there was no one left to invent innovative games to beat the competition. All they did was copy.”* (AN)

This situation was exacerbated by a shortage of professional programmers, itself the result of an insufficient “critical mass” of trained developers and of development technologies that, during the 1990s, were no longer adequate for contemporary needs. Additionally, Turin offered more lucrative professional opportunities due to its extensive industrial and electromechanical labour market, which drew away many of the hobbyists and semi-professionals of the time.

4.3.4 Institutional support before the cluster

Before ‘Year Zero’, institutional support was virtually non-existent. Indeed, no formal educational programmes specifically dedicated to video game creation were available. Enthusiasts in the 1970s,

1980s, and 1990s were largely self-taught, relying on the specialist magazines of the time and the limited programming materials imported from abroad, particularly from the United Kingdom. In the sphere of tertiary education, the only viable training pathway was a degree in computer science, which nonetheless offered no dedicated specialisation in video game development. This situation applied both locally in Turin and nationally across Italy.

Despite the absence of meaningful public support, an entrepreneurial ecosystem nevertheless emerged, facilitated by a deregulated market in which mechanical and electromechanical entertainment companies, together with specialised publishers, found favourable conditions for entering the arcade and home-computer sectors. The possibility for these companies to distribute hacked copies of original games enabled the growth and persistence of a highly distinctive market capable of generating substantial profits.

Individual enthusiasts, hobbyists, and semi-professionals, meanwhile, cultivated their interests within the various computer clubs distributed throughout the country. Despite the often limited and technologically outdated hardware available – particularly in comparison with that commonly accessible in other European countries – these enthusiasts succeeded in sourcing materials from abroad, along with information that would otherwise have been inaccessible to isolated users. Such resources served as a gateway for many of them to develop programming skills suited to the period and to acquire sufficient technical expertise to enter the market, frequently beginning within its illicit sphere.

4.4 Determining factors in the history of the cluster

4.4.1 Historical circumstances and events surrounding the local industry

Turin is currently the fourth largest Italian municipality in terms of population (after Rome, Milan, and Naples) and the third largest economic and manufacturing centre in the country. Together with Milan and Genoa, it formed the so-called industrial triangle, the core of large-scale industrialisation in the Italian economy at the end of the nineteenth century and throughout the years of the economic boom. It is also one of Italy's principal university, artistic, tourist, scientific, gastronomic, and cultural hubs.

The history of the city's cultural industries is particularly noteworthy. Turin, for instance, has a long-standing tradition in publishing, the earliest example of a Cultural and Creative Industry (CCI) in the city. The concentration of publishing houses is higher than the national average, and even today, 50 per cent of Italian school and university publishers are located in Turin. The city has been home to publishing houses of national significance, including UTET, Paravia, and Einaudi, and, since 1988, it has hosted its "International Book Fair" (Salone Internazionale del Libro). From the perspective of the press, the Piedmontese capital has historically been home to numerous newspapers of national relevance, such as La Stampa.

In addition to the publishing sector, Turin housed EIAR and later RAI for decades and was therefore the city from which most radio broadcasts originated in the pre-television era (1927–1954). With the introduction of television, the city became one of the principal sites of the RAI Television

Production Centre, alongside Rome, Milan, and Naples. Since the beginning of broadcasting in 1954, Turin – also home to the Museum of Radio and Television – was the first location of the national broadcaster. Turin’s ties to the film industry are equally significant. It is, in fact, the Italian city in which the film industry first took root, owing to its historical, geographical, and cultural proximity to France. The first film studios were founded in 1907. Today, Turin remains one of the primary locations for film and television production in Italy, thanks in part to the Turin Film Commission and the presence of numerous dedicated events, such as the Turin Film Festival, the Lovers Film Festival, ViewFest, and Cinema at the Palazzo Reale. Especially noteworthy is the presence of the National Cinema Museum, housed within the city’s symbolic monument, the Mole Antonelliana.

Above all, Turin is widely recognised as the city and capital of the automotive industry, historically home to companies such as FIAT and Lancia, among others. FIAT, which became Fiat Chrysler Automobiles (FCA) in 2014 following its acquisition of the Chrysler Group, later became part of the Stellantis group in 2021, progressively losing its central role in the city. Despite the deeply rooted industrial culture, Turin is now a mature post-industrial city that has undergone a comprehensive process of industrial transformation. Since the 1980s, the city has experienced significant tertiarisation while remaining one of the principal industrial centres in both Italy and Europe.

These characteristics have contributed to the emergence of a distinctive creative and cultural environment capable of supporting the current video game production industry. At the same time, however, they acted as a form of ‘brake’ during its prehistoric phase, offering limited professional opportunities to young enthusiasts and aspiring professionals in the 1980s and 1990s. The strong creativity and freedom of expression fostered by an intense connection with the established creative industries – particularly the film sector – and the presence of two major universities were counterbalanced by a city still firmly attached to an industrial identity and to creative applications associated only with it. The industrial sector functioned as a powerful magnetic pole, absorbing much of the creative impetus that might otherwise have been directed towards video games. The emergence of the cluster, as examined in D4.1 and D4.2, appears to have been driven more by individual initiative than by genuine endogenous factors.

4.4.2 Exogenous factors

In the prehistoric phase of the cluster, there were no institutional or economic factors in either Turin or Italy capable of supporting a video game production industry. Indeed, until the late 1990s, Italy lacked sufficient production volume to be relevant at the national or international level, particularly in the domain of home-computer and console video games, and therefore failed to attract the interest of public or private investors. The only relevant factors were those associated with the sphere of “grey” production – such as bootlegging and copy markets – which, while economically and culturally quite significant and of considerable creative interest, nevertheless remained limited in terms of entrepreneurial capacity and medium- to long-term strategic vision.

At the time, companies such as Simulmondo (1988–1999), Genias (1989–1993), Idea (1990–1992), Dynabyte (1991–1996), Trecision (1991–2003), and Graffiti (1993–1995) – the latter later becoming Milestone (1996) – represented isolated cases within an economic and cultural landscape that was

not particularly conducive to home video game development. Their presence, marginal within the national market, acted more as a pull factor for the limited number of professional and semi-professional talents in Piedmont than as a catalyst for the creation of development studios in Turin or the wider region.

The economic context of arcade video games was markedly different, with Turin having several illustrious representatives during the 1980s and 1990s. The coin-operated electromechanical entertainment market was of considerable importance in Italy and encompassed a chain of cabinet and game-board manufacturers, importers, distributors, and rental companies spread across the country. This market also included a substantial illegal component, particularly in the form of individual and industrial piracy, which significantly increased its economic volume. However, as described above, the sector's transformation during the 1990s – especially the shift towards the digital gambling industry – diverted potential talent away from any reconversion into the B2C video game development sector. Moreover, the skillsets possessed by firms operating in the arcade sector were primarily oriented towards mechanical and electronic engineering, offering no genuine continuity with the competences required by the evolution of the medium.

In the decades preceding the 2000s, video games themselves were frequently stigmatised and professionally devalued, resulting in a pervasive lack of institutional recognition and production (Carbone & Fassone, 2020). Turin, as the historic centre of several CCIs and a high-level cultural environment, has witnessed the emergence of highly creative video game production in recent decades, although only since the consolidation of the current development studios (2013–present).

4.4.3 Role of neighbouring industries

As highlighted in other deliverables, neighbouring industries have never played a decisive role in the formation of Turin's current video game development cluster. Although contemporary actors maintain various relationships with adjacent sectors – most notably cinema, special effects, and computer graphics – these interactions have primarily taken place through participation in the VIEW Conference (2000–present). The VIEW Conference is an annual event on computer graphics held in Turin at the OGR. Initially established as the Virtuality Conference (2000), it adopted the name VIEW: Virtual Interactive Emerging World in its eighth edition (2007).

During the interviews, several respondents referred to the activities done at the Lumiq Studios (2002–2013), a publicly owned company that produced CGI animations and live-action films. Lumiq Studios provided support for post-production and digital intermediate processes and operated across the design, development, production, and marketing of products and services for cinema, television, advertising, multimedia, and new media. Despite these accounts, it has not yet been possible to reconstruct the precise nature of any actual interactions between current and former actors in the local video game industry and Lumiq Studios.

However, the main endogenous and exogenous factors underpinning the creation and development of the cluster can only be traced back to the 2010s.

4.4.4 Role of other/proto-industries concerning the current cluster

The electromechanical coin-operated entertainment industry played a considerable role in Turin. In turn influenced by the city's longstanding industrial culture, it was significantly shaped by the national and international arcade video game market of the 1980s and 1990s, enabling companies of substantial national relevance to establish themselves locally. Fratelli Bertolino and Sidam/Sipem, in particular, undertook a partial reconversion of their business activities to enter this market, thereby securing national and international recognition and forging important contacts. As importers and licensed distributors of American and Japanese video games – including titles from Atari, Williams, Data East, Namco, Konami, Sega, and Nintendo, among others – they contributed to the development of a broad-based video game culture in Italy.

The electromechanical industry, both in the manufacture of pinball and arcade cabinets and in the industrial production of game boards, underwent a substantial evolution in terms of technical complexity and product quality. At the same time, it contributed to the training of numerous professionals, equipping them with skillsets that later proved valuable for transitions into other industrial sectors. However, as demonstrated by empirical research, this industry maintained no continuity with the contemporary video game development sector. The paradigm shift in the market – namely the rise of mass-market home consoles such as the PlayStation, the diffusion of more user-friendly home computing, and the gradual transformation of coin-operated entertainment into gambling – brought the Italian arcade industry to a virtual standstill. By the late 1990s, not only the culture of arcades but also the broader presence of arcade video games in social venues such as bars and other public spaces had effectively disappeared. Likewise, many professionals in the sector redirected their careers towards other industries, often in the design and production of slot machines.

Equally significant, although unrelated to the subsequent formation of the cluster, was the presence of Olivetti in Ivrea (TO), approximately 60 kilometres from the provincial capital. Olivetti is an Italian company operating in the IT sector and was historically one of the world's leading manufacturers of typewriters, calculators, and electronic equipment. Now wholly owned by TIM, the company was founded in 1908 by Camillo Olivetti and rose to particular prominence under the leadership of his son, Adriano Olivetti. In addition to producing the first portable typewriter (MP1), the world's first electromechanical calculator capable of performing all four operations and printing results (Divisumma14), and the first programmable personal computer (P101), the company became renowned for implementing an advanced welfare system for its employees and for its strong emphasis on technical and scientific research and design. Owing to these characteristics, Olivetti became one of the emblematic symbols of Italian economic development in the post-war period. Although it played no role in the field of video games, its presence in the wider Turin area contributed to the broader cultural climate in which the Piedmontese CCIs later developed.

4.4.5 Factors that influenced the birth and development of local industry

The local industry, which developed later than the mainstream video game development market, emerged within a context characterised by established technological standards and regulatory requirements. Once issues relating to copyright and publishing rights had been resolved, video game production in Italy became formally regulated, thereby entering mainstream distribution and commercial channels.

In this era of globalised markets, technologies have become largely uniform across production contexts, particularly in industrialised countries. Distribution channels – no longer tied to the manufacture and sale of physical copies in retail outlets – have converged around digital platforms, most notably Steam, which has enabled small independent studios to commercialise their products. Programming tools, including game engines such as Unity and Unreal Engine, have likewise become widely accessible and today constitute the standard instruments for contemporary video game development. The actors within the Turin cluster belong to this generation of development studios. One noteworthy aspect concerns the relatively limited number of Turin-based studios that have been acquired by large, often foreign, companies. This process, common within the industry, is often considered an indicator of a studio’s – and, by extension, a region’s – market success. To date, only a few cases can be identified: 34BigThings, acquired by Sweden’s Embracer Group in 2020; Memorable Games, 49% of which was acquired in 2024 by Turin-based uBroker (Utilia holding company); and DeadPixel, acquired in 2019 by TPS Group, based in Varese (VA). These remain the sole examples of studios incorporated by external companies.

4.4.6 Role of the territory for continuity/connection factors between before and after the birth of the cluster

The most evident element of continuity between the period preceding and the period following the establishment of the cluster derives from the city’s pre-existing cultural climate. This continuity is particularly visible in the educational sector, especially within tertiary education. Although the University of Turin and the Polytechnic did not, for many years, offer specialised programmes dedicated to video game development (a situation that remains unchanged at the University of Turin), they nonetheless contributed to fostering a cultural environment conducive to the cultivation of individuals and competencies that have been “carried over” across different generations.

The profound transformation of the city’s economic and productive landscape – marked by a near-total shift from industrial to service-based production – has facilitated a greater recognition of the potential of creative sectors, including video game development. Now a mature service-oriented city, which has progressively replaced fordist-type industrial manufacturing activity, Turin has reconfigured its economic and social models and, to some extent, compelled the expansion of its local productive sectors. The OGR, and OGR Tech in particular, have become emblematic of a new, albeit still limited, appreciation of the value of these “new” industries.

However, the more than ten-year gap between the disappearance of the local electromechanical entertainment industry and the formation of the first semi-institutionalised configuration of the cluster created significant disadvantages for emerging companies. Only through the cooperative model adopted by the Turin video game production cluster – currently consolidating through the multifunctional OGR hub; the mediation first of T-Union and now of IGDA; the presence of formal and informal local events organised by the latter; and the shared participation in national and international fairs – has it been possible to fill the technical and organisational void that persisted until the late 2000s.

4.5 Detailed historical timeline before the birth of the cluster and continuity factors

4.5.1 ‘New’ historical timeline

Thanks to the inclusion of historical analysis predating the so-called “Year Zero” and prior to the “proto-cluster” phase (2000s–early 2010s), it becomes possible to construct a new timeline concerning Turin and the subsequent video game production cluster, one that encompasses its entire prehistory.

The first phase may be defined as a “pre-prehistory” (up to the late 1970s), namely a historical period in which video games, in any form, did not attract significant interest. Pinball machines and other mechanical coin-operated entertainment devices were present, but video games – particularly arcade games – were not yet widespread.

The second phase of prehistory, known as the “arcade and amateur phase”, witnessed the boom of arcade games and amusement arcades (from the early 1980s to the mid-1990s), which became a mass phenomenon. Although amusement arcades remained a niche market, the city exhibited a notable presence of well-equipped venues offering all forms of electromechanical entertainment available at the time: *“Well, let’s say that in the early 80s, I clearly remember that there was Playtime, which was the first big arcade in Turin. The arcades I mentioned later came out later, not immediately. So we’re talking about the late 80s and early 90s. Almost all of the other three I mentioned, perhaps there was still the one in Via San Martino, it was still there in 1987-88, and then it moved, yes, it was still that one. DivertOne, on the other hand, perhaps as early as the 1990s, 1989-90. And also Primatist, also Primatist 88-89, roughly speaking. But not before, let’s say that these impossible arcades that existed in ‘85, well [...]. Let’s say, after the mid-90s, let’s say from 95 to 99, they all closed down.”* (RV)

At this point in history, several electromechanical manufacturing companies – including Fratelli Bertolino, Sidam, CDA, and Rumiano – decided to enter the market for producing arcade cabinets and video games. Following the trend of the Italian market, many of these companies manufactured bootlegs, i.e. illegally modified copies of original arcade boards. The 1983 ruling of the Court of Turin, won by Fratelli Bertolino and Atari against Sidam, constituted the first major turning point for this market, prompting a partial reconsideration of business strategies among companies engaged in video game piracy. Nevertheless, the market for copied video games continued for approximately

another twenty years and was gradually mitigated only with the introduction of the Law 518/1992 on copyright and publishing rights: *“We went to Japan, we took... we bought the original cartridge, if possible, or in America... but back then, most of the cartridges were American. Atari, Data East, things like that. And we brought two or three cartridges back to Italy, and copied them in their entirety. We made the card [...] The entire circuit. That’s what we did. We changed the title. So the software was also modified. Yes, we bought the card from one of their distributors, not directly from the manufacturer. And then we did the work in Italy.”* (GM)

And also: *“Because, obviously, starting in 1992, we were forced by the European Union to introduce copyright and video game publishing laws, otherwise we would have had to leave the European single market. In reality, it was introduced, but after ten years in which the market in Italy was completely based on illegal copying, it took almost another ten years before we got used to becoming a normal market. So we are now approaching the 2000s, practically speaking. And unfortunately, this has, how shall we say, with hindsight, because obviously at the time it was happening, when we were living through it, there were few, although there were some, there are articles by enlightened people who understood what was happening.”* (CS)

At the same time, this period saw the emergence of numerous hobbyists throughout the country. Some amateurs and semi-professionals in the Turin area were divided between those who exclusively produced illegal copies of video games for home computers and those who attempted to pursue a professional career by selling their games to foreign companies or working for the very few Italian video game development firms (most notably Simulmondo in Bologna). Crucial for the development of these individuals were the various computer clubs scattered across the country and the specialised magazines of the time, which the latter themselves distributed and sold bootlegs of original games: *“And then I tried to sell on the video game market that was in Turin in 1982-83. In Turin in 1982-83, there were a few guys selling audio cassettes of video games in Italian. It was a market of people who were smuggling them. They took the games, typically British ones, and there were some lads who cracked them, essentially trying to translate the instructions badly. These were photocopied with colour photocopiers, cutting the covers with scissors. They came out really ugly; in fact, they were all in colour at the time, smudged. And then they were resold in a certain circle of shops, more or less underground, and they sold this stuff. So I went to this guy, and he told me that he would sell the game in his circle, and then if I wanted to work on cracking other games. Then I said that I didn’t feel like cracking games and selling them, which is illegal anyway, and in Italy too, for various reasons. So he started selling my video game. And in the end, this guy was really pathetic. So basically, I had the cassette, and in the end, you got like 20-30 thousand lire worth of stuff, which was really laughable.”* (FD)

The same interviewee added that: *“In the 1980s, I made a video game called Specventure, the Spectrum adventure. I was 16 years old, so I was still a minor, and my father had to sign my first contract at Mastertronic in London. It was more difficult to get my father, who did not understand English, to sign the contract than it was to make the entire video game. He was convinced that they were going to take our house away because, in the 1980s, it was inconceivable that you would be paid for a game.”* (FD)

And again: “At the time, there was a whole circuit of magazines, especially at newsstands, that published video games. Most of these video games were clones, or at least bootlegs of, let’s say, official games, which were hacked, in quotation marks, and... Um, and they were often, um, reskinned, that is, um, the graphics were changed. I didn’t do that kind of thing, of course, but I made my own products, which I then tried to place with some of these companies that distributed these video games.” (DO)

The third phase of prehistory, referred to as the “rupture and void” phase (mid-1990s to early 2000s), marked the break between the previous context and the developments of the early 2000s. During this period, a small number of video game development companies emerged in certain Italian cities (Bologna, Milan, Genoa), yet they remained limited in number and dependent upon the entrepreneurial initiatives of a few “visionaries” of the time, such as Francesco Carlà with Simulmondo (Bologna) and Antonio Farina with Graffiti (Milan). However, the technological and entrepreneurial void, coupled with the lack of a critical mass of professionals – many of whom had previously been involved primarily in producing pirated copies of original video games – left Italy “impoverished” in comparison with its European and global competitors, often resulting in failures and bankruptcies. During these years, the law on copyright and publishing rights (1992) was also introduced, finally regulating the industry. Yet this was also a period marked by the gradual spread of gambling, which, together with the increasing prevalence of home gaming consoles and home computers that became progressively more accessible and user-friendly, led to the near-total disappearance of video games as they had previously existed in Italy: *“The other big gap in Italy in terms of video games is that in the 1990s, Sony entered the market with PlayStation. All these big consoles for which we don’t have the critical mass of developers, the skills, and the money to develop. As long as you develop on Commodore 64, Spectrum, Amiga, or PC, you can do it on your own, in small teams. To develop for PlayStation in 1994-95, you have to be... It’s a quality leap.”* (FD)

And lastly: *“You have to blend everything together. Otherwise, you would have to take each case individually. As I said before, the automation industries, the companies that managed automation in Italy, in my opinion, were not all truly... they knew the potential they had [...] The advent of the PlayStation, which, as we all know, has effectively changed the way... forever changed the way we interpret gaming [...] So perhaps if there had been no taxation, it would only have delayed things, but this thing has entered everyone’s homes, it has become... it has become a must-have. Even people who had never even heard of video games knew about the PlayStation concept. And that was the strength of the company. They managed to reach people who had nothing to do with it. Now, if you have to invest in something, do something; this is what you have to do. Expand even into markets that hypothetically should not be your responsibility. So yes, the answer to the question is yes, a combination of all this, a series of unavoidable events that, when put together, effectively decreed the death of arcades.”* (PB)

Turin, and Piedmont more broadly, were almost entirely excluded from this phase, failing to produce development companies or to retain professionals who had emerged during this period. All subsequent professionals trained in the Turin area relocated elsewhere – particularly to Milan – giving rise to the “proto-cluster” phase and to dynamics that, more than a decade later, culminated in the creation of the first semi-institutionalised configuration of the Turin video game production

cluster: “Yes, in my opinion, the biggest gap is between, perhaps roughly speaking, the mid-90s, maybe the late 90s, and the following decade. We’re somewhere around there.” (DO)

Figure 15. The ‘new’ historical timeline of Turin’s video game industry (and cluster).

4.5.2 Continuity factors between before and after the cluster

As demonstrated in this chapter, the empirical investigation revealed no significant factors of continuity between the cluster’s prehistory and its contemporary configuration. Actors involved in the earlier phases of video game-related activity in the Turin area either transitioned into other professional sectors or migrated to regions more conducive to career development within the video game industry. Expertise associated with electromechanical coin-operated entertainment was largely lost or redirected towards adjacent fields, such as slot machine manufacturing or industrial information technologies. Enthusiasts, hobbyists and semi-professionals, meanwhile, lacked both

the collective impetus and the organisational capacity required to establish locally rooted business ventures directly connected to video game production.

Similarly, firms – particularly those operating within the electromechanical sector – either diversified into alternative productive domains or ceased operations altogether as a consequence of market fluctuations. Public and private institutions, for their part, were established or began to engage with cluster actors only at a later stage, at least in close temporal proximity to the identified “Year Zero”. Overall, the cluster exhibits a rapid and largely discontinuous genesis, predominantly exogenous in nature and not grounded in prior local trajectories of continuity, nor in the presence of actors or firms active in the area before the early 2000s.

4.6 Conclusions

The analysis conducted for this report demonstrates that the video game development cluster in Turin emerged predominantly as a consequence of exogenous rather than endogenous factors. By cross-referencing the data obtained and examined in D4.1, D4.2, and D4.3, it becomes evident that the decisions and intentions of individuals not only determined the establishment of the current cluster but also shaped the entire history of video games in the region. The distinctive history of Italian video games – characterised for a long period by the prevalence of a parallel and illegal market – resulted in the conversion of a number of companies that had previously had little connection with the medium. Enthusiasts, hobbyists, and semi-professionals, therefore, found themselves obliged to “emigrate”, at least in professional terms, to locations more suited to nurturing their vocational ambitions.

Ultimately, the development studios that constitute the present ecosystem, together with the associations responsible for organising the events that structure it, are the direct outcome of the actions of individuals who, for a range of reasons – often personal – have contributed to building a local industry that is now recognised and appreciated both nationally and internationally.

The results of this study – initially premised on the possibility that there might exist some form of continuity between the prehistoric and contemporary phases of the cluster – proved this assumption to be incorrect. Nevertheless, this finding itself illustrates how sudden shocks, supported by an urban environment generally conducive to innovation and by a cultural climate that fosters creativity, can give rise to an industry of high creative value and considerable quality, emerging almost from nothing.

5 THE BRNO CLUSTER

5.1 Data collection and analysis

For this historical overview of the Brno cluster, we drew from original interviews, contemporary media interviews and documentaries, and archived documents (both online and offline).

We conducted seven original interviews with key people in the history of the Brno game development community (see Table 10). Some of them have already been interviewed by the media and researchers, but several – M. B., M. J., P. VI., and P. V. – have rarely spoken to the press or historians (at least in recent years), making their interviews particularly valuable. The selection of the interviewees covers the three studios that were instrumental in developing game production in Brno: Illusion Softworks, Pterodon, and Altar Interactive. We also included P. P., who was an active hobbyist developer from the late 1980s to the mid-1990s. In addition, we consulted the interviews collected for D4.1, some of which addressed the cluster’s history. We also drew from older interviews conducted for our team member Jaroslav Švelch’s book *Gaming the Iron Curtain*, namely interviews with Aleš Martiník and Petr Mihula, who were members of the 8-bit hobbyist and gaming scene in the 1980s (Švelch, 2018). All interviewees are men, reflecting the fact that game development was overwhelmingly male in the 1990s and 2000s in Czechoslovakia and the Czech Republic.

We collected 63 relevant retrospective and archived documents. Especially valuable was the series of retrospective video interviews – usually quite comprehensive and detailed – with Czech game developers made by the Vision Game website. We used the interviews with Roman Hladík (Petr, 2020b), Vladimír Chvátil (Petr, 2024c), Jaroslav Kolář (Petr, 2020a), Radim Křivánek (Petr, 2023b), David Šemík (Petr, 2023a), Jaroslav Turna (Petr, 2024a), and Lukáš Veselý (Petr, 2024b). We have previously analysed some of these interviews in D4.2, but here we focus specifically on the historical emergence of Brno’s video game industry ecosystem. Vision Game has also recently launched a two-part video documentary about Altar Interactive, which contains valuable behind-the-scenes information (Vision Game, 2025a; 2025b).

As for archived documents, especially important were contemporary reports from game studios and interviews. Around 2002-2003, for example, the Level magazine interviewed several key Czech game developers, many of them based in Brno. These must be interpreted carefully because the interviewees used them to promote their games and companies. At the same time, they offer a more immediate source, including information that might have been forgotten by the time of later interviews. We also looked at archived websites of Brno’s game studios and game-related events and sought factual information about companies in the official Czech Business Register.

Table 10. Original interviews conducted for D4.3.

Initials	Studio	Role(s) in the Brno game industry
M. B.	Illusion Softworks, Lonely Cat Games	Programmer, head of studio
V. C.	Altar Interactive	Designer, programmer
M. J.	Pterodon, Illusion Softworks	Programmer
J. K.	Pterodon Software, Pterodon, Illusion Softworks	Graphic artist, designer, head of studio
P. P.	G.C.C., NoSense	Designer, programmer, producer
P. VI.	Pterodon Software	Programmer
P. V.	Vochozka Trading, Illusion Softworks	Publisher, head of studio, producer

5.2 Cluster general historical information

5.2.1 Brief description of the cluster

Brno is the second-largest city in Czechia and the capital of the historical region of Moravia and of the South Moravian region. According to industry statistics collected by the Czech Game Developers Association (GDACZ), Brno is the second most important location for video game production in the country, with 21% of Czech studios located there compared to Prague’s 51% (GDACZ, 2023). Many of the Brno-based studios rank among the largest and most influential in the Czech Republic – see Table 11.

Table 11. A selection of notable game development studios based in Brno. This is an updated version of table BCZ8 from report D4.2.

Studio	Basic Info	Size & Structure	Specialisation
2K Czech / Hangar 13	Subsidiary of 2K, famous for the Mafia series	Approx. 80 in Brno; offices in California and Prague	Action-adventure games
Alda Games	Mobile game studio	Approx. 30	Mobile games across various genres

Amanita Design	Independent studio	Handful of developers in Brno; several teams across Czechia	Indie puzzle adventure games
Ashborne Games	Subsidiary of THQ Nordic (Embracer Group)	Approx. 15 (Mančař & Nouzová, 2025)	PC games
Bohemia Interactive	Veteran PC game studio	Approx. 120 in Brno; multiple other offices, including Prague	Shooter and simulation games
CBE Software	Small independent studio	2 developers	Horror adventure games
Czech Games Edition	Board game publisher with a digital division	Approx. 15 in Brno; Prague branch develops board games; Brno branch does digital versions	Family board games
GIANTS Software	International studio famous for Farming Simulator	Approx. 30 in Brno; multiple other offices, including Germany and Switzerland	Simulation games
Ingame Studios	Newer studio established by veteran developers (subsidy of Digital Bros./505 Games)	Approx. 70	Cooperative multiplayer shooter games
Madfinger Games	Veteran game studio	Approx. 80	Shooter games originally for mobile platforms, recently for PC
Nox Games	Mobile game studio	Approx. 30	Mobile games across various genres
Warhorse Studios	Subsidy of PLAION (part of the Embracer Group), famous for Kingdom Come: Deliverance	Approx. 30; Prague HQ and a new Brno office	Medieval role-playing games

The game development community in Brno is represented by the Game Cluster („Herní klastr“ in Czech) organisation, which was founded in 2020 and represents the core community of the ecosystem. However, in this document, we will discuss the cluster with lowercase “c”, meaning the whole ecosystem of game development in Brno. For more information about the Game Cluster organisation and the current state of game production in Brno, see [GAME-ER Reports D4.1 and D4.2](#).

5.3 Temporal perimeter: Cluster History

5.3.1 ‘Year Zero’

As already shown in [GAME-ER Report D4.1](#), the historical evolution of the cluster (meaning the ecosystem, not the organisation) can be divided into five phases: (1) mainframe and minicomputer era (until the early 1980s), (2) the amateur phase (in the 1980s, continuing into the early 1990s), (3) the semi-professional phase (from early 1990s to late 1990s), (4) the professionalisation phase (around 1997 to mid-2000s), and (5) the consolidation phase (mid-to-late 2000s).⁸ These phases are not clear-cut and often overlap. For instance, amateur game-making continued throughout the later decades but was overshadowed in its cultural and economic impact by commercial production. The institutionalisation of the cluster started in the 2010s.

If we understand the cluster in the broader sense of a functional industry ecosystem (as opposed to an institutionalised association), it is the year 1997 that is likely to be accepted as the cluster’s Year Zero and the beginning of the cluster’s professionalisation phase. In August 1997, the Brno-based entrepreneur and games publisher Petr Vochozka secured investment from the finance company Cash Reform Group and founded the development studio Illusion Softworks, which quickly attracted a group of developers from both within and outside of the city. Around the same time, Jaroslav Kolář and Michal Janáček, who had just returned from a stint in the German game industry, incorporated the company Pterodon s.r.o., which soon started collaborating with Illusion Softworks. In the same year, the Prague-based tabletop role-playing game and board game publisher Altar founded its Brno branch, Altar Interactive, specialising in computer game development. Unlike previous amateur and semi-professional operations, these three companies had stable offices and full-time workers. The three companies formed the backbone of the Brno game industry in the professionalisation phase. Thanks to their success in creating internationally recognised games like *Hidden & Dangerous* (1999), *Original War* (2001), *Mafia* (2002), and *Vietcong* (2003), along with Prague-based Bohemia Interactive’s *Operation Flashpoint*, the 1999–2004 period has been retrospectively called the “golden era” of the Czech game industry (Rohlík, 1998; bACH, 2012). At this point, Brno played an outsize role in the national industry. When the Czech gaming magazine Score compiled a list of the top ten Czech and Slovak games of all time in 2008, five of them were made in Brno (compared to

⁸ We have changed the names of these phases since D4.1 to more consistently reflect the change in the status of game workers.

three from Prague and two from Bratislava), leading the author to exclaim that “Moravia rules!” (Modrák, 2008, p. 50).

In the following two subsections, we will provide short summaries of the cluster’s historical development, which will be elaborated in more detail in section 5.5.

5.3.2 Before ‘Year Zero’

Before the Year Zero of the cluster in 1997, game production in Brno was mainly the domain of amateurs and semi-professionals. There is little to no documentation of games from the *mainframe and microcomputer phase*, but we can reasonably assume that games were being played and programmed (or adapted) by computer programmers and operators, as well as programming students (see 5.5.1. During the amateur phase in the 1980s and early 1990s, the overwhelming majority of game production was hobbyist and non-commercial. The significant Brno-based game authors at this time included Aleš Martiník, the Mihula brothers, and the Genial Computer Company (GCC) collective, whose work will be described in more detail in 5.5.1. During this period, many computer hobbyists were members of local computer clubs. Before 1989, these were mostly run by the Czechoslovak paramilitary organisation Svazarm (The Union for Cooperation with the Army). After 1989, they transformed into non-profit organisations, but their significance gradually waned (Švelch, 2018).

In the *semi-professional phase*, several Brno-based hobbyists started licensing their games to Czech publishers such as Proxima and Ultrasoft (for the Sinclair ZX Spectrum compatible computers) and later Vochozka Trading (for the Commodore Amiga and PC platforms). Among the key developer figures in Brno were Jaroslav Kolář and Petr Vlček (working as Pterodon Software), and Pavel Pospíšil and Jakub Dvorský (who worked under the label NoSense). However, at this point, all of them were students and making games was not their professional occupation. While the publishers were initially all based outside of Brno, Petr Vochozka of Vochozka Trading moved from the small town of Polička to Brno in 1995, laying the groundwork for the formation of the cluster.

Educational institutions played a crucial role, mainly by bringing like-minded people together and creating opportunities for collaboration; this will be further discussed in 5.4.2 and 5.5.1.

5.3.3 Institutional support before the cluster

Before 1989, the computer hobby was supported by youth organisations, and most notably by the paramilitary organisation Svazarm. Svazarm’s general aim was to train civilians, and especially young people, for potential roles in the military. In reality, Svazarm had become an umbrella for a wide range of hobby activities, including motorsports, dog training, marksmanship, ham radio, aviation, hi-fi, and electronics, often with no direct military application. In 1982, the organisation explicitly mentioned “building of various programs for calculations and games on programmable calculators and personal microcomputers” as one of the supported activities (Amatérské radio, 1982, p. 140). The reason was, however, not to create an industry, but to teach young people how to program. In the 1990s and 2000s, game production did not have direct official institutional or governmental

support. The main reason for the institutionalisation of the cluster in the 2010s was the negotiation with the local institutions and authorities about their potential support. The indirect influences of the industry, education, and other sectors will be detailed below.

5.4 Determining factors in the history of the cluster

5.4.1 Historical circumstances and events surrounding the local industry

Today, Brno is the Czech Republic's second-largest city, and its industrial and cultural significance is often compared to the larger and more populous capital, Prague. However, we should understand Brno not only in relation to Prague and today's Czechia, but also to other regions and cities. Brno is geographically closer to both Vienna and Bratislava than Prague. Since medieval times, Brno was the centre of the Margraviate of Moravia, which enjoyed varying degrees of autonomy from the Kingdom of Bohemia and later from the Habsburg monarchy. Following the formation of independent Czechoslovakia in 1918, Brno had to reorient from Austria's capital of Vienna towards Prague, which became the new country's capital. Within Czechoslovakia, Brno had an advantageous location in the geographical centre of the country. That was one of the important benefits of organising the official 1928 Exhibition of Contemporary Culture, commemorating the tenth anniversary of the new country, in Brno – instead of, for example, Prague (Jeřábek, 2008).

As a part of the Moravian German enclave, Brno had a majority German population until WWI. Brno's most famous historical figure is likely Gregor Mendel, the German-speaking Augustinian monk well-known as the founder of genetics. The ethnic make-up of this city changed with Czechoslovak independence and the subsequent influx of Czech-speaking students, public servants and other related professions. Germans nevertheless still accounted for 36% of citizens in 1921 (Jašš & Fňukal, 2009). Brno's multicultural and multilingual nature was drastically reduced during and after WWII due to the displacement of the Jewish and later German populations. However, the city's multi-ethnic history has left a trace in the Brno dialect or "hantec".

Brno has a long industrial history dating back to the 19th century, starting with the textile industry, after which the city was given the nickname "Austrian Manchester" based on its location in the Habsburg monarchy (Vaishar et al., 2025). In the 20th century, Brno transitioned to the machinery industry, exemplified by, for example, the gun manufacturer Zbrojovka Brno or the tractor manufacturer Zetor. The focus on machinery production continued during the interwar republic (1918–1938) and under the Communist regime (1948–1989). The industrial focus went hand in hand with the focus on technical education, with the city's first technical university founded already in 1873. The machinery sector shrank significantly after the end of the Communist regime, and Brno has shifted its focus to software development, in part thanks to a major investment by IBM in 2001 (Ženka et al., 2017).

5.4.2 Exogenous factors

This section will describe how Brno's characteristics relevant to game production evolved in the 1980s and 1990s. Brno's status as a large urban centre (with close to 400,000 inhabitants in 1991) and an industrial hub was reflected in the need for educational institutions. On the level of higher education, the most relevant institutions were the Brno University of Technology (BUT) and Masaryk University (MUNI). BUT was an early adopter of digital computing, acquiring its first computer in 1961 and founding its Department of Automatic Computers in 1964 (Blatný, 1985). Regarding other avenues of education relevant to games, the Janáček Academy of Performing Arts has hosted theatre and music programs since 1947. Interestingly, Brno had no higher education programme in visual arts until 1993, when the Faculty of Fine Arts was founded at BUT, combining art and technology. Several graduates of the faculty went into the game industry starting in the early 2000s, and the faculty became a key site for indie and art games.

Lower-level institutions were equally important. Three of the key early developers of PC games – Jaroslav Kolář, Petr Vlček, and Pavel Pospíšil – attended the same “elite” *gymnázium* (grammar school) on Slovanské náměstí square. Despite the Communist regime's proclaimed goals of equality, its educational policies resulted in the segregation of the working class and the intelligentsia (Simonová, 2006), meaning that the children of Brno's intelligentsia clustered in the same institutions, forging friendships and collaborations – but also limiting the chances of students from the working class and from the countryside. At least in the early years of game production, the schools' primary contribution was not the knowledge they taught (the programming classes and courses were often outdated or not applicable in game development) but the access to computers and, even more importantly, the meeting spaces that they created. In 1994, Kolář, Vlček, and Pospíšil spent much of their free time in a computer classroom without any supervision or instruction, working on their own projects. As J. K. attests, *“I am absolutely sure that this had enormous influence on us even starting anything because when you're sitting at home you can tinker around, but if you have three people around, they can show each other what they're doing and it has a much better effect.”*

Brno has also been the home of numerous research institutions, creating a significant population of technical intelligentsia, whose members had access to computers and were likely to support their children in pursuing hobbies such as computing. Vladimír Chvátil first encountered computers thanks to his mother, who worked in the Knitting Research Institute, while Pavel Pospíšil got his first computer games from his father's colleagues at the Research Institute of Macromolecular Chemistry.⁹ Many engineers working in the machinery industry also had access to computers, as was the case with Jaroslav Kolář's father, a programmer at Zbrojovka Brno.

The Brno Exhibition Centre was a significant boon for the city. Over the years, Brno's trade fairs have become the biggest and most important in the country. In the 1980s, the exhibition centre was a site of pilgrimage for many Czechoslovaks who saw it as an opportunity to purchase products unavailable in retail and to get a glimpse of Western consumer culture. Founded in 1970, Invex

⁹ Both institutes were privatised in the 1990s but still exist as private R&D companies.

(shortened from “International Exhibition of Inventions and Innovations”) gradually became the country’s number one trade fair for digital technologies (Svoboda, 1983). During its heyday in the 1990s, and it was arguably the biggest IT fair in post-Communist Europe (Peterka, 2005). The 1994 instalment even featured Bill Gates as a guest. In the mid-1990s, Invex started exhibiting games and attracted thousands of young people. The exhibitors included local hardware companies, game retailers, game developers, and game magazines (Lachtan [Martin Kalivoda], 1996). However, the gaming section was oriented towards consumers rather than developers. Its direct contribution to the formation of the cluster was therefore limited because Western game publishers – the most valuable contacts – did not attend.

Hobby computing clubs were instrumental in providing access to hardware and circulating home computing knowledge, skills, and software, especially in the 1980s when a software market did not exist and publishing was stunted by censorship. Brno-based game makers active in the 1980s (Aleš Martiník and the Mihula brothers) were all members of local clubs. Starting in the 1980s, Brno had separate official clubs catering to owners of Sinclair, Atari, Commodore, and Sharp computers (Grospietsch, 1994). In the 1990s, however, the importance of clubs waned as hardware, software and computing literature became readily accessible. In part, their role was replaced by demo scene events. Especially important for Brno was Re-setkání, a recurring event organised by the Czechoslovak Commodore Amiga community, whose first instalment took place in December 1992 in the great meeting hall of the Vlněna textile factory (AMIGA Star, 1992). Demographically, hobby computing was a regionally diverse but overwhelmingly male domain, dominated by young men (Švelch, 2018).

Another important hobby community was the science fiction and fantasy fandom. While the fandom was active throughout Czechoslovakia, especially in the 1980s (Adamovič, 2017), Brno was one of its important centres. V. C. of Altar Interactive joined the science fiction club NYX (founded in Brno in 1983) and its offshoot, the Czech Tolkien Society (founded in 1992), and attended their early LARP (live action role-playing) events. As he puts it, *“it was not just about sci-fi or fantasy, it was about meeting creative and driven individuals – a necessary foundation to actually start working together on something.”* Unlike Illusion Softworks and Pterodon, who came out of the computer hobbyist and demo scene milieu, Altar Interactive had its roots in sci-fi/fantasy fandom and tabletop roleplaying. Compared to hobby computing, the fandom was less male-dominated.

Brno has also been a home to a lively cultural and arts scene. While not having a stable film production industry of its own, it has hosted the regional branches of the country’s public broadcasters: Czechoslovak (later Czech) Radio since 1924 and Czechoslovak (later Czech) Television since 1961. In the 1970s and 1980s, it was famous for its small experimental theatre scenes, such as the Husa na provázku (Goose on a String) Theatre and Hadivadlo, which managed to stage progressive and innovative plays while evading the demands of censors (Beck, 1996). Some of the first local games with voice acting – *Dragon History* (1995) and *Asmodeus: The Mysterious Land of Ruthaniol* (1997) – feature voice talent from local theatres and amateur theatre groups. Brno was also a major centre of popular and rock music, spawning among others the progressive rock band Progres 2, who wrote science fiction rock operas about computers, robots, and space exploration, staged in collaboration with the Husa na provázku Theatre.

5.4.3 Role of neighbouring industries

As mentioned in 5.4.2, Brno benefited from the presence of research institutions and universities, and generally any institutions and industries that could provide access to computers – independently of those industries’ specific focus.

The most notable “neighbouring” software industry in Brno is the non-entertainment software industry. The first successful companies, such as Grisoft (later renamed to AVG Technologies for its flagship anti-virus software suite), emerged in the early 1990s. The industry received a big boost following IBM’s investment in 2001 (Ženka et al., 2017). The presence of a “serious” software industry supports the image of Brno as a hub of IT and innovation, which might have, in turn, fed into more institutional support for IT-related industries and study programmes, creating a synergistic situation. However, the interviews with cluster members from D4.1 do not mention the serious software industry as a factor contributing to the formation of Brno’s game industry. The role of this industry is therefore indirect. Brno also has strong semiconductor and electron microscope industries; both tangentially related to digital games (#brnoregion 2025).

5.4.4 Role of other/proto-industries concerning the current cluster

The Brno’s Zbrojovka Brno factory produced not only firearms but also typewriters and computers, including the Consul 2717, an 8-bit microcomputer that was never sold to end users but made it to some schools and computer clubs where it was used to teach programming (Skovajsa, n.d.). The machine was compatible with another Czechoslovak platform, the TESLA PMD 85. Despite this fact, there was no continuity between this machine and later game production.

5.4.5 Factors that influenced the birth and development of local industry

Since the 1990s, local game production in Brno (and the whole of Czechia) evolved into a fairly stable political, economic, and legal environment. The formation and continuation of the cluster were affected by the fact that Czechia was a post-Soviet, post-communist economy and society. Before 1989, private enterprise was virtually non-existent. The switch to a market economy opened a space for young budding entrepreneurs, such as P. V. of Illusion Softworks, who remembers reading self-help books on how to become a successful businessman, which were popular at the time. At the same time, the costs of production were relatively lower than in the West. According to P. V., making games was twice as cheap in Czechia as opposed to the U.S. (Polách, 2001), and the costs were even lower in Brno than in Prague.

Sections 5.4.1 to 5.4.4 have shown several factors that created favourable conditions for the formation of the cluster in Brno. Among the chief factors were the size of the city and high-quality education institutions that attracted talented young people. At the same time, these higher-level contextual factors interacted with serendipitous circumstances and individual decisions. Petr Vochozka, the founder of Illusion Softworks, originally hails from a small town of Polička, about 80

km away from Brno and 180 km from Prague. He started his publishing and distribution business, Vochozka Trading, while in Polička. He briefly moved to Prague to study at the Czech Technical University, but he dropped out and moved to Brno primarily for personal reasons – to be closer to his high school friends (P.V.) The fact that Pterodon Software, which had published games with him, also happened to be based there was an added bonus. The investor Jan Kudera, who co-founded Illusion Softworks with Vochozka, was also considering basing his company in Prague but eventually picked Brno for several reasons: lower costs, a loyal workforce, and a geographic location that allowed him to easily travel to both Czechia and Slovakia (Pospíšil, 2001).

5.4.6 Role of the territory for continuity/connection factors between before and after the birth of the cluster

After the birth of the cluster, the territory of Brno continued to be advantageous for the game industry. Brno’s shift from machinery towards IT industries, as well as the 2001 IBM investment, was a parallel development, which might have had a synergistic effect on the game industry. As Illusion Softworks, Pterodon, and Altar Interactive grew, they attracted more workers both from within and outside Brno. Some of them were semi-amateur developers with whom Vochozka had collaborated during his time as a publisher; some of them came from Slovakia, testifying to the continuing legacy of Czechoslovakia and the central position of Brno in the Czecho-Slovak space. By 2002, the largest Brno-based games company, Illusion Softworks, had teams not only in Brno, but also in Prague, Zlín, Bratislava, and Košice, covering most of former Czechoslovakia (saver, 2002).

Figure 16. A map of Illusion Softworks’ studios with Brno in the centre, originally published in an interview on the Sector.sk website.

The interview data suggests that while Brno’s proximity to Slovakia is of great importance, the proximity to Austria is not, except for the connection to the Vienna airport, often used for trips from and to Brno. The ties with the Austrian game industry have been and still are negligible, in part because the Austrian industry is less developed than the Czech one (Schneider & Koller, 2024), with the exception of the successful independent company Moon Studios.

5.5 Detailed historical timeline before the birth of the cluster and continuity factors

5.5.1 'New' historical timeline

This section will focus on the first three phases of the cluster's evolution, from the 1960s to 1997.

In the mainframe and minicomputer era (1960s to late 1970s), access to computer technology was mostly limited to a small group of specialised professionals. However, there is one important exception. Already in 1960, the International Engineering Fair in Brno exhibited a digital relay-based machine that could play the mathematical game Nim against human players, similarly to the 1940 US device Nimatron. It was designed by Pavel Pelikán, a young Czech computer scientist based at the Research Institute for Mathematical Machines in Prague (Bernášek, 2023). While made in Prague, the fact that it was exhibited in Brno serves as evidence of the Brno fair's status as a premier location for presenting technical innovations. While the machine was not a programmable computer but a custom-made single-purpose machine, it did use logic circuits, and is therefore probably the first publicly exhibited digital game in Czechoslovakia. It attracted ample interest from media and visitors to the fair ((Ih), 1960; Sdělovací technika, 1960).

The first people with the opportunity to play and program computer games in Brno were the programmers and operators of mainframe computers. Such computers were located in Brno's universities, factories, and institutions since at least the 1960s (Blatný, 1985). Vladimír Chvátíl, for example, remembers playing Hammurabi and Star Trek on a mainframe at the Knitting Research Institute. The mainframes were later followed by cabinet-sized minicomputers. Unfortunately, no original Czech game software for these platforms has been preserved so far.

In the amateur phase (from around 1980 to early 1990s), computer games were produced by hobbyists and distributed for free, in part because late socialist Czechoslovakia offered no commercial market for software. The early Western 8-bit home computers like the Sinclair ZX81 and the Sinclair ZX Spectrum started arriving in Czechoslovakia, including Brno, in the early 1980s. Many of them were individually imported from Western Europe, as home computers were only rarely available through Czechoslovak retail channels (Švelch, 2018). At the time, much of hobby computing and game making took place in computer clubs and collectives and depended on bottom-up activities of local hobbyists. The official clubs were usually affiliated with the paramilitary organisation Svazarm (see 5.3.3), although their day-to-day activities lacked ideological or political content. Another important hub was at the Brno University of Technology (BUT), where a group of students were exchanging and playing games. One of the earliest preserved Czechoslovak games is a conversion of the ZX Spectrum game *Manic Miner* to the earlier ZX81, programmed by the BUT student Aleš Martiník in the summer of 1984. Another BUT student, Petr Mihula (or Májasoft), was an active developer of ZX Spectrum games, making, among others, the popular text adventure *Fast Arrows: The Mystery of the Conundrum* (Rychlé šípy: Záhada hlavolamu, 1988), featuring characters from a popular Czechoslovak comic series. Mihula often worked with his younger brother Ondřej (or CIDSofT), forming the productive software development duo MS-CID (Švelch, 2018).

As computers became more readily available throughout the 1980s, they got into the hands of more and younger kids, who also engaged in building their networks and communities. One of them was Genial Computing Company (GCC), a loose collective of middle school friends from the centre of Brno, who, starting in 1989, ran an impressive hand-made fanzine, created with ball-point pens and felt-tip markers, and bound by needle and thread (P. P.). Some of the collective members also made amateur games, which they initially distributed for free.

1989's Velvet Revolution brought profound changes to the Czech society and economy, among other things, by abolishing censorship, opening the borders, and allowing free enterprise. Soon, it became possible to secure commercial nationwide distribution for games, triggering the start of the semi-professional phase (from early 1990s to late 1990s) of digital game development. Initially, no significant publisher resided in Brno. Local hobbyists – including GCC and the Mihula brothers – licensed their ZX Spectrum games to companies like Proxima (based in the North Bohemian city of Ústí nad Labem) or Ultrasoft (based in Bratislava). The royalties provided a decent side income for the student authors, although they did not suffice for professionalisation. As GCC's P. P. remembers: *"It was better than delivering leaflets to mailboxes."* In total, he sold 4,300 copies of all his games combined, including an unofficial conversion of the Russian MS-DOS game *Perestroika* (1991) and a *Tetris*-like puzzle game *Magic Dice* (1993).

Around 1993, local enthusiasts started to make games for the MS-DOS-equipped PCs. An important hub of activity was an after-school computer club at the high school on Slovanské náměstí (see 5.4.2), where the GCC alumnus Pavel Pospíšil hung out with Jaroslav Kolář and Petr Vlček, who called themselves Pterodon Software. While working on their new games, the three young men helped each other but also engaged in friendly competition (J. K., P. P.). Pterodon Software created the PC point'n'click adventure *The Secret of Donkey Island* (*Tajemství Oslího ostrova*, 1994), a spoof of Lucasfilm's *Monkey Island* games. Pospíšil, joined by a group of other high school and university students from Brno (including Jakub Dvorský, who later founded Amanita Design), designed and directed the fairy-tale adventure *Dragon History* (*Dračí historie*, 1995).

Both games were published by the young entrepreneur and video game fan Petr Vochozka, who did his business under the label Vochozka Trading. Originally from the town of Polička, about 80 km away from Brno, he used to come to the city for the Re-setkání Amiga events, where he connected with hobbyist developers and sold his first products (P. V.). Vochozka also had contacts in the Prague-based gaming magazine *Excalibur*, which published his ads and gave his games forthcoming reviews. Both *The Secret of Donkey Island* and *Dragon History* found success on the local market. The games had their flaws, but – in part thanks to humorous dialogues in Czech – *Dragon History* was released on a CD-ROM (alongside a floppy version) and was the first Czech (or Slovak) game featuring full voice-overs, setting expectations for future games. Vochozka moved to Brno in 1995, and the recording of *Dragon History*'s voiceovers – performed by a local amateur theatre group – already took place in Vochozka Trading's offices (P. V., J. K.). The offices also functioned as a warehouse and a retail location. According to J. K., the space could be considered the first hub of the nascent industry cluster: *"[Vochozka] did incredibly great work at finding skilled individuals and putting them together. [...] The people whom he had connected would then visit the office. [...] It*

became a hub of sorts. People went there, sometimes they would play games. It was not some stranger's company, it was like visiting a friend."

A community therefore already existed, but the existence of development teams was volatile because of the lack of stable funding. Pospíšil did not see a future in the game development business and quit soon after releasing the game, while Kolář and Vlček moved to Germany to develop games in a studio called Virtual X-Citement, recently founded by former employees of Blue Byte (J. K., P. Vl.). The transfer – which also included two other Czech developers Michal Janáček (from the town of Nové Město nad Metují) and Michal Mariánek (from Třebíč) – was mediated by Vochozka, who planned to distribute the resulting games in the Czech Republic (P. V.). For the young developers, their first Western experience was very different from what they expected. As J. K. remembers, *"they [German managers] did not understand game development. [...] It was a completely different experience than [...] joining a large team of professionals. We were actually building the team of professionals ourselves."* The Czech-German team produced the real-time strategy game *Akte Europa* (1997), but Kolář and Janáček eventually decided to move back to Czechia and start their own studio in Brno. Mariánek also returned to Czechia and eventually moved to Brno to study at BUT's Faculty of Fine Arts, while also working at Pterodon with Kolář and Janáček. Only Petr Vlček remained in Germany, eventually heading the FIFA Manager team at EA Sports' studio in Cologne, and later co-founding the studio Bright Future.

Around 1996, Vochozka's publishing business started facing intense competition from the Prague-based company JRC, the dominant Czech games retailer that was expanding into publishing. At the same time, development costs were rising because of the advancement of hardware. One way to run a profitable development business was to address international markets. But as Vochozka learned while attending international trade fairs like the European Computer Trade Show (ECTS), making games that would be competitive abroad required a significant amount of investment capital (P. V.). After four or five unsuccessful attempts, he was referred to the investor Jan Kudera of the factoring company Cash Reform Group (Rohlík, 2002). Vochozka presented Kudera with a pitch about developing games for the Western markets, and the latter was convinced. As the former has put it, *"[Kudera] likely believed that we can make a game at local costs and sell it for global money."* (P. V.) The two founded Illusion Softworks in August 1997, with Kudera investing 4 million CZK (equivalent to 10 million CZK or 400,000 EUR in 2025, when adjusted for inflation). Given how cash-strapped the industry had been until that point, this was a momentous turning point. In addition to the money, Kudera was involved in creating the company strategy and provided accounting and legal services (Rohlík, 2002).

Vochozka gathered some of his collaborators and invited new ones through magazine ads (Smolík, 1998). Former hobbyists from different parts of Czechia and Slovakia moved to Brno and started working full-time in the company. The early hires included Michal Bačík from the Slovak city of Banská Bystrica, who had previously released a game called *Lurid Land* (1997) through Vochozka. Illusion Softworks' initial project was an unreleased isometric action game called *For Rent*. After negotiations with potential publishers, it was cancelled in favor of a fully 3D tactical shooter, *Hidden & Dangerous* (1999), with Bačík assuming the role of the lead (and only) programmer and co-designer (M. B.) Vochozka managed to establish a fruitful publishing cooperation with the U.S.

publisher Take-Two Interactive, which was currently expanding and on the lookout for quality games. At the same time, both Kudera and himself were aware of the value of intellectual property in the video game industry – in part thanks to their familiarity with the “ten commandments” for developers written by Mike Wilson, founder of the developer-run publisher Gathering of Developers, and unlike Prague-based Bohemia Interactive, who sold IP rights to *Operation Flashpoint* to the U.K. company Codemasters, Illusion Softworks kept control of all their IPs (P. V., J. K.).

Also in 1997, Jaroslav Kolář and Michal Janáček returned from their German adventure and started a new incarnation of Pterodon, which – while an independent company – became a de facto subcontractor to Illusion Softworks, making their own games for Take-Two, the first being *Flying Heroes* (2000). Overall, there were around 20 developers working at Illusion Softworks and Pterodon in 1998 (Smolík, 1998), all of them young men (J. K.)

In 1997, the Prague-based tabletop RPG and board game publisher Altar opened its game development division Altar Interactive, which was based in Brno because that was the residence of the core designers and programmers, Vladimír Chvátil and Radim Křivánek. Unlike Illusion Softworks, Altar Interactive was funded only from the personal funds of company owners, partly because they wanted full control of the company (Vision Game, 2025b). Rather than producing digital adaptations of Altar’s non-digital games, Altar Interactive produced entirely original titles, which, according to V. C., “had no big commercial success but incredibly devoted fans.” Their first game was the narrative puzzle game *Fish Fillets* (sometimes listed as *Fillets*, 1998), which they unsuccessfully offered to international publishers and eventually self-published in the Czech Republic (Vision Game, 2025a).¹⁰ Their breakthrough title was the real-time strategy/RPG hybrid *Original War* (2001), published worldwide by Virgin Interactive. Although the game achieved only modest sales, it has attracted a loyal fan base, which has been modding and playing the game to this day (V. C.) In part thanks to their origins in the sci-fi/fantasy fandom, which was more gender diverse than hobby computing, Altar Interactive collaborated with three women who participated in making their first two games. Two of them were spouses of the developers and none of them were full-time employees, but they all made notable creative contributions.

5.5.2 Continuity factors between before and after the cluster

The professionalisation phase of the cluster, which started in 1997, resulted in a series of successful titles. Besides *Hidden & Dangerous* and *Original War*, these included Illusion Softworks’ *Mafia* (2002) and Pterodon’s *Vietcong* (2003) and *Vietcong 2* (2005). *Mafia* reportedly sold over 2 million copies by 2008 on all platforms combined, which was an admirable number at the time (Modrák, 2008).¹¹ The contemporary Czech press also noted the sudden rise in quality caused by professionalisation, with a local magazine describing the production value of *Hidden and Dangerous* as “absolutely unbelievable by Czech standards” (Smolík, 1998, p. 25). The 1999–2004 period was

¹⁰ The source code and data were later released under GNU/GPL, and the fan community created the *Fish Fillets Next Gen* version, which has been ported to multiple platforms and translated to numerous languages.

¹¹ Another big Czech success was *Operation Flashpoint* (2001) by Prague’s Bohemia Interactive.

later retrospectively called the “golden era” of the Czech game industry (Rohlík, 1998; Bach, 2012). To woo Western publishers, local studios mostly shifted from local themes to those that they believed would resonate in the West. The head of Illusion Softworks Petr Vochozka has previously admitted that he was never a fan of science fiction and fantasy (Rohlík, 2003). The combination of external and internal factors then led to the orientation towards themes like warfare and organised crime.

Despite these successes, it is important to note that in the early days of these studios, the development process and its management were not yet formalised. Development roles were often not fully differentiated, and the responsibility for design was not clearly assigned. Much of the design emerged organically by adding features that felt subjectively important to the developers, although they might not have been critical to core gameplay (M. B., P. V.). As P. V. has put it: *“We thought up all kinds of extra features because we had no idea how difficult they would be to make. But we were able to put most of them into the game and maybe that’s why it was so interesting and so good.”* This maximalist tinkering-style approach to design became a standout feature of many of the Czech games at the time. *Hidden & Dangerous* was praised by PC Gamer UK for having “more features than most other games” despite being in development for just one year (Gillen, 1999).

In part, this abundance of features was possible because the teams consisted of young workers who mobilised their enthusiasm and vocational passion (Chia, 2019), worked long hours and sometimes even slept in the offices. As M. J. remembers, *“we were young and without children and making games was our life, we even spent our free time working on it and discussing it.”* Looking back, some of the interviewees admit that it was not a healthy approach (see Vision Game, 2025b), but, at the time, it was considered the norm. At Altar Interactive, employees worked for months without regular salaries before receiving the advance for *Original War* – and then again after having spent it (Vision Game, 2025b).

Another typical feature of this phase was the emphasis on self-reliance, which can be illustrated by the example of *Hidden & Dangerous*’ engine. As the lead programmer M. B. remembers: *“[Vochozka] wanted to buy an engine from Finland, he already had a demo. And then I borrowed his 3D graphics card for a weekend, doing first attempts in 3D. I didn’t know anything about 3D beforehand. [...] Two or three weeks later, I managed to have to it [an early version of the engine] running. After some hesitation he had me doing it.”* While making in-house engines was common at the time, it was not common to give that job to a person who had no experience with 3D graphics – luckily for Illusion Softworks, M. B. was an extremely skilled and driven coder.

The teams functioned as tight-knit communities built on camaraderie and common goals. As M. B. remembers, *“we went for beers, went to discos,”* with the company co-owner Petr Vochozka often joining. In 2000, Illusion Softworks and Pterodon moved into the same building. As J. K. notes, *“this enabled the interactions of all these people, who went for lunches together, went for drinks together and spent their leisure time together.”* Although Altar Interactive was rather separate from the other companies, the scene was connected through freelancers and part-timers who worked for multiple studios, such as the sound engineer and music composer Filip Oščádal.

After the success of *Hidden & Dangerous*, Illusion Softworks started to rapidly expand. There were several external and internal reasons for it. As the head of studio P. V. has put it: “*Take-Two pushed us by wanting more games, so there was a bit of pressure there. [...] The investor wanted to accelerate a bit, potentially go public. [...] I wanted to make more games because we believed that the next ones would be just as good.*” The conditions seemed favourable as Illusion had a contract for 6+2 games and a smooth relationship with the British branch of Take-Two, which handled the publishing. In 2002, P. V. claimed that Illusion aimed to produce one game every quarter (Rohlík, 2002). The strategy included production of both AAA games and games for the budget market.

Some of the titles were subcontracted to other companies, the most high-profile of them being Pterodon. Their *Vietcong* (2003) started as a Rambo tie-in game, but Take-Two ended up not securing the license. *Vietcong 2* followed in 2005. Illusion also partnered with the upstart Brno-based studio Plastic Reality Technologies and acted as a publishing intermediary and co-producer for their first released title, *Loco-Commotion* (2001). As mentioned above, Illusion Softworks started in-house teams in multiple locations, including Prague, Zlín, Bratislava, and Košice, covering most of the former Czechoslovakia. In another 2002 interview, Petr Vochozka admitted he would have preferred if the other teams also relocated to Brno, but had to keep offices in other cities because “*people here [in Czechia and Slovakia] are not used to commute or move for work.*” (saver, 2002). While teams in Brno worked on the *Mafia* franchise and *Hidden and Dangerous 2*, the Bratislava studio worked on the stealth shooter *Chameleon* (2005), the Košice team on the tycoon game *Circus Grande* (2005) and the Zlín team on the unpublished project *Enemy in Sight*. The Prague branch provided engine technology and developed the action-flying sim hybrid *Wings of War* (2004) and several unpublished projects.

Table 12 shows the growing number of developers within the Brno game industry. The figures are based on contemporary sources such as magazines and online interviews, as well as on retrospective interviews conducted for **GAME-ER**, but should be considered approximations because the archived sources are inconsistent in terms of which professions and types of employment (full-time as opposed to part-time) get included and which do not.

Table 12. Growing numbers of full-time development staff at Brno studios. Unless specifically noted, the figures include neither non-development roles such as HR, accounting etc., nor staff located outside Brno. They do include Q&A workers.

Year	Estimated no. of full-time developers	Breakdown by studios and sources
1997	10-15	Illusion Softworks – 5 (M. B.) Altar Interactive – 4 (Vision Game, 2025a) Pterodon – 2 (J. K., M. J.)
1998	20-30	Illusion Softworks – 20, likely including admin staff (Smolík, 1998)

		<p>Illusion Softworks – 13 (J. K.)</p> <p>Pterodon – 5 (J. K.)</p> <p>Altar Interactive – 4 (Vision Game, 2025a)</p>
1999	40-50	<p>Illusion Softworks – 20 (P. V.)</p> <p>Pterodon – 15 (J. K.)</p> <p>Altar Interactive – around 10 (Vision Game, 2025b)</p>
2000	70-80	<p>Illusion Softworks + Pterodon – 80, likely including QA & admin (Rybka, 2000)</p> <p>Illusion Softworks – 30-40 (Polách, 2001)</p> <p>Pterodon (separately) – 15-20 (J. K.)</p> <p>Altar Interactive – 20 (V. C.)</p> <p>Lonely Cat Games – 3 (M. B.)</p> <p>Plastic Reality Technologies – around 3 (Codr, 2001, J. K.)</p>
2001	90-100	<p>Illusion Softworks – 30-40 (development only) (Polách, 2001)</p> <p>Illusion Softworks – 40 (J. K.)</p> <p>Illusion Softworks – 100, including admin staff and staff at other locations (Pospíšil, 2001)</p> <p>Pterodon – 25 (Polách, 2001)</p> <p>Altar Interactive – 20 (V. C.)</p> <p>Lonely Cat Games – 9 (M. B.)</p> <p>Plastic Reality Technologies – 8 (Codr, 2001)</p>

Illusion Softworks' ambitious plans did not pan out, leading to what we may call a **consolidation** phase (mid-to-late 2000s). The multiple projects across several studios became more difficult to manage. In addition, Take-Two Interactive started its internal 2K Games label in 2005, aiming to streamline its development and publishing strategies. As a result, it became more difficult to get Illusion's games published. Take-Two lost interest in the *Vietcong* series, leading to the disbanding of Pterodon, many of whom joined their partner company, Illusion Softworks (J. K.). The *Hidden & Dangerous* series was likewise discontinued, and its team went on to work on the unfinished FPS game *Moscow Rhapsody*. The Bratislava studio's *Chameleon* was declined by Take-Two and ended up being published only regionally. *Mafia II* kept hitting roadblocks for various reasons, including a switch to a new engine, the increasing complexity and labour demands of development due to new hardware, and management issues. To stabilise the situation, Illusion hired experienced managers from the U.K., taking the first steps to the internationalisation of teams beyond Czechs and Slovaks (P. V.). At this point, investor Jan Kudera was looking to sell his stake in the company (Malý, 2010), and Vochozka decided to sell, too. In 2008, Illusion Softworks was purchased by its publisher, Take-Two – a deal driven by the publisher's interest in keeping control of the *Mafia* IP – and was renamed

to 2K Czech. Around the time of the sale, several of Illusion's projects – *Enemy in Sight*, *Moscow Rhapsody*, and *Hi-Tech* – were cancelled to focus on the flagship *Mafia* series. As a result of the cancellations, some workers from remote studios moved to Brno to join the *Mafia II* team, centralising the operation. However, a large part of the Brno-based *Moscow Rhapsody* team refused to join the team and founded their own company, Vatra Games, with an investment from the British company Kuju Games. They produced games such as *Silent Hill: Downpour* (2012).

Other companies ran into difficulties, too. Altar Interactive followed *Original War* with *UFO: Aftermath* (2003), inspired by the X-COM series and initially started by the original X-COM developers. However, the company could not find a publisher for its upcoming RPG *Vision*. Due to mounting financial difficulties, the studio was sold to the Prague-based businessman Slavomír Pavlíček, co-owner of the retailer JRC and the publishing/development company Bohemia Interactive. Under the new ownership and the new label Altar Games, the studio continued producing titles in the *UFO* series and made *Fish Fillets 2*. It was later absorbed into Bohemia Interactive but kept offices in Brno. Many key staff members left the company, with Martin Klíma briefly joining the British developer Codemasters before co-founding Prague-based Warhorse Studios, and Vladimír Chvátil shifting his focus fully to board game design and co-founding the publisher Czech Games Edition, known for titles such as *Codenames* (2015) (V. C.). Plastic Reality Technologies published the RTS *Korea: Forgotten Conflict* (2003) and the *Max Payne*-inspired shooter *El Matador* (2006), neither a notable commercial success. The company folded around 2005, and many of its developers joined the *Mafia II* team at Illusion Softworks. Lonely Cat Games, a studio founded in 2000 by ex-Illusion programmer Michal Bačík, found a private U.S. investor but failed to secure a publishing deal for their ambitious action-adventure game *Atlantica*, with the team disbanding around 2005 and Bačík moving into mobile app development (M. B.).

In the 2000s, the increasing demand for labour on AAA titles made Illusion Softworks and later 2K Czech the centrepiece of Brno's industry structure, a company with a significant gravitational pull. At the same time, the industry was differentiating. Starting in the early 2000s, new avenues for development and publishing were gradually opening: mobile games, free online games funded by ads, and digital distribution of indie games on platforms like Steam. A new flock of small studios worked within these domains. Brno-based Enteron started as a group of students competing in the Becherovka game advergaming competition, organised by the liquor manufacturer Becherovka. They went on to write commissioned advergaming in Flash. Hammerware emerged from the Czech freeware scene, later producing commercial titles like the motorboat racer *Aquadelic GT* (2007). Noxgames likewise started making Flash games around 2005 before moving on to mobile. All three abovementioned teams scored in the Becherovka Game competition, which was an important platform for the nascent Czechoslovak independent scene. A later addition, Madfinger Games started in 2009 as a side project of Vatra Games and Illusion/2K Czech developers, initially specialising in premium mobile games before making the successful extraction shooter *Grey Zone Warfare* (2024) for PC and becoming one of Brno's largest game companies.

Perhaps the most influential indie studio with its roots in Brno is Amanita Design, the company behind the *Samorost* series (2003, 2005, 2016) and *Machinarium* (2009). Its founder, Jakub Dvorský, had already contributed to *Dragon History* in 1995 – while still in high school – and led the

development of the adventure/dungeon crawler *Asmodeus: The Mysterious Land of Ruthaniol* (1997), one of the last games published by Vochozka Trading before its transformation into Illusion Softworks. His first work under the label Amanita Design was the freeware adventure game *Samorost* (2003), originally made as his final project at the Academy of Arts, Architecture and Design in Prague. Amanita later evolved into an indie studio consisting of multiple small teams – however, while maintaining an office in Brno, the majority of the studio is based in Prague.

5.6 Conclusions

Sections 5.4.1. to 5.4.5. have shown several factors that created favourable conditions for the formation of the cluster in Brno. Among the chief factors were the size of the city and high-quality educational institutions that attracted talented young people.

Nevertheless, most interviewees agree that the most important factor was the early success of Brno's companies in finding funding (both from investors and publishers) and making several successful, profitable games. As M. J. has put it: *"It works like that in Prague, too, doesn't it? These are larger university cities. It's important that someone actually starts doing it, and then it just snowballs. The experienced people end up bringing in others. If you plant a seed, it will grow."* Although *Mafia* (2002) has become Brno's best-known success story, even more crucial was the earlier success of *Hidden and Dangerous* (1999). After all, Illusion Softworks started expanding *before* the release of *Mafia*. The fact that these games were made in Brno – as opposed to, for example, Prague – was in many ways a result of serendipitous circumstances and individual decisions. The publisher and producer P. V. of Illusion Softworks does not consider himself a Brno patriot and moved there primarily for personal reasons – because his hometown friends moved there for college. The investor Jan Kudera, who co-founded Illusion Softworks, was also considering basing his company in Prague but eventually picked Brno for several reasons: lower costs, a loyal workforce, and a geographic location that allowed him to easily travel to both Czechia and Slovakia (Pospíšil, 2001).

Regarding funding, the existing historical evidence highlights the importance of local (meaning Czech) investors. Two of the largest and historically most influential Czech studios – Illusion Softworks and Prague's Bohemia Interactive – were funded by local investors, who became personally involved in running the companies and provided not only money but also business acumen and ongoing support. On the other hand, companies that started with funding from abroad, such as Lonely Cat Games and Vatra Games, turned out to be short-lived.

A critical factor for the further development of the Brno cluster from the professionalisation phase (1997) onwards was the existence of a critical mass of experienced game developers who could form cores of new studios. This highlights the importance of an established studio such as Illusion Softworks (later 2K Czech and subsequently Hangar 13) as a site of knowledge transfer and network building. At various points in time, the company started to splinter, but – according to J. K. – *"there was always a splinter group of people who had the know-how and those pulled in more people, who happened to be talented and capable. Every time there was a splinter company, it needed to hire*

perhaps 40% of its staff. And then it splintered again, making the game dev bigger and bigger." Today, many notable Brno-based studios are headed by former employees of Illusion Softworks, Pterodon, and Altar Interactive (see Table 13). It is also important to note that several veterans of the Brno industry moved to Prague, continuing the process of cross-pollination between the two major centres of Czech game development. The management of Prague-based Warhorse Studios includes Martin Klíma (former producer and co-owner at Altar Interactive) and Daniel Vávra (former lead designer at Illusion Softworks).

According to some interviewees, Brno's size and its status as Czechia's second city are an advantage because they allow creative people to work with less distraction and outside pressure. As P. P. notes, *"In a smaller city, you make do with what's already there. It gives you focus."* The city is also seen as a less competitive and more collaborative environment. V. C. comments: *"It may be just my feeling and definitely does not apply to everyone – but in Brno, I encountered more people who were devoted to making great things, while in Prague, more people actually thought about how to sell them."*

As shown in report D4.1, the current-day workers in the city's cluster understand Brno game dev as a relatively tight-knit community. This is, to an extent, the outcome of the studios' histories. Many of the Brno-based developers first connected by working on the same projects. In the early stages, Petr Vochozka – himself an outgoing and sociable person – played an important role in bringing people together. Illusion Softworks and their partner and splinter studios (such as Pterodon, Plastic Reality Technologies, and Lonely Cat Games) were always personally connected. Altar Interactive has been described by J. K. as somewhat "isolated" but was connected through the freelancer Filip Oščádal, who did sound and/or music for both Pterodon and Altar. Another important way of bringing people together was regular events. As the industry was diversifying in the 2000s, the events were critical in connecting established developers with newcomers and hobbyists. The Game Developers Session conference was launched in 2003 in the city of Uherské Hradiště, but moved to Brno for the years 2004-2009. It started out as a relatively informal event, organised by the ČeskéHry.cz (CzechGames.cz) non-profit, which originated on the eponymous online forum for hobbyist developers. Interestingly, the impetus to organise a meeting of game developers came from the hobbyist and independent space, who felt a greater need to network and meet physically. Nevertheless, the established "professionals" from Illusion Softworks and Altar Interactive took part from the very beginning (Game Developers Session 2003, 2007). While the conference moved to Prague in 2010, some of the former organisers started a new event called Game Access in 2016. The formalisation of Game Cluster as a non-profit organisation followed in 2020 (see reports D4.1 and D4.2).

Table 13. A list of veterans of the Brno game industry in the leadership of today's game studios. The rightmost column shows the years they joined one of Brno's historically important teams or companies.

Studio	Name	Title	Previous Brno studio experience
2K Czech (Hangar 13)	Roman Hladík	General Manager	Illusion Softworks (since 1997)
Czech Games Edition	Vladimír (Vlaada) Chvátil	Management member, lead designer	Altar Interactive (since 1997)
Giants Software	Lukáš Kuře	Studio Manager	Illusion Softworks (since 1997)
Ingame Studios	Jaroslav Kolář	Head of Development	Pterodon Software/Pterodon (since 1994) Illusion Softworks (since 2005)
Madfinger Games	Marek Rabas	CEO	Illusion Softworks (since 2000)
Warhorse Studios (Brno branch)	Petr Kolář	Executive Producer	Bohemia Interactive Brno, formerly Altar Interactive/Altar Games (since 2010)

6 THE LYON AND BORDEAUX CLUSTERS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter examines the historical development of two major French video game clusters: Lyon and Bordeaux, based on a comprehensive documentary base and semi-structured interviews. This analysis complements previous results provided in D4.1 and D4.2 by focusing on several important dimensions. It traces the parallel yet distinctive emergence and evolution trajectories of these two regional ecosystems from the founding of pioneering companies through their crystallisation. The two cases illustrate how industrial crises paradoxically catalysed the transformation of mono-enterprise models into diversified, resilient, and creative ecosystems characterised by sophisticated governance structures and multi-scalar coordination mechanisms and collective activities. The simultaneous collapse of the two major anchor companies – Infogrames in Lyon and Kalisto Entertainment in Bordeaux – during the 2001–2003 period created conditions for what we term "creative diaspora," a phenomenon whereby the dispersion of talent from failed companies generates new entrepreneurial ventures that collectively create more diverse and sustainable ecosystems than the original mono-enterprise models.

This chapter is organised into three main sections. The first section establishes the national context of the French video game industry during the 1990s and 2000s, examining the emergence of national coordination mechanisms through the transformation of APOM (*Association des Producteurs d'Œuvres Multimédia* - Association of Multimedia Producers) into SNJV (*Syndicat National du Jeu Vidéo* - National Syndicate for Video Games) and the development of inter-cluster collaboration. The second section analyses the Lyon cluster, focusing on the Infogrames era under Bruno Bonnell's leadership and the subsequent restructuring through Lyon Game, Imaginove, and Game Only. The third section examines the Bordeaux cluster, centred on Nicolas Gaume's Kalisto Entertainment and the post-crisis renaissance led by Asobo Studio and structured through Bordeaux Games and SO Games.

6.2 Methodological Approach

The specific characteristics of the Bordeaux and Lyon cases led us to adopt a slightly different approach from the other clusters. Field research (D4.1) and documentary research (D4.2) revealed the structuring dimension (path dependency) of their history, which was therefore given significant attention in these deliverables. Furthermore, this research has highlighted the highly centralised structure of the French video game ecosystem and the decisive role played by national-level policy instruments (notably CNC and CIJV). The French clusters are strongly shaped by national governance frameworks and sector-wide support mechanisms. For this reason, a macro-institutional analytical perspective was adopted alongside the shared WP3 framework, to ensure both analytical coherence and meaningful cross-case comparability.

6.2.1 The choice of a single chapter for the French case studies

Lyon and Bordeaux video game clusters share the same national context and, as such, they have many contextual factors in common, notably institutional aspects, which significantly influenced their emergence and catalysis. Situating these two clusters within a broader national and inter-regional framework allows a better understanding of their dynamics of development and helps to connect their individual trajectories with several significant forces that enabled and constrained their evolution. This methodological choice reflects a fundamental insight from cluster studies: regional ecosystems do not develop in isolation but are shaped by national institutional frameworks, policy environments, and inter-cluster dynamics that create enabling conditions or constraints for local development (Markusen, 1996; Porter, 2000).

Several other considerations justify the emphasis on the French national context. First, the regulatory and policy frameworks that affected both clusters – including tax policy, cultural industry support mechanisms, and educational standards – operated at the national level. Second, the systemic crisis of 2001–2003 affected the entire French video game industry, revealing structural vulnerabilities that transcended regional boundaries. The collapse of Kalisto in Bordeaux and the crisis at Infogrames in Lyon were not isolated local failures but manifestations of industry-wide weaknesses in financing structures, publisher relationships, and institutional support. Understanding how this industry-wide shock was experienced, interpreted, and responded to at the national level can shed light on why certain regional responses proved more effective than others, and how the institutional learning that occurred during this period shaped subsequent cluster development. For instance, the absence of collective representation mechanisms during the formative years of the industry (1983-2000), the subsequent creation of national advocacy organisations (APOM in 2001 transformed into SNJV in 2008), and the development of supportive public policies, all influenced how regional clusters could organise, access resources, and develop governance structures. The CIJV (*“Crédit d’impôt jeu video”* - Video Game Tax Credit), obtained through collective lobbying in 2008, benefited studios in Lyon and Bordeaux and other regions equally, demonstrating that regional outcomes could depend significantly on national-level advocacy. Third, the inter-cluster collaboration played a significant role in the structuring of the different video games clusters that emerged in France. The construction of collective governance through APOM, and subsequently SNJV, created national platforms where regional actors could coordinate, learn from each other, and develop shared resources. The federal model that emerged – bringing together representatives from Lyon, Bordeaux, Paris, and other clusters – established mechanisms for inter-regional knowledge transfer that influenced local development trajectories. Apart from the national federation meetings, other mechanisms were mobilised, including knowledge exchange through joint advocacy efforts, shared training initiatives, and coordinated international representation. They created a network of mutual learning and support that benefited all participating clusters. The Lyon cluster’s expertise in business events (Game Connection) and the Bordeaux cluster’s contributions to national governance (through Nicolas Gaume's presidency of SNJV) illustrate how regional strengths were pooled at the national level, creating collective

resources that no single cluster could have developed alone. This federal coordination model represents a distinctive feature of the French video game industry that deserves analytical attention. These cross-regional dynamics also mean that the history of either cluster cannot be fully understood without reference to the national network within which it operated.

This present chapter, therefore, adopts an integrated approach, treating Lyon and Bordeaux not as isolated case studies but as interconnected nodes within a national ecosystem.

6.2.2 The focus on anchor companies and their entrepreneurs

This chapter adopts a particular analytical focus on two anchor companies – Infogrames in Lyon and Kalisto Entertainment in Bordeaux – and their founding entrepreneurs, Bruno Bonnell and Nicolas Gaume. This choice is methodologically grounded in the specific dynamics of creative cluster genesis and formation. Anchor companies play structuring roles that extend far beyond their direct economic contributions, in the emergence of creative clusters (Feldman et al., 2005; Spigel & Vinodrai, 2021; Harris & Menzel, 2023). During their periods of growth, Infogrames and Kalisto served as training grounds for an entire generation of video game professionals, concentrating technical expertise, creative talent, and industry knowledge within their respective territories. Infogrames, at its peak, employed over 2,400 people globally, with a substantial concentration in Lyon; Kalisto employed 250-300 people in Bordeaux. The skills, relationships, and tacit knowledge accumulated within these companies became the human capital foundation upon which subsequent cluster development would build. When these anchor companies collapsed, the dispersion of their former employees generated waves of entrepreneurial activity – the “creative diaspora” – that transformed concentrated, mono-enterprise ecosystems into diversified, multi-firm clusters. Anchor companies also provide legitimation for their territories, establishing reputations that attract additional investment, talent, and institutional attention (Feldman, 2003; Markusen, 1996; Casadei et al., 2023). Lyon’s identity as a video game centre was inseparable from Infogrames’ presence; Bordeaux’s recognition derived substantially from Kalisto’s achievements. Furthermore, anchor companies create spillover effects through supplier relationships, service demands, and knowledge diffusion that benefit the broader regional economy (Spigel & Vinodrai, 2021; Chaudhary et al., 2024).

The focus on founding entrepreneurs – Bonnell and Gaume – also reflects the distinctive importance of individual agency in the early development of both the companies and the clusters they anchored (Stephens & Sandberg, 2019; Bækkelund, 2021). These figures were not merely business operators; they were institutional entrepreneurs who shaped industry practices, advocated for policy changes, and embodied visions of what the French video game industry could become. Bruno Bonnell’s ambition to make Infogrames a global entertainment leader drove strategic choices that would determine Lyon’s subsequent trajectory. Nicolas Gaume’s transition from failed company founder to national industry leader – through his presidency of APOM and then SNJV – exemplifies how entrepreneurial learning from crisis can be channelled into collective institution-building.

The analysis of these two anchor companies and their entrepreneurial journey enriches the understanding of cluster genesis by revealing, concomitantly, the common patterns and the

distinctive variations. Both clusters experienced the anchor company model, crisis-induced collapse, and creative-diaspora-driven regeneration. Yet the specific trajectories differed in timing, scale, and subsequent institutional development. Bonnell pursued aggressive external growth through acquisitions, creating a global but ultimately fragile empire. Gaume built a more technically focused company but pursued similar capital market strategies with equally devastating consequences. Both founders demonstrated remarkable capacity for reinvention after the crisis: Bonnell entered politics and subsequently returned to technology entrepreneurship; Gaume became a national industry leader before eventually rejoining international technology companies.

6.2.3 Data collection

This section describes the methodology employed for the historical research conducted on the Lyon and Bordeaux clusters. The Lyon and Bordeaux video game clusters occupy a distinctive position within the **GAME-ER** project's theoretical sample: they are among the oldest clusters examined, with both ecosystems tracing their origins to the early 1990s. Infogrames was founded in Lyon in 1983, while Kalisto Entertainment was established in Bordeaux in 1990. This temporal depth – spanning over three decades of development – presented specific methodological requirements that shaped our data collection strategy from the outset of the **GAME-ER** project.

Unlike more recently emerged clusters where contemporary observation and real-time data collection might suffice, the French cases required systematic archival research, interviews with historical actors who participated in foundational events, and careful triangulation of sources to document phenomena that occurred twenty to thirty years ago. The historical nature of these clusters necessitated a deliberate emphasis on retrospective data collection, combining primary and secondary sources to reconstruct developmental trajectories that predate the project's inception by several decades.

The research design follows an embedded approach, treating Lyon and Bordeaux as two distinct yet comparable cases within the broader context of French video game industry development. This design enables within-case analysis while also considering larger phenomena intervening at the national and international level and influencing these two clusters concomitantly.

The temporal scope extends from 1983 (the founding of Infogrames in Lyon) through 2025, encompassing over four decades of industry development. This longitudinal perspective is essential for understanding the path-dependent processes through which the two clusters emerged. The analysis pays particular attention to the critical junctures, moments of significant change, that enabled the two clusters to emerge and be established and recognised as such.

For this task, multiple methods were used to capture relevant individual accounts as well as documents of historical significance. This approach included the implementation of semi-structured qualitative interviews, informed by oral history methodologies, with relevant stakeholders, as well as the documentary analysis of relevant documents identified from a multiplicity of sources (Chapman, 2016). The work unfolded in two distinct yet interconnected operational phases, which informed each other organically.

6.2.4 Primary data: semi-structured interviews

The primary data collection conducted for Task 4.1 comprised 47 semi-structured interviews conducted between 2023 and 2025 with key stakeholders across both clusters. The interview protocol was designed to elicit detailed accounts of cluster history, governance mechanisms, collective action, and stakeholder perspectives on cluster dynamics.

Given the historical focus of this deliverable, particular attention was also devoted during the activities of T4.1 to securing interviews with actors who were directly involved during the emergence and early structuration of the clusters. Through purposive sampling specifically targeting historical actors, we conducted 13 interviews with individuals who participated directly in cluster emergence during the 1996–2007 period: 7 in Lyon and 6 in Bordeaux. These interviewees included studio founders from the Infogrames and Kalisto diaspora, initiators of early collective organisations (Lyon Game, Game Connection, Bordeaux Games), and institutional actors who facilitated the first formalisation efforts. Their first-hand accounts proved invaluable for reconstructing events and dynamics that occurred two to three decades ago.

For the interviews, a flexible script based on the Analytical Grid of the **GAME-ER** project (WP3) was generated to bring to the fore events, actors, and conditions that allowed the Lyon and Bordeaux video game clusters to emerge. The interview approach followed the principles of “responsive interviewing” (Rubin & Rubin, 2012), allowing considerable flexibility and enabling interviewees to narrate and reconstruct events in their own way. Interviews in person were prioritised, conducted at respondents’ professional locations, with virtual interviews offered as an alternative due to scheduling constraints or respondent preference.

Respondent selection followed a purposive sampling approach informed by theoretical considerations, seeking to capture diversity across several dimensions: organisational role (studio founders, association directors, public officials, educators), organisational size (micro-studios to large employers), cluster affiliation (Lyon, Bordeaux, national organisations), and career stage (industry pioneers, mid-career professionals, emerging entrepreneurs). Snowball sampling supplemented the initial purposive approach, with interviewees recommending additional informants whose perspectives would enrich the analysis.

Key informants included representatives from Game Only, SO Games, Asobo Studio, Arkane Studios, regional development agencies (Grand Lyon, Bordeaux Métropole, Région Nouvelle-Aquitaine), and national industry organisations (SNJV). Several interviews involved founding figures whose involvement spans multiple phases of cluster development – including actors present during the Infogrames and Kalisto eras of the 1990s – providing an invaluable longitudinal perspective. Interviews were conducted in French, the native language of all respondents. Their duration ranged from 60 minutes to 120 minutes. All interviews were audio-recorded with informed consent and subsequently transcribed verbatim. Transcripts were anonymised for analysis, though several respondents consented to attribution of specific statements in the final deliverables.

It should be noted that it was not possible to contact all actors involved in the clusters’ early history. In the case of Infogrames, several key figures from the 1980s and 1990s – including Bruno Bonnell himself – could not be interviewed due to scheduling constraints or non-response. Similarly, for Kalisto Entertainment, while we successfully interviewed actors who participated in the post-collapse diaspora, direct testimony from the pre-2002 period relied primarily on secondary sources and retrospective accounts from former employees who founded subsequent ventures.

Table 14. Profiles of interviewees for the historical emergence of the French clusters.

Cluster	Number of interviews	Profile of interviewees
Lyon	7	Studio founders (Infogrames diaspora), Lyon Game/Game Connection initiators, early institutional facilitators
Bordeaux	6	Studio founders (Kalisto diaspora, including Asobo founders), Bordeaux Games initiators, early ecosystem actors
Total (historical focus)	13	

6.2.5 Secondary Data: documentary Sources

The secondary data collection compiled a comprehensive documentary base of 228 sources spanning the period 1983–2025. This documentary base was organised according to a standardised reference system (FR001–FR228), enabling systematic citation and cross-referencing throughout the analysis.

While the complete documentary base covers the entire trajectory of both clusters through to the present day, particular emphasis was placed on sources documenting the emergence and early structuration phases (1983–2005). For the historical reconstruction of cluster genesis, the following source categories proved especially valuable:

Sources related to anchor companies and early industry development:

- Infogrames corporate documentation and press coverage (1983–2007), including founding narratives, expansion strategy documents, and crisis-period reporting.
- Kalisto Entertainment archives and media coverage (1990–2002), documenting the company’s growth, IPO, and subsequent liquidation.
- Contemporary press articles from regional media (Tribune de Lyon, Lyon Mag, Rue89 Bordeaux) covering the video game industry’s emergence in both territories.

Sources related to early collective organisation:

- Lyon Infocité and Lyon Game founding documents and activity reports (1999–2005).
- Game Connection business plans and financial projections (2001–2006).
- Digital Worlds feasibility study (2003).

- APOM and early SNJV documentation (2001–2008).
- Bordeaux Games founding documents and early activity reports (2007–2012).

Contextual and institutional sources:

- DATAR and regional council documentation on cluster policy (SPL - “*Système Productif Local*”, Local Productive System - programme, Competitiveness Hubs).
- CNC (“*Centre National du Cinéma et de l’image animée*” - National Centre for Cinema and the Moving Image) reports on the video game industry during the crisis period.
- Academic publications analysing the 2001–2003 industry crisis and its aftermath.

The broader documentary base additionally encompasses more recent materials – including Imaginove documentation (2005–2019), Game Only organisational documents (2019–2025), and SO Games documentation (2021–2025) – which provided essential context for understanding how early dynamics shaped subsequent cluster evolution.

The documentary analysis allowed the team to position the emergence of both clusters embedded in the broader French video game industry history and the conditions of the international video game market. Documents were coded according to a seven-dimensional analytical framework addressing: cluster emergence and founding conditions; collective actions and initiatives; industry characteristics and composition; evolutionary trajectories and phases; resource mobilisation and competencies; coordination structures and governance; and inter-organisational relationships. Given the diversity of source types – ranging from official organisational documents to press coverage to academic publications – particular attention was paid to source triangulation. Claims appearing in multiple independent sources were accorded greater confidence than those appearing in single sources.

6.2.6 Data Analysis

The analytical approach adopted for this study was abductive, iterating between empirical data and theoretical frameworks in a process of continuous refinement (Timmermans & Tavory, 2012). This approach proved particularly suited to the historical nature of the French cases, where preconceived theoretical assumptions needed to be continuously tested against documentary evidence and interview accounts that often revealed unexpected patterns and relationships.

Interview transcripts and documentary sources were analysed using AI-assisted coding procedures. The coding process leveraged large language model capabilities to identify thematic occurrences across the substantial corpus of 228 documents and 47 interview transcripts, enabling systematic pattern recognition while maintaining researcher oversight and interpretive control. This AI-assisted approach allowed for efficient processing of the large documentary base while ensuring consistency in code application across materials spanning four decades of cluster development.

The analytical process proceeded through iterative phases:

- Phase 1: Initial Coding – Each transcript and document was processed to identify relevant passages and assign preliminary codes. This first-level coding remained close to the source material, capturing both manifest content and latent meanings.

- Phase 2: Pattern Recognition – Initial codes were progressively grouped into higher-order categories through systematic comparison across sources. This phase identified relationships among codes and organised them into thematic clusters, with particular attention to temporal patterns and cross-case similarities and differences.
- Phase 3: Theoretical Integration – The final analytical phase integrated emergent themes with existing theoretical frameworks on cluster dynamics, creative industries, and institutional entrepreneurship. This abductive movement between data and theory allowed for the refinement of analytical categories and the identification of the “creative diaspora” concept as a central explanatory mechanism.

Throughout the analysis, particular attention was paid to triangulating findings across multiple source types. Claims supported by convergent evidence from interviews, archival documents, and press coverage were accorded greater confidence than those resting on single sources. Where sources offered conflicting accounts – as occasionally occurred regarding the precise timing or attribution of historical events – discrepancies were noted and, where possible, resolved through additional documentary research.

Analytical memos documented emerging interpretations, theoretical connections, and methodological decisions throughout the coding process. These memos served as intermediate products linking raw data to final analytical claims and provided an audit trail for the analytical process.

6.3 The National context of the French video games industry (1983–2010): the emergence of the “French Touch”

6.3.1 The foundation years (1983–1995): creative dynamism amid institutional void

The French video game industry has its origins in hobby computing and individual entrepreneurship rather than established industrial practice. It emerged in the early 1980s as part of a broader technological and cultural moment that saw the large diffusion of personal computing. Many early French studios emerged from communities of enthusiasts who had taught themselves programming on personal computers like the Thomson MO5 and TO7. This period was characterised by entrepreneurial dynamism, creative experimentation, and the gradual development of technical expertise, which led to the foundations of what would become a significant national industry. This grassroots creativity was a source of innovation, but it also meant that the industry developed without the institutional infrastructure that might have provided stability and collective capacity. Thus, during this period, the French video games industry was rather informal and atomised.

Beneath the creative ferment lay a fundamental structural characteristic that would shape the industry’s trajectory for decades: the near-complete absence of collective organisation and institutional support. Unlike established cultural industries such as cinema or publishing, which had developed robust professional associations, regulatory frameworks, and public support

mechanisms over many decades, the video game sector, as a nascent and digitally native industry, operated in an institutional void. There were no professional unions or trade associations representing video game developers. There were almost no collective efforts or actors responsible for articulating the industry's needs to policymakers or coordinating responses to shared challenges. There were also no dedicated public policies recognising video games as a cultural or industrial sector meriting support. The absence of industry-wide standards for employment practices, training requirements, or professional development was also a major weakness.

This lack of institutionalisation had several important consequences. Individual companies operated in isolation, with limited mechanisms for sharing knowledge, pooling resources, or coordinating action. When individual companies experienced difficulties, there were no collective mechanisms to provide support or facilitate orderly restructuring. Within this context, studios suffered from the asymmetries in bargaining power within their relationship with publishers – predominantly foreign. Publishers typically tended to retain intellectual property rights and impose terms that left studios vulnerable to project-by-project survival.

Despite this institutional void, the early French video game industry was distinguished by a “French Touch” – a distinctive approach to game design that emphasised narrative sophistication, artistic direction, and innovative gameplay mechanics (Blanchet, 2022b). This creative identity would become a source of competitive advantage for French studios in international markets, distinguishing them from the more mercantile approaches that characterised much of the industry elsewhere. Games like *Alone in the Dark* (Infogrames, 1992), which pioneered survival horror conventions and real-time 3D graphics, demonstrated that French studios could achieve both artistic innovation and commercial success.

At the firm level, apart from Infogrames and Kalisto documented in the following sections, Cryo Interactive is also a major French video game developer and publisher founded in Paris in 1992 by Philippe Ulrich and Rémi Herbulot, former Infogrames employees, along with Jean-Martial Lefranc from Virgin. Reorganised as Cryo Interactive Entertainment in 1994, it pursued an ambitious strategy of adaptation games based on prestigious intellectual properties. The company became renowned for its adventure games blending artistic ambition with historical and science-fiction settings – most notably *Dune* (1992), *Versailles 1685* (1997), and the *Atlantis* series (1997–2007). The studio's work on *Dune* (1992), developed in collaboration with Virgin Interactive, achieved both critical and commercial success, validating the approach of combining French artistic sensibility with recognisable franchises. Cryo's subsequent productions, including adaptations of *Atlantis* and various historical themes, built a substantial catalogue that positioned the company as a major French publisher.

During the same period, Ubisoft was founded in 1986 by the Guillemot brothers in Bretagne, before rising to prominence afterwards and establishing itself as a major international publisher with development studios in multiple countries. The company's success demonstrated that French-origin enterprises could compete at the highest levels of the global video game industry. Other French publishers and developers similarly expanded their international reach, building relationships with console manufacturers and developing capabilities in technically demanding production.

These parallel trajectories of the major studios established several patterns that would prove significant for cluster development. First, they demonstrated that French studios could achieve international commercial success through distinctive creative approaches rather than simply imitating American or Japanese models. Second, they revealed the instability inherent in the hit-driven economics of video game publishing, with even successful studios proving vulnerable to market shifts. Third, they created networks of relationships and flows of talent that connected the emerging regional clusters to the broader national and international industry.

Apart from the dynamics of studios' creations, the technological context of this period was also crucial to the industry's development and the establishment of the "French Touch". The transition from 8-bit to 16-bit computing platforms, followed by the emergence of CD-ROM technology and eventually 3D graphics, created successive waves of creative and commercial opportunity. French studios demonstrated aptitude for adapting to these technological transitions, developing technical capabilities that would sustain their competitiveness. Yet the absence of collective organisation meant that each studio navigated these transitions independently, without the benefit of shared learning or coordinated investment in new capabilities.

By the mid-1990s, the French video game industry had achieved notable creative success but remained fundamentally fragile. The lack of institutionalisation, combined with dependence on foreign publishers and hit-driven economics, created vulnerabilities that would be brutally exposed during the crisis of the early 2000s.

6.3.2 The Expansion era (1995–2000): National growth without national organisation

The mid-to-late 1990s represented a period of rapid expansion for the French video game industry. France represented approximately 10% of the European video game market. This was an era of remarkable commercial growth, international ambition, and increasing recognition of video games as a significant economic sector. Yet paradoxically, and despite the establishment of major studios as flagship companies for the industry, the institutional framework remained underdeveloped, leaving the industry vulnerable to the shocks that would come at the turn of the millennium. At the national level, the French video game market achieved significant scale during this period. The local market for video games grew rapidly during this period, driven by increased console penetration, the emergence of PC gaming as a major segment, and growing consumer acceptance of video games as mainstream entertainment. Consumer spending on video games increased substantially, creating commercial opportunities that attracted both domestic entrepreneurs and international investment.

The French development sector grew correspondingly, with the number of active studios increasing through the decade. France had become one of Europe's leading centres of video game development by 1999, with several studios of varying sizes active across the country. The industry's geographical distribution was notably decentralised compared to other creative sectors: while Paris hosted numerous studios, some indie studios began developing in Lyon, Bordeaux, Montpellier, and other regional centres.

By the end of the decade, the French video game industry had achieved significant scale and international visibility. The concentration of development activity in regional clusters created economies of agglomeration that attracted talent, investment, and institutional support.

A distinctive characteristic of the French video game industry was its geographic distribution. Unlike many European countries, where creative industries are concentrated heavily in capital cities, France saw the development of major video games companies in multiple regional centres outside of Paris and IDF. By 2000, the industry landscape included:

- **Paris/Île-de-France:** The capital region hosted the largest concentration of publishers and some development studios, benefiting from proximity to media industries, finance, and international connections.
- **Lyon/Rhône-Alpes:** Dominated by Infogrames, which by 1999 had become the second-largest video game publisher globally, Lyon represented approximately 30% of French video game development.
- **Bordeaux/Aquitaine:** Home to Kalisto Entertainment, Bordeaux emerged as a significant secondary centre.
- **Montpellier:** Ubisoft's decision to establish major development operations in Montpellier contributed to the emergence of another regional cluster.
- **Other centres:** Smaller concentrations existed in Lille, Marseille, Nantes, and other cities.

On the positive side, French studios had developed strong capabilities in specific genres – adventure games, racing games, action-adventure – and had established valuable relationships with major console manufacturers and publishers. The “French Touch” identity provided creative differentiation in international markets, and several French-developed titles achieved both critical acclaim and commercial success.

Yet, this period saw the accentuation of many structural weaknesses and financial issues, which became painfully apparent during the subsequent crisis. Dependence on hit-driven economics meant that studios' fortunes could swing dramatically based on the performance of individual titles. Limited access to capital – venture capital, institutional investment, or long-term bank financing – forced studios to rely on project-by-project publisher financing that left them vulnerable to shifts in publisher priorities. The challenges of competing with well-capitalised American and Japanese competitors for market position created constant pressure.

Thus, the competitive positioning of French studios reflected both strengths and vulnerabilities. Their expansion occurred without corresponding development of collective organisation or public policy support. The industry remained characterised by isolation rather than organised collaboration. There were still no effective trade associations representing the developers and studio interests. The SELL (“*Syndicat des Éditeurs de Logiciels de Loisirs*” - Leisure Software Publishers Association), founded in 1995, represented publishers – a different constituency with most often divergent interests from studios and developers. Despite the growing interest in the spectacular growth and revenues generated by the industry, the French public authorities had not yet developed dedicated policies for the video game sector, which remained invisible in cultural policy frameworks designed for cinema, music, and other traditional cultural industries.

The financial structures that sustained industry expansion during this period accentuated these vulnerabilities. The expansion of the major established studios had been achieved through individual entrepreneurial effort rather than collective capacity-building. These studios pursued capital-intensive growth strategies financed through public equity markets. The growing costs of video game development, driven by technological advancement and rising consumer expectations, required access to capital that exceeded the individual internal capacity of most studios. Consequently, studios became increasingly dependent on publisher advances, venture capital investment, and – for a few fortunate companies – public equity markets. The dot-com era valuations of the late 1990s enabled these strategies and created favourable conditions for technology-related IPOs. Video game companies were swept up in the enthusiasm. The public listings raised significant capital but also created shareholder expectations for continued growth that would prove difficult to sustain when market conditions deteriorated. The debt burdens accumulated during expansion would become fatal when revenue projections failed to materialise.

6.4 The Systemic crisis of 2001–2003

6.4.1 The bursting of the Internet bubble and its industry-wide impact

The crisis that struck the French video game industry in 2001–2003 must be understood as a systemic event affecting the entire national video game industry rather than merely the isolated problems of individual companies or specific regions. The bursting of the Internet bubble in March 2000 triggered a cascade of consequences that exposed the structural vulnerabilities of the French video game sector, detailed above, and notably the high dependence on publishers, the limited capital reserves, the absence of collective bargaining capacity, and the overreliance on hit-driven economics.

The NASDAQ crash and subsequent technology sector downturn affected the French video game industry through multiple interconnected channels. Access to equity financing, which had fuelled the expansion of the late 1990s, contracted sharply as investors fled technology stocks. Companies that had recently completed IPOs or that depended on continued access to capital markets found themselves unable to raise funds. The decline in stock prices triggered covenant concerns with creditors, margin calls for founders who had pledged shares as collateral, and liquidity crises that exposed underlying financial weaknesses. Beyond the direct financial impacts, the crisis transformed the broader environment in which French studios operated. Publisher caution increased dramatically as major international publishers – themselves struggling with the technology downturn – became reluctant to commit to new development contracts or advance milestone payments on existing projects. Consumer spending on discretionary entertainment products softened during the economic downturn. The advertising revenues that had supported some business models (particularly those oriented towards online or casual gaming) evaporated.

The scale of industry destruction during this period was devastating, with employment falling correspondingly from an estimated 10,000 jobs to around 4,800. France's global ranking in video game production fell from fifth to seventh. On average, one out of every two studios active in 2001

would close its doors during the crisis and its aftermath. A “brain drain” occurred as talent migrated to countries with more stable industries.

6.4.2 Structural and institutional dimensions of the crisis

The crisis revealed and exacerbated the structural vulnerabilities that had characterised the French video game industry throughout its development. The relationship between French development studios, be they big studios or small indies, and international publishers is one of the most significant structural problems. French studios had developed capabilities in game development but remained largely dependent on publishers – predominantly American, Japanese, and British – for financing, distribution, and market access. This dependency created an asymmetric power relationship in which publishers could impose terms that concentrated risk on studios while retaining the most valuable IPs. Studios typically operate on a “work-for-hire” basis, developing games based on publisher-owned franchises or ceding IP rights in exchange for development financing. When the crisis struck, many publishers cancelled ongoing projects, delayed milestone payments, or simply demanded renegotiation of terms, leaving studios with limited recourse.

The industry’s cooperative landscape was severely underdeveloped during the crisis. The absence of effective mechanisms for studios to coordinate their responses, share information about changing market conditions, or present a unified voice to publishers, investors, or policymakers was detrimental to the French video game industry. Each studio faced the crisis in isolation, negotiating individual survival strategies without the benefit of collective resources or coordinated action. This atomisation weakened the bargaining position of all studios and prevented the emergence of industry-wide solutions to shared problems.

The absence of dedicated public policy support for video games compounded the difficulties. While France had well-developed systems of cultural support for cinema, publishing, and other traditional cultural industries, video games remained outside these frameworks. There was no equivalent of the CNC’s automatic support mechanisms for cinema production, no tax incentives specifically designed for video game development, and no public funding programmes targeting the sector’s specific needs. When studios encountered difficulties, they could not access the safety nets available to other cultural industries.

At the technological level, the console transition cycle added to the uncertainties and challenges weighing on the industry. The transition to new console generations – from the PlayStation/N64/Saturn era to PlayStation 2/Xbox/GameCube – required massive investment in new technical capabilities precisely when financing was least available. The short life cycles of gaming platforms meant that studios could not simply wait out the crisis while maintaining their existing product portfolios; they needed to invest in next-generation development or become obsolete. These transitions created both opportunities and risks, as studios that successfully navigated technological change could establish strong market positions, while those that stumbled could find themselves unable to recover.

6.4.3 The wave of failures and their geographic distribution

The crisis manifested through a wave of studio failures, restructurings and significant downsizing that affected companies across France, regardless of their regional location or apparent market position. While certain high-profile failures attracted particular attention, the crisis was industry-wide rather than concentrated in companies or regions.

Historical analysis indicates that the French video game industry experienced approximately 80% decline in the number of active studios between 2003 and 2013. Lyon saw the progressive decline of Infogrames, which accumulated €580 million in debt by 2002 and would ultimately relocate to Paris (2009) before entering bankruptcy (2013). Bordeaux experienced the immediate collapse of Kalisto, which entered liquidation in January 2002, eliminating 250-300 jobs. Cryo Interactive in Paris declared bankruptcy in July 2002 with approximately €40 million in debt and the loss of more than 250 jobs. Several smaller Parisian studios also failed during this period. No Cliché, founded by former Sega employees to develop innovative games, closed its doors. Lankhor, developer of classic adventure games, ceased its operations. Montpellier, home to Ubisoft's French studios, weathered the crisis better than most but was not immune to industry-wide pressures. These failures represented not merely the loss of individual companies but the potential destruction of accumulated expertise, established relationships, and institutional memory. The diversity of affected locations underscored that the crisis stemmed from structural factors affecting the entire industry rather than specific local conditions.

For the studios that survived the initial crisis or that were founded directly in its aftermath, the following years brought continued difficulties. Funding remained constrained, publisher relationships remained asymmetric, and market conditions remained challenging. Many studios that avoided outright closure were forced into severe restructuring, layoffs, and strategic reorientation. The human toll – in terms of jobs lost, careers disrupted, and expertise dispersed – extended far beyond the headline-grabbing failures.

6.4.4 The crisis as catalyst for collective action

Paradoxically, the very severity of the crisis created conditions for a fundamental transformation of the French video game industry organisation. The failures and near-failures of 2001–2003 showed that the atomised, unorganised structure of the French industry was unsustainable and that individual studios, regardless of their size or talent, could not survive industry-wide shocks without collective resources and coordinated action.

Thus, the crisis of 2001–2003 catalysed several collective efforts to build the institutional infrastructure that had been lacking throughout the industry's development. The creation of APOM in 2001 marked the beginning of organised collective action in the French video game industry. This institutionalisation was also carried out at the local level of several regions. Locally, in the major territories, like IDF, Lyon and Bordeaux, where many new studios sprouted following the collapse of large studios, several professional associations with regional focalisation were created.

The crisis also prompted the first tentative steps towards inter-regional coordination. Actors in Lyon, Bordeaux, and Paris began to recognise their shared challenges and the potential benefits of a coordinated response. While formal inter-cluster mechanisms would not emerge until later, the crisis period established relationships and shared understandings that would prove foundational for subsequent collaboration.

The collective memory of the 2001–2003 crisis would remain a powerful motivator for industry organisation in subsequent years. The experience of facing systemic challenges without adequate collective resources became a reference point for arguments in favour of stronger industry associations, more robust public policy support, and more extensive inter-cluster collaboration.

6.4.5 The national policy for cluster's promotion

The examination of the contextual factors shaping the two studied clusters reveals several elements operating at the national level that, while not directly targeting the video game industry, significantly influenced its territorial organisation. Understanding the evolution of French cluster policies is essential to analysing the emergence and dynamics of the Lyon and Bordeaux video game ecosystems, as these regional clusters did not develop in an institutional vacuum. Rather, they evolved in constant interaction with – and sometimes in tension with – a shifting national policy landscape that shaped the resources available to them, the organisational models they could adopt, and the legitimacy they could claim vis-à-vis public authorities.

The French state's approach to territorial economic development during the late 1990s and 2000s influenced video game clusters in at least three significant ways. First, at the cognitive and discursive level, successive cluster policies introduced and popularised the very concept of "cluster" within the vocabulary of both industry professionals and policymakers, making territorial agglomeration and interfirm cooperation a legitimate and recognisable strategic option. Second, at the organisational level, the policy frameworks – from SPLs to "*Pôles de compétitivité*" (Competitiveness Hubs) to "*Grappes d'entreprises*" (Clusters of firms) – provided templates for governance structures, membership models, and activity portfolios that regional actors could adopt. Third, at the material level, these policies channelled financial resources, institutional support, and symbolic recognition towards clustered forms of organisation, creating incentives for young industries, such as the video games industry, to engage with territorial networks even when the policy instruments had been designed for different sectoral logics.

From the late 1990s onwards, the French state's approach to territorial economic development underwent a significant transformation, progressively constructing a layered policy architecture for cluster support. In 1997–1998, the DATAR ("*Délégation interministérielle à l'aménagement du territoire et à l'attractivité régionale*" - Interministerial Delegation for Regional Planning and Attractiveness) launched the "SPL" programme, directly inspired by Italian industrial district scholarship and Marshallian agglomeration economics (Marshall, 1920). The intellectual foundations of this policy drew heavily on the work of Becattini, Brusco, and other analysts of the "Third Italy" who had demonstrated how networks of specialised SMEs in regions such as Emilia-

Romagna achieved collective efficiency through interfirm cooperation, shared labour markets, and localised knowledge spillovers. French policymakers saw in these models a potential antidote to the vulnerabilities of territories dominated by large firms or traditional industries facing global competition.

Through two national calls for projects in 1998 and 1999, approximately 160 SPLs were labelled across the country, receiving modest financial support from the FNADT (*“Fonds National d’Aménagement et de Développement du Territoire”* - National Fund for Regional Planning and Development). The programme primarily targeted traditional manufacturing sectors – textiles, metalworking, plastics, agri-food – where SME networks already exhibited spatial concentration, sectoral specialisation, and some degree of interfirm cooperation. Emblematic cases included the Cosmetic Valley in Eure-et-Loir, the plastics industry in Oyonnax (Ain), and the cutlery cluster in Thiers (Puy-de-Dôme). The SPL policy philosophy was fundamentally conservative in the sense that it aimed to formalise, reinforce, and provide visibility to existing local dynamics rather than create new clusters *ex nihilo*. Public intervention was conceived as a catalyst for latent cooperative potential rather than as a driver of structural transformation.

The benefits of the SPL framework for the video game industry’s relationship proved to be ambiguous. On the one hand, the sector’s characteristics – small creative firms, project-based collaboration, knowledge-intensive production – diverged significantly from the traditional manufacturing districts that had inspired the policy. On the other hand, the SPL label offered access to public resources and institutional legitimacy that could prove valuable for an emerging industry still struggling for recognition. The creation of Capital Games in Paris in April 2004 illustrates this dynamic. Established as “SPL Capital Games” with support from the DATAR, the Île-de-France Regional Council, and the City of Paris, this association represented one of the first attempts to apply the SPL framework to the video game sector. By adopting the SPL label, the founders of Capital Games – industry professionals seeking to federate the fragmented Parisian video games development ecosystem – signalled their willingness to engage with existing policy instruments, even when these had been designed for very different industrial realities. This institutional bricolage, combining formal policy labels with sector-specific objectives, was replicated in many other regions in France.

However, comprehensive evaluations of the SPL programme conducted in 2008 revealed mixed results across all sectors. While the programme successfully introduced many firms to networking logics and partnership practices, enterprise mobilisation remained modest overall. The evaluators noted that the quality of cluster animation proved critical yet highly uneven across territories: SPLs with professional, well-resourced governance structures outperformed those relying on voluntary coordination or weak institutional support. The policy also suffered from limited financial means and a lack of strategic selectivity, spreading resources thinly across many heterogeneous initiatives. By the mid-2000s, the SPL framework was increasingly perceived as insufficient to address the competitive challenges facing the French economy in a globalising world.

A major policy shift occurred in 2004–2005 with the launch of the *“Pôles de compétitivité”* programme, which represented both a rupture and a continuity with previous approaches. The

intellectual and political context had evolved significantly. Influential reports – notably Christian Blanc's *“Pour un écosystème de la croissance”* (2004) and the DATAR's *“France, an industrial power”* (2004) – diagnosed a French innovation deficit and advocated for a more ambitious, selective, and innovation-oriented cluster policy inspired by international benchmarks such as Silicon Valley, the Cambridge cluster, or Bavarian high-tech networks. Concerns about deindustrialisation, relocation of production to low-cost countries, and France's mediocre performance in R&D investment provided the political impetus for action.

The government announced this “new industrial policy” at the inter-ministerial committee, CIADT, (*“Comité Interministériel d'Aménagement et de Développement du Territoire”* - Interministerial Committee for Regional Planning and Development) in 2004, positioning it as a strategic response to globalisation. Following a competitive call for projects that generated considerable territorial mobilisation – with over 100 candidatures submitted – 67 poles were labelled in July 2005, classified into three categories: worldwide poles (7), poles with worldwide vocation (10), and national or regional poles (50). The initial budget allocated was substantial: 1.5 billion euros for the 2005–2008 period, including direct funding for collaborative R&D projects, tax exemptions for firms located within designated zones, and support for governance structures. Imaginove, in Lyon, was among the poles that were selected and labelled.

Unlike SPLs, which focused on production cost reduction through resource mutualisation and collective services, the *“Pôles de compétitivité”* explicitly targeted R&D collaboration and technological innovation as their primary objectives. The policy targeted structured partnerships between large firms (often serving as anchor tenants), innovative SMEs, public research laboratories, and higher education institutions. Projects funded through the programme had to demonstrate significant innovative content, collaborative governance, and potential for commercial application. The policy also introduced demanding criteria, including international visibility and strategic positioning on high-growth global markets – requirements that implicitly favoured high-tech sectors with strong scientific foundations (biotechnology, nanotechnology, aerospace, digital technologies) and major metropolitan areas with dense research infrastructure.

This institutional evolution created both opportunities and tensions for the video game industry. The sector's core characteristics – dominance of creative SMEs and micro-enterprises, project-based organisation with volatile employment, rapid technological cycles, integration of artistic and technical competencies, and business models heavily dependent on hit-driven markets – aligned imperfectly with policy frameworks designed for different economic logics. The SPL model, with its emphasis on traditional manufacturing districts and stable interfirm production networks, offered limited relevance to an industry characterised by discontinuous project collaborations and fluid labour markets. The *“Pôles de compétitivité”* framework, while more attuned to innovation dynamics, implicitly favoured science-push models of technological development – where academic research generates knowledge subsequently transferred to industry – rather than the demand-pull, user-driven innovation typical of creative industries.

This misalignment placed regional video game clusters in an ambiguous position vis-à-vis the national policy instruments. They could attempt to integrate existing poles with a broader

technological scope (such as digital or multimedia poles), but risked marginality within governance structures dominated by other sectors. Alternatively, they could develop autonomous cluster organisations operating largely outside the labelled pole system but forfeiting access to associated resources and legitimacy. The strategic choices made by cluster entrepreneurs in Lyon and Bordeaux – and the institutional bricolage they deployed to navigate this policy landscape – significantly shaped their respective developmental trajectories, as the following sections will demonstrate.

6.5 Inter-clusters collaboration & national governance

6.5.1 The establishment of a collective union

The 2001–2003 crisis marked the beginning of a profound transformation at the institutional level. Paradoxically, the very moment when the industry was experiencing a major crisis also witnessed the first serious attempts at collective organisation – both at the national level, through the creation of professional associations, and at the regional level, through early reflections on local coordination that would eventually give rise to formal cluster structures. These two dynamics were rather simultaneous and mutually reinforcing: the same actors who were building bridges across regional boundaries to advocate for national policy support were also beginning to recognise the value of territorial proximity and local ecosystems. The founding of APOM in 2001 thus represented not only the emergence of a national voice for the industry, but also the starting point of a broader shift towards collaborative logics that would subsequently materialise in regional cluster initiatives in Lyon, Bordeaux, and Paris. The institutional innovations that would reshape the French video game industry in subsequent years – the transformation of APOM into SNJV (2008), the achievement of the CIJV tax credit (2008), the creation of regional cluster associations, the development of training labelling programmes – all have their origins in the collective awakening catalysed by the 2001–2003 crisis.

APOM was founded precisely as the crisis was beginning to unfold, by industry figures who recognised that a collective voice was essential for survival. The founding group included Nicolas Gaume of Kalisto, Stéphane Baudet of Eden Studios, Alain Le Diberder (former cabinet member and industry author), Romain Poirot-Lellig, and Antoine Villette of Darkworks, a studio located in Paris. This founding group represented a deliberate effort to transcend regional boundaries and create a national platform for industry representation. APOM was established specifically for game developers, complementing the existing SELL, which represented publishers' interests. This organisational distinction recognised that developers and publishers, while interdependent, had distinctive needs and perspectives that required separate representation. APOM's creation aimed to enable developers to articulate their collective interests, coordinate advocacy efforts, and engage with public authorities from a position of organised strength rather than individual weakness.

In November 2002, Prime Minister Jean-Pierre Raffarin visited the Darkworks studio and formally invited game developers to submit policy proposals, promising to respond in Spring 2003. The visit had concrete policy consequences. It contributed to the decision to create ENJMIN ("*École Nationale du Jeu et des Médias Interactifs Numériques*" – National School of Gaming and Interactive Digital

Media) in Angoulême in 2003, establishing the first state-recognised educational institution specifically dedicated to video game development. This governmental engagement – unprecedented for the video game industry – reflected both the severity of the crisis and the effectiveness of APOM’s advocacy in placing industry concerns on the political agenda. Confronted by the bankruptcies of Cryo, Kalisto, Arxel Tribe, and others, APOM had to propose both short-term crisis measures and long-term growth-oriented policies.

The organisation’s early activities focused on two priorities: advocating for public policy support and establishing the French video game industry’s legitimacy as a cultural and economic sector. Between 2001 and 2008, APOM engaged in sustained lobbying efforts that would ultimately prove transformative. The organisation advocated for the creation of the FAEM (*“Fonds d’Aide à l’Édition Multimédia”* – Multimedia Publishing Assistance Fund) pushed for the recognition of video games as a cultural product eligible for state support and worked to establish educational standards for the emerging video game training programmes.

The transformation of APOM into SNJV in July 2008 marked the maturation of the national governance structures. The change from an association to a professional union reflected the industry’s growing sophistication and its need for formal representation in labour negotiations, tax policy discussions, and regulatory frameworks. Nicolas Gaume served as president of SNJV from 2009 to 2014. SNJV’s organisational structure deliberately incorporated representatives from regional clusters, creating a federal model that balanced national coordination with local autonomy. The organisation’s board included representatives from Lyon Game/Imaginove, Bordeaux Games, Capital Games (Paris), and other regional associations. This structure ensured that national policy positions reflected the diverse needs and perspectives of clusters operating in different territorial contexts.

6.5.2 The federal coordination model and multi-scalar governance

The governance structure established through SNJV created mechanisms for inter-cluster collaboration that would prove important for the industry’s development. Monthly board meetings, which alternated between Paris and regional hubs, brought together representatives from regional clusters, creating opportunities for knowledge exchange, coordination of advocacy efforts, and development of shared services. This decentralised governance approach recognised that while certain issues – like tax policy and international representation – required national coordination, others – like talent development and local business support – were best addressed at the regional level. This federal model balanced the benefits of local autonomy with the advantages of national coordination. The practical manifestation of this coordination included joint international missions, shared policy advocacy, pooled communication resources, and collaborative training initiatives. The Bureau Export du Jeu Vidéo, created to support French studios’ international market access, represented one tangible outcome of inter-cluster collaboration.

The French video game industry developed a sophisticated multi-scalar governance system that articulated local, regional and national levels of organisation. At the local level, clusters like LyonGame/Imaginove/Game Only and Bordeaux Games/SO Games provided networking, support

services, and local advocacy. At the regional level, relationships with territorial authorities (Regions, Metropoles) enabled access to economic development resources. At the national level, SNJV provided policy advocacy, industry representation, and coordination of collective action. At the European level, membership in EGDF (European Game Developers Federation) enabled participation in continental policy discussions.

This multi-scalar articulation proved essential for navigating the complex institutional landscape of French public policy. Different levels of government have been controlling different resources and policy levers relevant to the video game industry. Regional authorities could provide direct financial support, business development services, and infrastructure investments. National authorities have been controlling tax policy, cultural support programmes, and education policy. European authorities influenced competition policy, digital market regulation, and cross-border funding programmes.

The effectiveness of this multi-scalar system depended on having organisations at each level that could represent industry interests while understanding the specific institutional logics and decision-making processes of their counterparts in government. The development of these representative capacities across multiple scales represents a significant organisational achievement for an industry that had lacked collective voice only a decade earlier.

6.5.3 Major actions

SNJV's most significant achievement during this period was the successful advocacy for the CIJV, a tax credit for video game production that was finally implemented in 2008. This policy victory represented the culmination of years of lobbying and demonstrated the effectiveness of organised industry representation. The CIJV would become a crucial tool for supporting French video game production, helping studios compete with international rivals who benefited from similar incentives in countries like Canada and the United Kingdom.

The CIJV represented a fundamental shift in how the French state related to the video game industry. By recognising video games as eligible for cultural production tax credits, the government acknowledged the industry's legitimacy as a creative sector comparable to film, television, and other traditional cultural industries. This recognition had both practical financial benefits and symbolic importance in establishing the industry's position within French cultural policy.

The implementation of the CIJV also created new institutional relationships between the video game industry and public authorities. The CNC became the administrative home for video game support programmes, integrating the industry into established structures for cultural production support. This institutional embedding would prove valuable for accessing additional public support in subsequent years.

Another significant area of inter-cluster collaboration was the development of educational standards and training programme labelling. The SNJV recognised early that the quality of training programmes directly affected the industry's access to skilled talent and that establishing quality standards would benefit all clusters by ensuring a reliable supply of qualified graduates.

The training labelling programme, launched in 2010, created a framework for evaluating and certifying video game education programmes across France. This initiative served multiple purposes: it provided guidance to prospective students about programme quality, incentivised schools to maintain high standards, and created a basis for dialogue between industry and educational institutions about evolving skill requirements.

The creation of ENJMIN in Angoulême in 2003 represented state recognition of video game development as a legitimate profession requiring specialised training. The decision to locate the school in Angoulême rather than Paris reflected deliberate regional development considerations. The choice positioned ENJMIN within the broader Nouvelle-Aquitaine ecosystem, creating institutional links that would prove valuable for the Bordeaux cluster’s subsequent development.

The school’s curriculum, developed in consultation with industry practitioners including figures from both Lyon and Bordeaux clusters, established a comprehensive approach to video game education covering programming, game design, art direction, sound design, and project management. The five-year programme (later restructured as Master-level training) aimed to produce graduates capable of assuming leadership roles within studios, addressing the industry’s persistent need for experienced talent. Annual cohorts of approximately 35 students created a steady pipeline of highly qualified professionals who would subsequently staff studios across France.

ENJMIN’s institutional positioning within the broader educational landscape also merited attention. As a public institution under the supervision of the Ministry of Culture and the Ministry of Higher Education, the school represented a formal acknowledgement of video games as a cultural production worthy of state investment. This institutional embedding provided legitimacy that benefited the entire industry, supporting arguments for additional public support mechanisms, including the CIJV tax credit.

Apart from ENJMIN, Ecole Emile Cohl, founded in Lyon in 1984 by Philippe Rivière, represents an early example of artistic training that would prove relevant for video game development. Originally focused on illustration, animation, and graphic design, the school progressively adapted its curriculum to address the emerging digital content industries. The establishment of programmes in digital creation and game art provided Lyon studios with access to artistically trained graduates who could contribute to the visual dimensions of game development. The school’s continued presence in the Lyon ecosystem represents over four decades of contribution to the region’s creative industries infrastructure.

6.6 The emergence of the Lyon Cluster

6.6.1 Bruno Bonnell: The visionary entrepreneur

6.6.1.1 Origins and background

Bruno Bonnell, born in 1958 in Lyon, emerged as one of the most influential figures in the French video game industry’s formative years. His entrepreneurial journey began in 1983 when, together with Christophe Sapet, he founded Infogrames in Villeurbanne, a city adjacent to Lyon. The company’s origins were remarkably modest – initial financing came from the revenues of a book

introducing readers to computer programming, and the founders operated from a small apartment with minimal resources.

Bonnell's background combined technical curiosity with commercial instinct. Before founding Infogrames, he had developed expertise in the emerging personal computer market, understanding both the technology's potential and the consumer demand for accessible software. His co-founder, Christophe Sapet, brought complementary skills in programming and technical development. Together, they formed a partnership that would shape the French video game industry for two decades.

What distinguished Bonnell from other entrepreneurs of the period was his ability to articulate a cultural vision for video games. At a time when software was often dismissed as a trivial pursuit, Bonnell strived to position video games as a legitimate creative medium deserving recognition alongside traditional arts. This cultural ambition would prove important for securing institutional support and establishing the industry's legitimacy in French public discourse.

6.6.1.2 Entrepreneurial vision and expansion strategy

The founding vision of Infogrames articulated three principles that would guide the company's development: broadening the public for home computing through family-friendly products, discovering new uses for home computers, and establishing software as a "tenth art" alongside the nine classical arts. This vision positioned Infogrames not merely as a commercial enterprise but as a cultural project.

From the outset, Bonnell envisioned Infogrames as a global player capable of competing with American and Japanese giants. This ambition drove the aggressive expansion strategy of the 1990s, with its wave of international acquisitions. It also contributed to the overreach that would eventually lead to the company's difficulties.

The acquisition strategy was predicated on achieving economies of scale in an industry characterised by rising development costs and hit-driven economics. By controlling a large portfolio of franchises and development studios, Infogrames aimed to diversify risk while achieving efficiencies in distribution, marketing, and corporate functions. The strategy also reflected Bonnell's belief that consolidation was inevitable in the video game industry and that it was better to be a consolidator than to be consolidated. The acquisition strategy created a global presence and portfolio of franchises. But it also created a complex organisation that proved difficult to manage, accumulated substantial debt, and established shareholder expectations for continued growth that would prove impossible to sustain.

Bonnell's charisma and communication skills made him an effective spokesperson for both Infogrames and the broader French video game industry. He cultivated relationships with media, investors, and public officials, building visibility for an industry that lacked institutional representation. His ability to articulate a compelling narrative about video games' potential attracted talent, capital, and attention to Lyon.

Bonnell was known for his hands-on involvement in creative decisions, maintaining engagement with game development even as the company grew. He championed projects that reflected his vision of games as artistic expression, supporting titles like *Alone in the Dark* that pushed creative and technical boundaries.

6.6.1.3 Building the Lyon ecosystem

Bonnell's influence extended beyond Infogrames to shape the entire Lyon video game ecosystem during the company's growth years. As Infogrames expanded, it attracted talent to Lyon from across France and internationally. The company's success created a concentration of video game expertise that made Lyon attractive for related businesses – service providers, specialised suppliers, and eventually educational institutions oriented towards video game careers.

The physical manifestation of Bonnell's vision in Lyon was the construction of Infogrames' iconic headquarters – four modern buildings designed to resemble ships or “*péniches*”, located on the banks of the Saône River in the Vaise district. Completed in 2000, these buildings became architectural landmarks and symbols of Lyon's emergence as a centre of the video game industry. They represented Bonnell's ambition to create not just a successful company but a permanent institution that would anchor the industry in Lyon.

Bonnell's role in Lyon extended to civic and cultural engagement. He became a prominent figure in the city's business community, advocating for the digital economy and creative industries. He participated in regional economic development initiatives, positioning Lyon as a technology hub. His visibility helped establish video games as a legitimate industry worthy of public attention and institutional support.

The ecosystem that developed around Infogrames during Bonnell's leadership created the conditions for subsequent cluster development. Suppliers, service providers, and partner companies established operations in Lyon to serve Infogrames. Educational institutions developed programmes to meet the company's talent needs. When the crisis came, this ecosystem infrastructure would enable the diaspora studios to emerge and survive.

6.6.2 Infogrames: from regional success to global player

6.6.2.1 Early commercial success

Infogrames' first commercial success came quickly after its founding. *Le Cube*, released for the Christmas 1983 season, sold 60,000 copies – a remarkable achievement for the nascent French software market. This early success validated the founders' belief that there was substantial consumer demand for entertainment software and provided capital for continued development.

The subsequent years saw steady growth as Infogrames developed a portfolio of successful titles. *Autoroute* and *Mandragore* (1984) demonstrated the company's ability to develop both accessible family entertainment and more sophisticated games for dedicated players. Each success reinforced

the company's reputation and attracted additional resources – talent, capital, and publishing partnerships.

Alone in the Dark (1992) would later be recognised as a pioneering work in the survival horror genre and one of the first games to feature three-dimensional graphics rendered in real-time. This title established Infogrames' reputation for technical innovation and creative ambition, positioning the company as a leader in game development rather than merely a regional publisher.

6.6.2.2 The acquisition strategy

Beginning in the mid-1990s, Infogrames embarked on an aggressive international expansion strategy built around acquisitions. This strategy reflected Bonnell's vision of creating a global video game company capable of competing with American and Japanese giants. The acquisition approach was predicated on achieving economies of scale in an industry characterised by rising development costs and hit-driven economics.

The purchase of Ocean Software in 1996 provided access to the British market and established franchises. Subsequent acquisitions of GT Interactive, Hasbro Interactive, and Shiny Interactive transformed Infogrames from a European publisher into a global player. By 1999, following the acquisition of GT Interactive, Infogrames had become the second-largest video game publisher in the world, with a global workforce exceeding 2,400 employees.

The Hasbro Interactive acquisition brought the Atari brand into Infogrames' portfolio – a name that carried enormous recognition value in video game history. This acquisition seemed to cement Infogrames' status as a major global player, providing access to classic intellectual properties and established distribution channels. Yet the acquisition also added to the company's debt burden and organisational complexity.

6.6.2.3 Strategic decisions and missed opportunities

The Infogrames era was marked by several strategic decisions that would have significant long-term consequences – including opportunities not taken. Documents from this period reveal that Infogrames considered but ultimately declined to acquire the license for *Grand Theft Auto* from DMA Design/Rockstar before it became a global phenomenon. The company also explored but did not complete an acquisition by Electronic Arts.

These missed opportunities reflected the challenges of strategic decision-making in a rapidly evolving industry. The *Grand Theft Auto* franchise, which seemed of uncertain commercial potential when Infogrames considered it, would become one of the best-selling entertainment properties of all time. The EA acquisition might have provided financial stability that could have helped Infogrames weather the coming crisis.

The strategic decisions that Infogrames made during this period established both the company's global presence and its vulnerabilities. The acquisition strategy created a portfolio of franchises and international operations. But it also created a complex organisation that proved difficult to manage,

accumulated substantial debt, and established shareholder expectations for continued growth that would prove impossible to sustain.

6.6.2.4 Crisis and decline

By 2002, Infogrames had accumulated debts of €580 million – a burden that would constrain the company's operations for years to come. This debt resulted from the aggressive acquisition strategy of the late 1990s, which had been financed largely through borrowing and equity issuance. When market conditions deteriorated and revenues failed to meet projections, the debt burden became unsustainable.

The crisis at Infogrames was exacerbated by several underperforming major releases. Development costs for AAA (Triple A) titles had escalated dramatically, with projects like *Alone in the Dark 5* costing €20 million to develop. When such titles failed to achieve expected sales, the financial impact was severe. The hit-driven economics of the video game industry meant that success required not just good games but blockbuster games.

The company's global structure, which had seemed a source of strength during the expansion era, became a liability during the crisis. The costs of maintaining international operations exceeded the revenues they generated. Coordination across dispersed studios proved difficult. The synergies anticipated from acquisitions failed to materialise, while integration costs continued to mount.

Beginning in 2001, Infogrames entered a period of successive restructurings, asset sales, and strategic pivots. Development studios were closed or sold. Staff were laid off in successive waves – thousands of jobs eliminated across the company's global operations. The ambitious expansion of the late 1990s gave way to a desperate struggle for survival that would extend over more than a decade.

Financial data from this period illustrates the severity of the decline. In 2008, Infogrames reported revenues of €305 million but losses of €103 million. The company's market capitalisation collapsed from its peak during the dot-com era. Successive rounds of financing diluted existing shareholders while failing to resolve the underlying structural problems.

Bruno Bonnell's departure in 2007 marked the end of the founding era. The company subsequently transformed itself into Atari (2009), adopting the brand of its acquired subsidiary to leverage its greater name recognition. The headquarters relocated from Lyon to Paris (2009), severing the company's connection to the city where it had been founded. The eventual bankruptcy in 2013 marked the final chapter of a decline that had begun during the 2001–2003 crisis.

6.6.3 Bonnell's trajectory: from industry to politics

Bruno Bonnell's departure from Infogrames in 2007 came after years of restructuring and decline. Bonnell witnessed the successive restructurings, the asset sales, the transformation into Atari, and the relocation of headquarters from Lyon to Paris. The company he had built was gradually

dismantled and transformed, a process that extended over years rather than occurring in a single traumatic moment.

Bonnell's post-Infogrames trajectory took him into a domain quite different from video games: politics. In 2017, he was elected to the French National Assembly as a deputy for the Rhône, representing the "La République en Marche" party.

The political career represented a continuation of Bonnell's engagement with public affairs. Throughout his time at Infogrames, he had advocated for the video game industry in public forums, built relationships with government officials, and participated in regional economic development initiatives.

As a deputy, Bonnell engaged with technology and innovation policy, bringing his industry experience to legislative debates. He served on committees related to economic affairs and digital transformation, areas where his background provided relevant expertise. His presence in the National Assembly gave the technology sector a voice with direct industry experience, even if video games were no longer his primary focus.

Despite his departure from Infogrames and transition to politics, Bonnell maintained connections to Lyon's technology ecosystem. His political role allowed him to advocate for regional interests in national forums. His continued visibility as a public figure associated with Lyon's digital economy reinforced the city's identity as a technology centre.

Bonnell's legacy in Lyon extended beyond his direct activities. The ecosystem he had helped create during the Infogrames years continued to evolve, generating the diaspora studios that would form the foundation of the contemporary cluster. The institutional attention he had attracted to video games in Lyon persisted, even as new leaders emerged to organise collective action.

6.6.4 The immediate aftermath of the crisis

The Infogrames crisis had profound but complex effects on the Lyon video game ecosystem. In the immediate term, the successive layoffs and studio closures eliminated hundreds of jobs and created uncertainty about the region's future in the industry. The decline of the anchor company that had defined Lyon's identity as a video game centre raised questions about whether the cluster could survive. Yet the crisis also created conditions for renewal.

Apart from the talent, the spin-off waves and the accumulated knowledge, the physical infrastructure of the Infogrames era also remained. The iconic "*péniche*" buildings continued to house video game companies and related creative industries. The reputation that Lyon had established as a centre of video game development persisted, even as the company that had created that reputation declined. Educational institutions that had developed to serve Infogrames' talent needs continued to produce graduates who would staff the new generation of studios.

6.6.4.1 The dispersion of talent

The crisis at Infogrames dispersed the concentration of talent that had developed around the company. As layoffs proceeded in waves, experienced professionals found themselves seeking new opportunities. Some left the industry entirely. Some relocated to other regions or countries where video game employment was available. But many remained in Lyon, channelling their experience and expertise into new ventures.

This dispersion of talent created the conditions for a “creative diaspora” effect. The skills, relationships, and industry knowledge that had accumulated within Infogrames did not disappear with the company’s decline – they were redistributed across a new generation of entrepreneurial ventures. Former Infogrames employees founded studios, joined emerging companies, or provided consulting services to the growing ecosystem.

The creative diaspora from Infogrames would eventually generate an estimated 200 new studios in the Lyon region. This proliferation created a far more diverse ecosystem than the mono-enterprise model that had preceded the crisis. While no single company would achieve Infogrames’ scale, the collective output of the diaspora studios would eventually exceed what the anchor firm had accomplished.

6.6.4.2 The diaspora studios

Several studios that emerged from the Infogrames diaspora would achieve significant success, demonstrating that the talent developed during the anchor company era could generate value in new organisational contexts. Arkane Studios, founded in 1999 by Raphaël Colantonio (a former Infogrames employee), established itself as one of the world’s leading developers of immersive simulation games. The studio’s early productions, including *Arx Fatalis* (2002) and *Dark Messiah of Might and Magic* (2006), demonstrated technical ambition and design innovation that distinguished Arkane from more conventional studios. The subsequent *Dishonored* franchise (2012, 2016, 2017) achieved both critical acclaim and commercial success, establishing the studio’s reputation for rich, player-driven experiences. Arkane’s acquisition by ZeniMax Media (later acquired by Microsoft) provided resources for continued growth while the studio maintained its Lyon presence, employing over 150 people by the early 2020s.

Eden Games, spun out from Infogrames in 1998 (originally as Eden Studios), specialised in racing games that built on technical expertise developed within the parent company. The *V-Rally* franchise, initially created at Infogrames, continued to generate commercial success under Eden’s stewardship. *Test Drive Unlimited* (2006) represented a significant innovation in the racing genre, combining open-world exploration with multiplayer connectivity in ways that anticipated later industry trends. Eden’s trajectory illustrated both the potential and the vulnerability of diaspora studios – the company experienced closure in 2013 before being revived, demonstrating the persistence of creative identities even through corporate discontinuities.

Ivory Tower, founded in 2007 by former Eden Games developers continued Lyon’s specialisation in racing games while pioneering new approaches to the genre. *The Crew* franchise, developed in

partnership with Ubisoft, featured an open-world representation of the United States that could be traversed in real-time, representing technical achievements in world streaming and multiplayer connectivity. Ubisoft's acquisition of Ivory Tower integrated the studio into a major international publisher while maintaining its Lyon base, where the team grew to over 200 employees working on successive instalments of the franchise.

Étranges Libellules, founded in 1999, developed licensed games including adaptations of popular animated properties. The studio's work demonstrated how diaspora companies could find viable market positions through specialisation and partnership strategies different from the broad ambitions of the Infogrames era. The studio's eventual acquisition by Gameloft in 2010 represented one pathway for successful exit, validating the entrepreneurial investments of the founding team.

Doki Denki Studio and Pumpkin Effect Studio represented smaller-scale ventures that contributed to the ecosystem's diversity without achieving the scale of larger diaspora companies. These studios, along with numerous other ventures founded by former Infogrames employees, created the dense network of relationships and accumulated expertise that would characterise Lyon's mature cluster. The collective employment across diaspora studios – eventually exceeding what Infogrames had provided at its peak – demonstrated that distributed ecosystems could generate more total economic activity than concentrated mono-enterprise models.

These diaspora studios demonstrated different organisational models from the anchor firm. Rather than pursuing aggressive expansion and acquisition, most focused on developing distinctive creative capabilities and sustainable business models. The experience of Infogrames' overreach informed more cautious approaches to growth and financing.

6.6.4.3 The emergence of collective organisation

The crisis period also catalysed the first serious efforts at collective organisation in Lyon's video game sector. Lyon Infocité, an association created to support the broader digital economy, provided an initial institutional framework for collective action. Between May 1999 and May 2000, the association's membership grew from 40 to 105 members, reflecting the dynamism of the digital sector during the dot-com boom period.

Lyon Game emerged as a specialised initiative focused specifically on the video game sector. The creation of Game Connection in October 2001 represented a significant innovation in industry networking. This business-to-business event, featuring structured 30-minute meetings between developers and publishers, created a new model for facilitating industry relationships. The first Game Connection in December 2001 brought together 27 developers and 20 publishers, establishing a format that would grow substantially in subsequent years.

These organisational innovations demonstrated the capacity for creative problem-solving that the crisis had catalysed. Faced with the decline of the anchor firm, actors within the Lyon ecosystem developed new mechanisms for connecting French developers with international publishers – addressing a core challenge that had contributed to the industry's difficulties.

6.6.5 The Infogrames alumni network as organisational foundation

The emergence of Lyon Game as a collective organisation cannot be understood without examining the core group of entrepreneurs who initiated and sustained the effort. Lyon's restructuring was driven by a cohort of entrepreneurs who shared common origins in Infogrames. Several key figures have contributed to transforming informal networking into institutionalised cluster governance: *"Everyone knew each other through Infogrames. After a few meetings, we asked them if they would be interested in forming an association. Collective attendance at trade shows increased. With UbiFrance, we organised a collective presence at trade shows in Los Angeles and Cannes. This initiated collaboration between the organisations."* (historical player of the cluster)

6.6.5.1 The founding core

Hubert Chardot emerged as the central figure in the initial mobilisation. A former screenwriter at Infogrames, where he contributed to landmark titles including *Alone in the Dark*, Chardot has a very particular profile. His trajectory – Sciences Po studies abandoned for theatre, followed by a career shift into video game narrative design – gave him both creative legitimacy and intellectual credibility that proved valuable in articulating the industry's case to policymakers and the broader public.

Chardot co-founded GameSquad in the late 1990s with several Infogrames colleagues, positioning the studio as a development services provider. His decision to accept the presidency of Lyon Games reflected pragmatic calculation rather than personal ambition; as he later recalled, he explicitly stated his intention to serve only one year before passing leadership to others. This approach to governance – rotation of responsibility, reluctance to concentrate power – would become characteristic of Lyon's cluster institutions.

Chardot's vision of the video game industry was distinctly cultural and artistic. In interviews, he described a conviction that video games represented a genuinely new artistic medium rather than merely a commercial entertainment product. This perspective informed his advocacy for industry recognition and his insistence that French studios embodied a distinctive creative approach.

Laurent Paret complemented Chardot's creative profile with technical expertise and international experience. Also an Infogrames alumnus, Paret had participated in establishing Infogrames' American subsidiary in California, giving him direct exposure to the Silicon Valley ecosystem and a comparative perspective on cluster development models. He co-founded GameSquad with Chardot before establishing TeK5, a studio specialised in game engine development – a technically demanding niche that demonstrated the sophisticated capabilities that had developed within the Infogrames ecosystem.

Paret succeeded Chardot as president of Lyon Games and proved particularly effective in developing relationships with local political leadership. His approach to collective organisation emphasised the distinction between competition and collegiality.

Christophe Nazaret and Laurent Salmeron completed the founding core of entrepreneurs who initiated the collective mobilisation. Both shared the common Infogrames background and the technical expertise that characterised Lyon's development community. Nazaret subsequently

founded his own studio in southern France, continuing to develop game engine technology for mobile platforms. Salmeron, founder of Adeline Software, represented the first generation of Infogrames spin-offs, predating even the formal cluster organisation.

Pierre Mousson joined the founding group in a second phase, bringing business school training from the United States and a more structured approach to economic development. His arrival marked the beginning of professionalisation in cluster management, introducing frameworks and methodologies that complemented the organic networking that had characterised earlier efforts.

6.6.5.2 The Institutional facilitators

The entrepreneurs' initiative would not have succeeded without institutional facilitation from actors positioned at the intersection of public policy and private enterprise. Three figures proved particularly important in creating conditions for collective organisation.

Pascal Sagnol, director of Lyon Infocité, played a crucial facilitating role by proposing the integration of video game activities within the existing association structure. This decision avoided the complications of creating a new organisation from scratch while providing immediate access to administrative infrastructure, established relationships with local authorities, and a framework for mixed public-private governance. Sagnol recognised the potential synergies between video games and the broader digital economy that Lyon Infocité was already supporting, understanding that the sectors shared technological foundations and faced common challenges in gaining institutional recognition.

Lionel Martinez, innovation officer at Grand Lyon (the metropolitan authority), provided the policy framework that enabled public support for cluster development. Arriving in his position in 2000, Martinez brought methodological sophistication to cluster policy, drawing on international benchmarks including Bilbao's urban regeneration, Montreal's multimedia cluster, and Silicon Valley's innovation ecosystem. Martinez's contribution extended beyond facilitation to conceptualisation. He understood clustering as requiring both bottom-up entrepreneurial energy and top-down institutional support, and he worked to ensure that public authorities provided resources without attempting to direct private sector activities: *"The role of the metropolis was to identify where there was ultimately a critical mass that could be boosted, with the ingredients being clustered, a leader, a world-class event, and that's what we had to support or bring to the fore. So my role was ultimately modest: it was to initiate, but to provide a meeting room, if I want to be even more modest, so that these people who knew each other more or less could talk to each other, and to start to stimulate them, to identify what they could do together."* (policymaker)

Gérard Collomb, mayor of Lyon from 2001 to 2017 (with interruption), provided political legitimacy and personal engagement that validated the video game sector's claims to recognition. An unusual figure for a municipal leader – an agrégé in literature with scholarly interests in medieval poetry – Collomb found unexpected common ground with video game creators. His cultural formation enabled him to appreciate the narrative and artistic dimensions of game development that entrepreneurs like Chardot emphasised: *"We could unlock opportunities internationally. That's*

what Olivier Masclef did with Gérard Collomb, for example. They went to Shanghai, and there was a stand there for French video game designers. So, as a result, there may be companies that have worked with the Chinese.”

Pierre Carde represented a different profile from the founding entrepreneurs – a professional manager rather than a studio founder, with formal business education (Sup de Co Montpellier, Paris Dauphine, CELSA) and prior experience at Infogrames as a producer on titles including *Alone in the Dark 4*. His arrival to direct Lyon Game in 2000–2001 marked the transition from volunteer-driven networking to professional cluster management.

Carde’s most significant contribution was the creation of Game Connection in October 2001 – a business-to-business event that would become Lyon’s signature contribution to international video game industry infrastructure. Carde subsequently spun off the Game Connection format into a separate company, Connection Events (founded July 2006), which expanded the model internationally while Lyon Game evolved into Imaginove. This trajectory – from cluster initiative to independent business – illustrated both the entrepreneurial potential within cluster activities and the tensions that could arise between collective and commercial logics.

6.6.5.3 The governance members in Lyon Infocité/Lyon Game (2004)

By April 2004, the governance structure of Lyon Infocité/Lyon Game had formalised into a bicephalous organisation reflecting the distinct but complementary interests of the broader digital economy and the specialised video game sector.

Philippe Renaudin, CEO of Doki Denki studio, served as president of the global Lyon Infocité association. Doki Denki, founded in 1997, had established itself as a significant Lyon-based developer with titles across multiple platforms, giving Renaudin both industry credibility and organisational experience.

Olivier Masclef, CEO of WideScreen Games, served as vice-president with specific responsibility for Lyon Game activities. WideScreen Games’ focus on racing games continued the specialisation that had characterised Lyon’s development community since the *V-Rally* franchise at Eden Studios.

The Lyon Game board included Eric Angelier from Krysalide and Arnaud Blacher from Nobilis as administrators, ensuring representation from studios of different sizes and specialisations. This governance structure embodied the democratic principles that the founders had established: rotation of responsibility, representation of diverse interests, and resistance to domination by any single actor, however economically important.

6.7 The Bordeaux Cluster emergence

6.7.1 Nicolas Gaume & Kalisto: the founding firm

6.7.1.1 The precocious entrepreneurship

The Bordeaux video game cluster's emergence is inseparable from the story of Nicolas Gaume, who founded Kalisto Entertainment in 1990 at the age of 19. Gaume's youth was both an asset and a challenge. As a young entrepreneur, he brought fresh perspectives and a willingness to challenge established conventions. He was unconstrained by prior industry experience that might have counselled caution. Yet his youth also meant limited management experience, fewer established relationships, and a learning curve that would play out in real-time as Kalisto grew.

The founding of Kalisto came at a moment of technological transition in the video game industry. The shift from 2D to 3D graphics, the emergence of CD-ROM as a distribution medium, and the growing sophistication of home gaming platforms created opportunities for studios willing to invest in new technical capabilities. Gaume positioned Kalisto to exploit these transitions, building technical expertise that would distinguish the company's productions.

6.7.1.2 Building Kalisto's identity

Under Gaume's leadership, Kalisto developed a distinctive identity centred on technical ambition and creative risk-taking. The company's productions pushed the boundaries of what was possible on contemporary platforms, establishing a reputation for innovation that attracted talented developers. This identity reflected Gaume's own orientation: he was not content to develop safe, conventional games but sought to create productions that would stand out in a crowded market.

Gaume's approach to company-building combined creative vision with commercial pragmatism. Early in Kalisto's history, the company took on contract work for established publishers – including *Pac-In-Time* for Namco – that provided revenue to support the development of more ambitious original projects. This strategy allowed Kalisto to build capabilities and relationships while maintaining financial viability.

As Kalisto grew, Gaume emerged as a spokesperson for the French video game industry more broadly. His youth and success made him an attractive figure for media coverage, and he used this visibility to advocate for the industry's recognition as a legitimate creative and economic sector. This public role would later inform his transition to industry leadership following Kalisto's collapse.

6.7.1.3 Gaume's journey post-Kalisto

Rather than retreating from the video game industry after the collapse of his company, which was liquidated in 2002, Nicolas Gaume leveraged his experience and relationships to assume national leadership roles that would prove beneficial for the entire French industry. He became involved in the creation and governance of trade unions at the national level.

His involvement in founding APOM in 2001 positioned him at the centre of efforts to create collective representation for the French video game industry. The timing was significant: Gaume helped create the institutional framework for industry advocacy in the immediate aftermath of his own company's failure. His experience of the crisis informed his understanding of what the industry needed.

Gaume's subsequent service as president of SNJV (2009–2014) placed him in the leading role for national industry advocacy during a critical period. Under his leadership, the organisation successfully advocated for the implementation of the CIJV tax credit. This policy achievement, which had been the goal of industry advocacy since APOM's founding, demonstrated the effectiveness of organised representation.

6.7.2 Kalisto entertainment: rise and fall

6.7.2.1 Commercial success and rapid growth

Kalisto achieved significant commercial success in the mid-to-late 1990s, which established Bordeaux as a serious video game production centre.

Dark Earth (1997), a post-apocalyptic role-playing game, demonstrated the studio's narrative and artistic ambitions. The game's atmospheric world-building and innovative mechanics attracted critical attention, positioning Kalisto as a creative force rather than merely a contract developer.

Nightmare Creatures achieved sales exceeding 2 million copies, establishing Kalisto as a commercially significant player in the global video game market. This success generated revenues that funded continued expansion and attracted investor interest. The game's commercial performance demonstrated that a French studio outside Paris could compete with international rivals on major releases.

The company's growth during this period was substantial. At its peak, Kalisto employed between 250 and 300 people – a remarkable scale for a French video game company outside of Infogrames. The workforce included specialists in programming, art, design, and production, creating a concentration of video game talent in Bordeaux that had not previously existed.

6.7.2.2 International expansion

International expansion accompanied domestic growth. Following Kalisto's acquisition of Mindscape in 1996, the company established offices in the United States, the United Kingdom, Japan, and China. This global footprint reflected ambitions to compete with the leading video game publishers worldwide and to access markets beyond France and Europe.

The international expansion created both opportunities and challenges. Access to global markets increased Kalisto's commercial potential. Relationships with international partners provided knowledge and capabilities that enriched the company's development. Yet the expanded footprint also increased organisational complexity and required management capabilities that the young company was still developing.

By the late 1990s, Kalisto had developed over 50 games and established itself as one of France's most significant independent game developers. The company's trajectory seemed to validate Gaume's ambitious vision and to demonstrate the potential for French studios to achieve global success.

6.7.2.3 The IPO and its consequences

Kalisto's IPO in 1999 also led to the creation of vulnerabilities that would contribute to its eventual collapse. The IPO raised significant capital, enabling continued investment in development and expansion. It validated Gaume's vision and provided resources for ambitious new projects.

However, the IPO also created shareholder expectations for sustained growth and returns that would prove difficult to meet during the following crisis. The timing of the IPO, coinciding with the peak of the dot-com bubble, meant that Kalisto accessed capital markets at valuations that would not be sustainable. When the bubble burst in 2000, the company's stock price declined sharply.

The financial structure created by the IPO became a trap as conditions deteriorated. Declining stock prices constrained access to additional financing. Covenant concerns with creditors limited operational flexibility. The expectations established during the IPO era could not be met in the post-bubble environment, creating pressure that the company could not withstand.

Kalisto Entertainment entered liquidation in January 2002, just over a decade after its founding. The collapse resulted from the intersection of external market conditions with internal financial vulnerabilities. Several ambitious projects in development consumed resources without generating near-term revenue. The contraction of publishing deals and the reluctance of investors to provide additional financing created a liquidity crisis that the company could not overcome.

The human impact of Kalisto's failure was substantial and immediate. The sudden loss of 250-300 jobs represented a significant shock to the Bordeaux economy and to the individuals and families affected. Former employees faced an uncertain future in a city that had only recently developed a significant video game sector – there were no obvious alternative employers of comparable scale.

The collapse was particularly devastating because of its speed. Unlike Infogrames' prolonged decline, which allowed for gradual adjustment, Kalisto's liquidation was sudden. Employees learned of the company's end with little warning. Projects in development were abandoned. The ecosystem that had developed around the company was abruptly disrupted.

The liquidation of Kalisto marked the end of a dynamic human, entrepreneurial and industrial adventure. For Bordeaux, it spelled the end of a dream of a new economy where a young company could reach considerable heights in just a few years and create 300 direct jobs. Yet, this economy proved to be risky, as evidenced by the end of Kalisto's incredible journey.

Apart from its significant economic impacts, the collapse of Kalisto was a social tragedy. Around three hundred people became jobless in an area with no single other video games company to take them on. Moreover, there were no video game education programmes, no specialised suppliers or venture capital and no institutional support for game development. In ecosystem terms, the environment was completely hostile for any new venture in the video games industry.

To make things worse, the only legacy that the company seems to have left behind in the region appears to be a significant trauma: a deep-seated aversion of most stakeholders to this ill-fated sector.

6.7.3 The creative diaspora: immediate aftermath

6.7.3.1 The founding of Asobo Studio

The most immediate and significant response to Kalisto's collapse was the creation of Asobo Studio in 2002 by 12 former Kalisto employees. The founders moved with remarkable speed: within months of Kalisto's liquidation, they had established a new company, acquired the assets of the defunct Super Farm studio, and begun development on new projects.

This rapid entrepreneurial response demonstrated that the human capital developed at Kalisto had not been destroyed by the company's failure – it had merely been redistributed. The 12 founders brought with them the technical expertise, creative capabilities, and industry relationships developed during their Kalisto years. These assets could be deployed in a new organisational context.

The founding of Asobo represented a deliberate choice to remain in Bordeaux and in the video game industry. The founders could have sought employment elsewhere, relocated to regions with more developed video game sectors, or left the industry entirely. Their decision to stay and found a local studio demonstrated a commitment to both the industry and the region that had been created during the Kalisto era.

Asobo's founding team faced a challenging environment. The broader video game industry was experiencing the aftermath of the 2001–2003 crisis. Access to financing was constrained. Publisher caution following recent failures made securing development contracts more difficult. Yet the founders persevered, adopting an approach that differed from Kalisto's aggressive expansion.

The early strategy focused on contract development for established publishers and licensed properties. Working with partners including Disney, Pixar, Universal, Fox, and Hasbro, Asobo developed games based on popular animated films and franchises. This work-for-hire approach provided steady revenue while the studio was engaged in building its capabilities and reputation.

This strategy reflected lessons learned from the Kalisto experience. Rather than pursuing rapid expansion financed through equity markets, Asobo prioritised sustainable growth funded through operational revenues. Rather than betting on original intellectual property that required substantial upfront investment, the studio focused on developing technical capabilities through contract work that carried lower financial risk.

6.7.3.2 The broader entrepreneurial response

Asobo was the largest but not the only entrepreneurial response to Kalisto's collapse. The years following 2002 saw the emergence of additional ventures founded by former Kalisto employees or enabled by the ecosystem that had developed around the company. Several resources and assets

remained in the devastated landscape of 2002 (“The Kalisto way”, shared technical knowledge and organisational processes, reputational capital, etc.), and were mainly internalised within employees rather than institutionalised territorially. When Kalisto declared bankruptcy, these resources acted as seeds that allowed the emergence of a new video game development ecosystem.

Even if the main bulk of the former Kalisto’s employees either migrated to more thriving video games ecosystems, such as Montréal, or opted to work in other local industries, several talents chose to remain in the local industry. Many factors can explain these decisions: quality of life, family ties, lower living costs and most of all: emerging opportunities for collaboration with former colleagues.

As detailed in the following table (Table 15), and apart from Asobo, the immediate post-Kalisto period saw the creation of at least 6 new studios, which represented diverse approaches to game development. Jean-Dominique Lauwereins, a former Kalisto employee, and Sylvie Clin founded BeTomorrow in 2002, a studio specialised in connected mobile applications for sports and video games. Pascal Jarry, former COO of Kalisto, did the same and created SolidGame, an innovation management consulting firm, whereas Fabrice Carré established Mad Monkey Studio in 2003 as the entertainment division of an IT services company which provides interactive solutions for the video game industry. Other companies were also established at that time, with varying degrees of success. In addition to these founding members, the industry at that time included other companies, notably MotionTwin, founded in 2001 by three people, two of whom had worked at Kalisto, and In-Fusio, a major player in mobile gaming. Motion Twin would notably develop *Dead Cells*, which sold over 6 million copies. BeTomorrow pioneered mobile game development and real-time sports tracking systems. AtOnce Technologies, founded in 2004, focused on middleware solutions and was recognised with a National Innovative Enterprise Competition award. These diverse ventures demonstrated that the skills developed at Kalisto could generate value across multiple market segments and technology platforms.

Table 15. Companies created by former Kalisto employees after the company’s collapse.

Company	Founders	Employment at Kalisto	Last position at Kalisto
Asobo (2002)	S. Wloch	8 years (1994–2002)	Tech skills (Lead Developer)
	D. Dedeine	5 years (1997–2002)	Design & art skills (Game designer)
	R. Musti	Unknown	Design & art skills (Level design)
	M. Bossard	6 years (1996–2002)	Tech skills (Software engineer)

	N. Coquard	7 years (1995–2002)	Project Management skills (Game manager)
	C. Rousseau	2 years (2000–2002)	Design & art skills (Artist 3D)
	F. Sseiss	Unknown	Unknown
	F. Manon	4 years (1998–2002)	Design & art skills (Graphist)
	A. Guyet	10 years (1992–2002)	Tech skills (Lead Programmer)
	N. Becavin	2 years (2000–2002)	Tech skills (Software engineer)
	P. Bourroncle	Unknown	Unknown
	A. Nick	2 years (2000–2002)	Design & art skills (Animator)
AtOnce Technologies (2004)	G. Gainant	4 years (1998–2002)	Tech skills (Software engineer)
	F. Lamidey	5 years (1997–2002)	Design & art skills (Worldbuilder & Content manager)
	P. Rivailon	6 years (1996–2002)	Tech skills (Lead Programmer)
BeTomorrow (2002)	J-D. Lauwereins	2 years (2000–2002)	Tech skills (Online CTO)
SolidGame (2002)	P. Jarry	3 years (1999–2002)	Project Management skills (COO, Head of production)
MadMonkey (2003)	F. Carre	3 years (1999–2002)	Project Management skills (Manager)
MotionTwin (2001)	N. Cannasse	Less than 1 year (1999)	Trainee
	P. Peridont	Unknown	Trainee

The table highlights an interesting pattern. The remaining talents who chose to create local studios had an average of 5–6 years of experience within Kalisto. Almost all of them were present in the

company during its collapse. They presented an interesting heterogeneity with mixed skills ranging from programmers, artists, designers and producers and mixed specialisations in market segments. Early informal coordination between these firms built the foundations of the current video game cluster in the city. Former Kalisto employees maintained social connections, exchanging information about clients, contracts and new opportunities and sharing workspace in converted warehouses. Thus, the first months saw intense informal activity with the shared crisis creating unusual openness for collaboration.

Apart from friendship, these interactions helped the studios to pool crucial information and reduce the uncertainties weighing on their innovation processes. Patterns of collaboration began to form as the studios began combining their capabilities for larger projects that were unattainable for small studios alone. Technical challenges prompted informal knowledge exchanges facilitated by the existing bonds of friendship between the former employees of Kalisto. This solidarity, which seems to be rooted in shared Kalisto training, helped the newly created studios to enhance their production pipelines.

6.7.3.3 The formalisation of collective response

By 2007, the creation of Bordeaux Games, a local professional association, marked an important transition towards intentional clustering. It signalled and triggered an important change in the local dynamics, thus revealing how the 2002–2007 period served as an incubation phase for what would become a fully-fledged and formalised cluster. The association emerged through a bottom-up process, initiated by studio founders who recognised that collective action was a viable and efficient solution for their common challenges: *“The aim was for Bordeaux Games to become a separate entity with its own added value, independent of its members. In other words, why not offer training, organise events, or hold a trade fair?”* (cofounder of Bordeaux Games); and also *“The name Bordeaux Games was inspired by Lyon Games, which is an association.”* (cofounder of Bordeaux Games).

The momentum was both internal, with the development of numerous initiatives by the newly created association Bordeaux Games, and external, with the continuation of the industry’s development in the region. Internally, the association provided a suitable institutional framework to seek public funds and recruit new members. Many collective initiatives were launched and helped to structure the local industry by bringing new resources and working to resolve several structural problems common to the local video game companies: public funding, business development in events and trade fairs, networking initiatives, etc. Externally, the local video game industry experienced an important growth. The number of association members rose from 5 at launch to 17 two years later, then to 31 in 2012, representing 320 employees at that time. The scope of the association activities was enhanced. Many new initiatives were launched. The cluster’s maturation attracted regional government attention, leading to the creation of support programs and mechanisms, including promotional initiatives and funding schemes. This public support helped to amplify the new local dynamics and endow them with additional resources.

6.8 Conclusion

The analysis of the emergence of Lyon and Bordeaux video game clusters reveals that, despite their distinct regional identities and historical specificities, both ecosystems evolved within a shared national context that fundamentally shaped their trajectories.

Both clusters originated from the same foundational moment in French video game history – the entrepreneurial explosion of the 1980s and early 1990s that established France as a significant player in the global industry. Infogrames (Lyon, 1983) and Kalisto Entertainment (Bordeaux, 1990) emerged from this pioneering generation, and both achieved international prominence before succumbing to the systemic crisis of 2001–2003. This shared temporal rhythm – foundation, expansion, crisis, reconstruction – creates a common periodisation that structures the historical development of both clusters and the French video games industry.

The 2001–2003 crisis represented a national inflection point that affected both territories simultaneously. The collapse of Kalisto and the progressive decline of Infogrames were not isolated regional failures but manifestations of broader industry vulnerabilities exposed by the bursting of the Internet bubble. This shared crisis experience created parallel conditions for the “creative diaspora” phenomenon observed in both cases: the dispersion of talent from anchor companies into new entrepreneurial ventures that would eventually constitute more diverse and resilient ecosystems.

The construction of national governance structures provided an institutional framework within which both regional clusters developed. The creation of APOM (2001), its transformation into SNJV (2008), and the successful advocacy for the CIJV tax credit (2008) represented collective achievements that benefited both Lyon and Bordeaux equally. The federal governance model adopted by SNJV – with board representation from regional clusters – ensured that national policy positions reflected diverse territorial perspectives while enabling coordinated advocacy on issues like tax policy, training standards, and international representation.

Both clusters developed analogous organisational forms through similar evolutionary processes. Lyon progressed from Lyon Infocité to Lyon Game and then Imaginove to Game Only; Bordeaux evolved from informal post-Kalisto networks to Bordeaux Games. Despite differences in timing and specific configurations, both dynamics of emergence reflect a common pattern: initial informal networks giving way to formalised associations.

The multi-scalar articulation of governance – linking local clusters to regional authorities, national syndicates, and European networks – characterises both cases. Both clusters participate in SNJV governance and benefit from national support mechanisms (CIJV, CNC programmes). Both engage with European networks through EGDF membership. This parallel multi-scalar embedding reflects a common French model of cluster governance that balances territorial specificity with national coordination.

Apart from these aspects, the analysis of the entrepreneurial figures who shaped both clusters shows striking commonalities. The two founding figures were visionaries with international ambitions. Bruno Bonnell (Infogrames) and Nicolas Gaume (Kalisto) both founded their companies

at remarkably young ages with ambitions that transcended regional and national boundaries. Both pursued aggressive growth strategies financed through public equity markets. Both achieved significant international presence before their companies' difficulties became insurmountable. Their parallel trajectories – from regional entrepreneurs to global industry figures to eventual departure from their founding companies – reveal common patterns in the scaling challenges faced by French video game pioneers.

The post-crisis trajectories of key figures demonstrate how entrepreneurial failure in creative industries can generate, rather than destroy, leadership capacity. Nicolas Gaume's transformation from Kalisto founder to APOM co-founder to SNJV president (2009–2014) exemplifies this pattern. His experience of company failure provided credibility and motivation for building collective institutions that would help others avoid similar fates. The Bordeaux cluster's contributions to national governance – through Gaume's SNJV leadership and the territorial representation model – reflect how regional crisis generated national institutional innovation.

Both clusters benefited from figures who operated at the intersection of business and policy. In Lyon, actors like Pierre Carde (creator of Game Connection) and Lionel Martinez (Grand Lyon) bridged entrepreneurial and institutional logics. In Bordeaux, the founding teams of Bordeaux Games similarly combined industry credibility with capacity for public engagement. These institutional entrepreneurs share common characteristics: legitimacy derived from professional experience, ability to articulate collective interests, and skill in navigating both commercial and political environments.

In both clusters, shared professional backgrounds created the relational foundations for collective action. Lyon's founding entrepreneurs – Hubert Chardot, Laurent Paret, Olivier Masclef, and others – shared Infogrames' origins that provided common references, mutual trust, and proven collaborative capacity. Bordeaux's post-Kalisto entrepreneurs, including the 12 founders of Asobo Studio, similarly drew on shared professional experience to enable rapid collective mobilisation. This pattern suggests that anchor company employment, even when ending in crisis, creates human capital that includes not only individual skills but also relational networks enabling subsequent collective organisation.

The examination of Lyon and Bordeaux reveals that French video game clusters, despite their regional distinctiveness, share fundamental commonalities rooted in national industry dynamics, common institutional frameworks, and analogous entrepreneurial patterns. The creative diaspora phenomenon – whereby anchor company collapse catalysed more diverse ecosystem development – operated similarly in both territories. The construction of multi-scalar governance linking local, regional, and national levels followed parallel paths. The entrepreneurial figures who shaped both clusters exhibited common characteristics: international ambition, capacity to transform failure into institutional leadership, skill in bridging public and private worlds, and commitment to democratic governance.

These commonalities suggest that the French video game industry, despite its geographical distribution across multiple regional clusters, constitutes a coherent national ecosystem with shared characteristics, common challenges, and collective institutional achievements. The CIJV tax credit,

the SNJV governance model, the training certification system, and the inter-cluster collaboration mechanisms represent collective goods that benefit all French clusters while respecting their territorial specificities.

7 THE FUNDÃO CLUSTER

7.1 Data collection and analysis

This chapter employs a dual methodological approach combining documentary analysis with oral history interviews to reconstruct the historical trajectory leading to the Fundão gaming cluster's formation. The research aligns with T4.3 objectives, using both textual evidence and stakeholder perspectives to provide a comprehensive understanding of the cluster's development. All data collection activities, including both archival research and interviews, were conducted between February and November 2025. This comprehensive temporal frame allowed for the systematic gathering of historical materials while conducting in-depth conversations with key stakeholders who shaped the region's innovation ecosystem.

The documentary analysis phase examined diverse historical materials to trace the early history of gaming in Fundão and the broader innovation ecosystem that enabled its emergence. The archival work focused on multiple types of sources that together provided a multifaceted view of the cluster's development. Municipal strategic plans and policy documents, particularly the foundational Fundão Innovation Plan from 2012, offered insight into the official vision and strategic frameworks guiding the municipality's transformation. Government reports and public records from municipal and regional institutions documented the formal actions, programmes, and investments that operationalised the innovation strategy. Educational materials and documents revealed how academic institutions adapted to support gaming education and talent development. Records detailing the creation of innovation infrastructure, such as the Living Lab Cova da Beira,¹² illuminated the governance structures and collaborative mechanisms established to coordinate diverse stakeholders. Documentation from national and regional innovation programmes provided context on how Fundão's initiatives connected to broader policy frameworks and funding opportunities. Together, these materials provided essential context for understanding the institutional foundations supporting the cluster's emergence and the formal policy frameworks guiding territorial development.

Five semi-structured interviews were conducted with individuals who played significant roles in Fundão's innovation ecosystem development. To maintain confidentiality in accordance with GDPR, interviewees are not identified by name in this analysis. The sample was carefully selected to represent diverse perspectives and roles within the ecosystem. The group included the municipal mayor, who provided leadership for over twelve years, bringing political vision and sustained commitment to the innovation strategy. The head of the innovation division, responsible for strategic planning and implementation, offered operational insights into how policies were translated into programmes and actions. A municipal official working directly on innovation

¹² <https://www.ccdrc.pt/pt/fundao-vai-acolher-living-lab-da-cova-da-beira/>.

programmes provided ground-level perspectives on community engagement, business support, and infrastructure development. A former gaming industry professional now active in international advocacy brought the perspective of someone who moved to Fundão during the ecosystem's early development and subsequently built a career in gaming. Finally, a professional with experience in both public sector roles and private innovation consulting offered insights spanning both municipal strategy development and its broader regional and economic context.

The interviews followed a semi-structured protocol developed by UNITO for T4.3 and adapted to address the specificities of the Fundão context. This approach guided conversations through several key areas while maintaining flexibility to explore unexpected themes. This semi-structured format balanced the need for comparable data across interviews with openness to emergent insights, allowing interviewees to emphasise what they found most significant while ensuring that all key analytical themes were addressed.

The analysis phase combined thematic analysis of documentary sources with oral historiographical methods, integrating these complementary approaches to build a comprehensive historical reconstruction. Documentary materials were systematically reviewed to identify all references to gaming, innovation policies, territorial development strategies, and key events or milestones. This review created a chronological framework of formal actions, policy decisions, and institutional developments. Interview transcripts were analysed for recurring themes that appeared across multiple respondents, narratives about causation that explained why certain developments occurred, identification of critical actors and institutions that shaped outcomes, and perceptions of turning points that marked significant shifts in the ecosystem's trajectory. The analytical process paid particular attention to how different actors understood and explained the same events, recognising that multiple valid perspectives might coexist. Cross-referencing between documentary evidence and interview data enabled triangulation and validation of historical claims. When documents and interviews aligned, this provided strong evidence for particular interpretations. Discrepancies between sources, rather than being treated as problems, provided opportunities to explore multiple perspectives on contested or ambiguous aspects of the history. These varying perspectives enriched understanding rather than undermining it, revealing the complexity of historical processes and the multiplicity of factors influencing cluster development.

7.2 Cluster general historical information

7.2.1 Brief description of the cluster

Fundão, located in the Castelo Branco District of central Portugal, within the Beiras and Serra da Estrela sub-region, has long been known for its rich agricultural landscape, particularly its cherry cultivation. However, the region has faced significant demographic and economic challenges, including a gradual population decline and an ageing demographic. According to the 2021 census, Fundão's population stood at 26,503, a decrease from 31,482 in 2001. The average age of the

population is notably high, with a substantial proportion (32.5%) of residents over the age of 65 as of 2023.¹³ These challenges have made economic diversification a critical focus for the municipality.

In response to these challenges, Fundão has undergone a remarkable transformation over the past two decades, shifting from a predominantly agricultural economy to one focused on technology and innovation. This shift began with the launch of the Fundão Innovation Plan in 2012, a strategic initiative aimed at repositioning the municipality as a hub for digital innovation, particularly in software development, IT, and digital media.¹⁴ The plan sought to attract high-tech companies and foster entrepreneurship, which has led to the development of a more diversified economic base.

The impact of this transformation is evident in the region's economic growth. By 2022, the tertiary sector had grown significantly, employing over 3,200 individuals in Fundão. The tourism sector has also seen substantial development, further diversifying the local economy.¹⁵ Notably, Fundão has experienced modest population growth in recent years, with a 1.3% increase from 2022 to 2023, reversing a decades-long decline.¹⁶ This is attributed in part to the success of the municipality's innovation initiatives, which have attracted skilled professionals, including a significant number of international migrants. One of the strategic decisions Fundão made after the COVID-19 pandemic was to focus on the rising video game industry, capitalising on trends within Portugal's broader digital economy. In alignment with national strategies like Portugal Digital Strategy¹⁷, Fundão has made notable strides in developing its own gaming cluster. The partnership with Universidade da Beira Interior (UBI)¹⁸ in nearby Covilhã has played a key role in developing a talent pipeline for the sector, offering specialised education in game design and software engineering. Fundão's appeal as a location for the gaming cluster extends beyond its strategic initiatives to include its quality-of-life advantages. The municipality offers a peaceful environment with affordable living costs, access to nature, safety, and the possibility of a car-free lifestyle due to its compact city centre.

These lifestyle factors, combined with genuine economic opportunities, have attracted both returning Portuguese talent and international professionals seeking alternatives to the high living costs of coastal urban centres. Today, Fundão stands as a key case study of a rural municipality successfully leveraging strategic vision, institutional support, and quality of life factors to develop a nascent but growing gaming cluster. This region's evolution from a traditionally agricultural economy to a tech-driven hub serves as a model for other rural areas seeking to diversify and attract new industries.

¹³ <https://repositorio.iscte-iul.pt/handle/10071/17570>.

¹⁴ https://www.interregeurope.eu/sites/default/files/inline/file_1545388692.pdf.

¹⁵ <https://www.gee.gov.pt/pt/docs/doc-o-gee-2/estatisticas-regionais/distritos-concelhos/castelo-branco/fundao/3055-fundao/file>.

¹⁶ <https://movetofundao2024.pt/>.

¹⁷ <https://digital.gov.pt/pt/documentos/portugal-digital-strategy>.

¹⁸ <https://www.ubi.pt/>.

7.3 Temporal perimeter: Cluster History

7.3.1 'Year Zero'

The year 2012 represents the foundational moment for Fundão's contemporary innovation ecosystem and, consequently, the preconditions for its eventual gaming cluster. This year marked the beginning of strategic planning for what would become the Fundão Innovation Plan (*Plano Estratégico de Inovação do Fundão*) under the leadership of Paulo Fernandes, who was serving as Vice-Mayor and would assume the full mayorship in 2013. The convergence of strategic thinking and initial actions during this period created the conditions from which the gaming cluster would later emerge, making 2012 the logical choice for identifying the cluster's "year zero".

The year 2012 is significant for several convergent reasons that, together, constitute a transformative moment. As one official described, this new socio-economic strategy for Fundão began to be developed in mid-2012, when Paulo Fernandes started his term as Mayor, initially substituting the previous mayor who suspended his mandate one year before term end. Even in that transitional moment, one year before the 2013 elections, the decision was made to design this new strategy called *the innovation plan*. The process was done very openly, collaboratively, and participatively, involving local, regional, and national partners. Importance was placed on listening to the community and citizens to understand their needs and expectations.

The design phase of the innovation plan occurred rapidly during 2012. One official recalled the team starting in March or April 2012, and by May, presenting the first draft of the plan. From there, implementation began incrementally, taking "baby steps". The first action was creating a structure in Fundão aimed at fostering innovation within the digital sector, recognising it as a huge opportunity for rural and low-density areas. The rationale was that with significant digitalisation of economic activity, people could work from anywhere to anywhere in the world, allowing them to choose where they want to live based on their desired lifestyle, rather than opting for larger cities for employment reasons.

The context of demographic crisis gave urgency to these initiatives. As one municipal architect recalled, in 2012, the municipality was losing around two people per day to foreign countries and large cities, and if this path continued, the city would disappear. Another official emphasised that the innovation strategy was clearly born in the context of crisis, during the period of Troika¹⁹ intervention (European Commission, European Central Bank, and International Monetary Fund), with Portugal highly conditioned in its investment capacity, in a strong context of restriction regarding confidence and investment.

The Mayor himself described the decision-making during this period. He explained that when he was part of the municipal government as Vice-Mayor and councillor, he became very aware that in the case of Fundão and other low-density territories, it was necessary to significantly strengthen capacity to act on the value of innovation: "*As a municipality so characterised by traditional sectors, such as agriculture and even traditional industry, it was crucial to create more value and diversify*

¹⁹ <https://www.bportugal.pt/listagem/memorando-de-entendimento-sobre-condicionalidades-de-politica-economica>.

revenue sources. *Innovation and technology would be fundamental partners in achieving these goals*". Technological factors needed, therefore, integration into structures, especially economic ones, and that economic activity diversification was essential. However, the critical challenge was "how" – while all could agree on technology's importance, the question was how to make it a reality. The decision was made to move forward with an innovation plan in 2012, not a conventional strategic plan, but rather an innovation one, disruptive in terms of public policy.

A key early initiative in 2012 was the PechaKucha²⁰ events. One official recalled doing this work with the Mayor and a very small team of one or two people. They met early in the morning, at 7 a.m., when there was time to identify people who had some connection to Fundão – those who were born there, had family there, or had lived there and achieved success around the world – and invite them to share ideas and experiences. The events, following the Japanese (PechaKucha) format of 6 minutes and 40 seconds presentations (20 slides with 20 seconds per slide automatically), gathered about seven or eight editions in a short space of time. These events played a very important role in collecting ideas and contributions for the strategy.

The relationship between 2012 as "year zero" for innovation planning and the later emergence of gaming as a distinct focus reflects the layered, evolutionary nature of cluster formation. The 2012 initiatives created enabling conditions – the beginning of talent attraction strategies, innovation infrastructure planning, and quality of life improvements – that would eventually allow gaming companies to establish themselves. But gaming was not an explicit focus in 2012; rather, it emerged organically as the ecosystem matured.

7.3.2 Before 'Year Zero'

7.3.2.1 Actors and Individual Developers

Before 2012, Fundão possessed virtually no visible actors specifically engaged in video game development or the gaming industry. The territory lacked game studios, organised developer communities, or individuals publicly identifying as game creators. Unlike some European gaming clusters that emerged from demoscene cultures, hobbyist programming communities, or early software industries, Fundão had no such proto-gaming community. The actors who would later become central to the gaming cluster were, during this period, either not yet present in the territory, not yet engaged with gaming professionally, or were students beginning their technical education without yet specialising in games. The actors who would prove crucial to the innovation ecosystem's formation were primarily engaged in other domains during the pre-2012 period. Mayor Fernandes was working in regional development, community animation, and territorial development projects, including the Aldeias do Xisto, but not specifically focused on technology or gaming. Municipal officials who would later lead innovation initiatives were working in traditional municipal services – tourism, culture, urban planning – developing administrative capacity and territorial knowledge, but not yet oriented towards innovation ecosystems. One official described beginning their professional career at the Municipality of Fundão at the beginning of the millennium, integrated into tourism

²⁰ <https://www.pechakucha.com/>.

services in 2001, working directly with Paulo Fernandes on programmes connecting traditional territorial identity with contemporary animation and events. At UBI, faculty members were contemplating gaming education during this period, representing a crucial pre-cluster actor whose vision would materialise in 2014 with the launch of the gaming course. Students were enrolled in computer science and multimedia programmes, acquiring technical skills without yet having access to specialised gaming education. Some of these students would later become early employees of gaming companies or founders of studios, but during the pre-2012 period, they were simply university students pursuing general technical education.

7.3.2.2 Market Conditions

The market for video game development in Fundão before 2012 was essentially non-existent. There was no local demand for game development services, no companies commissioning games, and no established pathways to market games commercially. The broader Portuguese gaming market was small, fragmented, and heavily concentrated in Lisbon and Porto. International markets were accessible theoretically through digital distribution platforms that were beginning to democratise game publishing, but Portuguese developers generally lacked the knowledge, networks, and resources to access these markets effectively. The local economy remained oriented towards traditional sectors that bore no relationship to gaming, like cherry and textile production, nature tourism, cultural heritage, and gastronomy. There was no local market for digital services generally, let alone for specialised creative digital products like games. The absence of a local market meant that any future gaming activity would need to orient towards external markets from inception. Unlike some industries that can grow serving local demand before expanding regionally or nationally, gaming in Fundão would necessarily be export-oriented, targeting national and international markets. This characteristic would shape the cluster's later development, requiring companies to develop international connections, marketing capabilities, and cultural competencies from their earliest stages.

7.3.2.3 Individual Programmers and Technical Talent

Before 2012, the territory possessed some technical talent through UBI's computer science and multimedia programmes, though not specifically oriented towards gaming. These programmes produced graduates with programming skills in various languages, an understanding of software engineering principles, database design knowledge, and competencies in digital media production. However, as one academic expert would later note, the challenge was that most graduates historically migrated elsewhere for job opportunities, characterising the interior's biggest industry as the human capital it exported – training students who then left. The technical talent that did exist locally was employed primarily in traditional sectors, public administration, or small businesses providing IT support services. There were no concentrations of programmers working in creative or innovative contexts, no culture of experimental projects or side ventures, and minimal awareness of contemporary software development practices common in technology hubs. The few technology professionals present were typically working in isolated positions rather than as part of technical

teams or communities. Individual programmers with gaming interests likely existed, but remained invisible, pursuing gaming as a personal hobby rather than a professional activity. Without local community, events, or visible role models, these individuals had no way to connect or recognise gaming as a viable career path. The democratisation of game development tools that was beginning to enable indie game creation globally had not yet reached or been recognised in this interior Portuguese territory.

7.3.2.4 Institutions

The institutional landscape before 2012, as already described in the previous section, consisted primarily of organisations oriented towards traditional sectors and conventional development approaches. UBI stood out as the most significant institution with potential relevance to future gaming development, though its connection was indirect through general technical education. During this pre-2012 period, the gaming course was still in the conceptual phase, but not yet having launched specialised gaming education. The municipality itself was the other crucial institution, possessing administrative capacity and territorial development experience, but not yet oriented towards innovation or technology attraction in the systematic way that would emerge from 2012 onward.

Importantly, institutions specifically supporting gaming or creative industries did not exist. There were no industry associations for game developers, no gaming-focused incubators or accelerators, no events or conferences bringing together gaming practitioners, and no policy frameworks recognising gaming as a sector worthy of support. At the national level, the Portuguese gaming industry's fragmentation meant that even in metropolitan centres, institutional support was minimal. Organisations that would later play roles in the national gaming ecosystem, such as the Portuguese Association of Videogame Developers,²¹ were either not yet formed or not yet effective. The absence of gaming-specific institutions meant that when gaming activity eventually emerged in Fundão, it would need to fit within or adapt to general innovation support structures rather than accessing specialised gaming infrastructure. This would prove both a challenge and an opportunity – a challenge as generic support might not address gaming's specific needs, but an opportunity because gaming would benefit from integration within a broader innovation ecosystem rather than being isolated in a single-sector focus.

7.3.2.5 Education

Education represented an essential precondition for gaming cluster emergence, though this potential was not yet fully recognised or activated before 2012. UBI's computer science programmes throughout the 2000s and early 2010s provided foundational technical education relevant to game development. Students learned programming, algorithms, data structures, computer graphics, human-computer interaction, and other topics directly applicable to creating interactive digital entertainment. The quality of this education meant that graduates possessed

²¹ <https://apvp.pt/>.

technical competencies comparable to those from metropolitan universities, even if the “UBI brand” lacked the prestige of institutions in Lisbon or Porto. Crucially, the conception and planning of UBI’s gaming course occurred during this pre-2012 period. This comprehensive approach to gaming education would distinguish the programme when it was launched in 2014 from purely technical training. However, educational infrastructure beyond UBI was not oriented towards gaming, or even towards technology generally. Secondary schools offered traditional academic tracks preparing students for university or professional tracks focused on conventional trades. There was no coding education in schools, no digital literacy emphasis, and minimal use of technology in pedagogy. The gap between UBI’s technical education and secondary school preparation meant that students often arrived at university with limited prior technical background, requiring foundational skill development before advancing to specialised topics. The challenge of graduate retention meant that educational investments did not automatically translate into local economic development; UBI could produce technically skilled graduates, but without local employment opportunities matching their qualifications and aspirations, these graduates departed immediately upon degree completion. The innovation strategy planning that began in 2012 would need to complement educational capacity with employment opportunities, entrepreneurial support, quality of life advantages, and community building to transform educational outputs into sustainable local economic activity.

7.3.3 Institutional support before the cluster

7.3.3.1 University of Beira Interior (UBI)

As mentioned before, UBI played a foundational role in creating preconditions for Fundão’s gaming cluster even before 2012. UBI maintained strong programmes in computer science and multimedia despite the challenges of operating in a non-metropolitan location, providing the region with an unusual asset: an institution capable of forming highly skilled technical graduates. Within UBI’s academic community, Professor Abel Gomes and Professor Ernesto Vilar had been contemplating for years the creation of specialised programmes in video game design and development, recognising gaming’s transition from niche entertainment to a major global industry. The university’s decision to launch Portugal’s first university video game development course in 2012 represented both the culmination of years of faculty vision and a crucial enabler of the gaming cluster’s emergence. UBI’s later contribution to the gaming cluster would prove more effective precisely because the Fundão Innovation Plan created local opportunities that gave graduates reasons to stay or return.

7.3.3.2 Regional Development Structures and Experience

Before 2012, the Beira Interior region possessed institutional structures focused on territorial development, though oriented primarily towards traditional sectors. The municipal government maintained divisions focused on tourism promotion, cultural programming, and urban planning. Regional development programmes, particularly European Union frameworks like LEADER, had created experience with participatory planning, project design, and accessing external funding. The

Mayor's extensive background included work on integrated forest development, organisation of small forest producers with a capacity-building focus, empowering rural women with low qualifications, creating facilities in low-density areas, and integrated community development approaches. He was also the founder of various development tools, including associations and cooperatives, serving as President of the Assembly for the Association of Forest Residents and President of the Board for Aldeias do Xisto.²² The Aldeias do Xisto network represented a particularly significant precedent, demonstrating how heritage valorisation, sustainable tourism, and territorial branding could revitalise declining rural villages. This experience would inform the innovation strategy's emphasis on leveraging Fundão's distinctive characteristics as competitive advantages.

7.3.3.3 Cultural institutions

Cultural institutions provided venues for community engagement and maintained connections between the municipality and cultural practitioners, creating foundations for later creative industries development and demonstrating the territory's capacity for collective organisation. One interviewee described involvement in regional cooperation around a project coordinated by the Institute for Nature Conservation. When the project lost resources during the financial crisis, Fundão assumed coordination to prevent financing loss, with this individual dedicating time to PROVERE Buy Nature²³ while the innovation plan work was beginning. This illustrated the municipality's capacity to mobilise around development opportunities and manage complex multi-stakeholder initiatives. However, none of these pre-2012 structures were specifically oriented towards technology, innovation, or creative industries in the modern sense.

7.3.3.4 Employment, Training, and Entrepreneurial Infrastructure

The Institute of Employment and Vocational Training (IEFP), particularly through the Employment Service of Covilhã²⁴, provided workforce development infrastructure. Although not specifically oriented towards gaming or technology before 2012, IEFP's presence meant mechanisms existed for vocational training and workforce retraining. Professional education infrastructure existed in regional secondary schools, offering technical tracks in various fields, though focused on traditional sectors rather than digital technologies. As already stated, Fundão's entrepreneurial ecosystem before 2012 was weak regarding technology ventures; however, traditional entrepreneurship did exist—small business owners in retail, services, and agriculture demonstrated entrepreneurial spirit and business management skills. The challenge was not the absence of entrepreneurial capacity, but its orientation towards traditional sectors and conventional business models.

²² <https://www.aldeiasdoxisto.pt/en/>.

²³ <https://www.ccdrc.pt/pt/areas-de-atuacao/desenvolvimento-regional/inov-e-competitividade/provere/>.

²⁴ <https://iefponline.iefp.pt/IEFP/centros-emprego-detalle.do?idcentro=50>.

7.4 Determining factors in the history of the cluster

7.4.1 Historical circumstances and events surrounding the local industry

The emergence of Fundão's gaming cluster was profoundly shaped by specific historical circumstances that created the conditions for what would otherwise have seemed an improbable development. The most immediate and determinant historical circumstance was Portugal's financial crisis and Troika intervention (2008-2012), which created a paradoxical context of constraint and opportunity. Yet this very severity forced unconventional thinking and created political space for radical experimentation. The necessity-driven character of the response gave it authenticity and urgency that might have been absent during more prosperous times when incremental improvements seemed sufficient.

The political transition in 2011-2013, when the previous mayor suspended his mandate, and Paulo Fernandes assumed leadership first as substitute and then through a formal election, provided the second crucial circumstance. This transition brought to municipal leadership someone whose entire professional background prepared him specifically for territorial transformation initiatives. His decision to immediately initiate strategic planning in 2012 rather than maintain the status quo until elections demonstrated both urgency and confidence in a radically different approach. The 2013 electoral validation provided political legitimacy for sustained implementation over more than a decade, creating the temporal stability essential for long-term ecosystem building.

The broader technological and economic circumstances of the 2010s created enabling conditions for gaming cluster emergence in non-traditional locations. The democratisation of game development tools, becoming accessible to small teams, lowered barriers to entry that had previously required substantial capital and specialised expertise. Digital distribution platforms like Steam, App Store, and Google Play eliminated traditional publishing gatekeepers, enabling direct market access from any location with internet connectivity. The rise of indie game development as culturally and commercially significant demonstrated that small teams anywhere could create successful games, challenging the assumption that gaming required concentration in established hubs. Remote work practices were gradually normalising in technology sectors even before COVID-19, with companies increasingly accepting distributed teams and location-independent work arrangements. However, Portugal's national context provided mixed circumstances for gaming development. No tax relief comparable to the UK's Video Games Tax Relief existed, and public funding mechanisms generally did not recognise gaming as a strategic sector. Gaming industry infrastructure – associations, events, networks – was weak and disconnected. This meant that when gaming activity emerged in Fundão, it developed largely outside established national industry structures, relying on municipal innovation support rather than gaming-specific national programmes. This circumstance was both a constraint – lacking established support systems – and opportunity – avoiding path dependencies and established hierarchies that might have favoured metropolitan locations.

The COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2023) represented an unexpected historical circumstance that paradoxically accelerated Fundão's model. The pandemic normalised remote work industry-wide

almost overnight, eliminating the perceived strangeness or risk of working from interior locations. Metropolitan residents confined to small apartments during lockdowns suddenly valued space, nature, and quality of life in ways that had been difficult to communicate previously. Economic uncertainty made lower living costs more attractive. The pandemic validated Fundão's distributed work model precisely when the municipality was mature enough to capitalise on this validation, attracting professionals relocating from Lisbon and Porto who brought expertise and networks that strengthened the emerging gaming sector.

These historical circumstances created a unique temporal window in which a gaming cluster could emerge in Fundão. No single circumstance was sufficient; rather, their convergence and interaction over more than a decade created the conditions for this improbable development. The detailed chronology of how these circumstances unfolded and interacted through specific events, decisions, and turning points is presented in section 7.5.

7.4.2 Exogenous factors

7.4.2.1 National Policy Context and Gaming Industry Recognition

Portugal's national gaming policy landscape evolved gradually during the period under study, shaping the environment in which Fundão's gaming cluster emerged. During the early 2010s, the Portuguese gaming sector received minimal public recognition or dedicated support. However, by the late 2010s, national awareness was gradually increasing. The eGamesLab consortium²⁵ emerged as an initiative aimed at establishing Portugal as a gaming development hub, mobilising a fragmented industry and increasing international visibility. Moreover, the Portuguese Association of Videogame Developers began providing industry representation. The limited national institutional support meant that Fundão's gaming development occurred largely outside established industry structures, relying instead on the municipality's broader innovation support mechanisms.

7.4.2.2 European Union Frameworks and Regional Policy

European Union regional policy frameworks significantly influenced Fundão's approach, even if indirectly. Smart Specialisation Strategies (RIS3) encouraged territorial innovation and place-based development approaches that aligned with Fundão's strategy. The URBACT²⁶ programme, focused on sustainable urban development and innovation, provided both framework and validation. Fundão participated in URBACT projects, gaining European recognition for its innovative approach. One official noted that participation in European cooperation projects recognised the strategy developed in this territory for creating value, attracting investment, employment and innovation, and welcoming citizens from throughout the world, constituting an example of good practices.

²⁵ <https://egameslab.pt/>.

²⁶ <https://urbact.eu>.

These European frameworks provided legitimacy, networking opportunities, and conceptual models that informed Fundão's approach. The Living Lab model itself, which became central to Fundão's governance structure, emerged from European innovation thinking.

7.4.2.3 Global Gaming Industry Trends and Technological Democratisation

Several global trends in the gaming industry created favourable conditions for cluster emergence in non-traditional locations like Fundão. The democratisation of game development tools, particularly Unity and Unreal Engine becoming accessible to small teams and individuals, lowered barriers to entry dramatically. Moreover, the global recognition of games as culture and creative industry, not merely entertainment products, provided legitimacy that helped position gaming within Fundão's innovation and cultural development frameworks. The expansion of applied games and serious games in sectors like education, health, and training created alternative markets beyond commercial entertainment, diversifying potential revenue sources.

7.4.2.4 Cultural Shifts and Creative Industries Recognition

Broader cultural shifts in how creative industries were understood and valued created enabling contexts. The recognition that knowledge economies depend not only on technology but also on creativity, design, and cultural production meant that gaming could be positioned as strategically important rather than frivolous. However, tensions remained in how gaming was culturally framed. One former industry professional noted: *"I think the thing with Fundão is that the council and its communications, even when they went to fairs, always had a very technological angle – very TechHub, very focused on that side of things. And I think that overshadowed the games aspect a little bit."* They elaborated on gaming's dual nature: *"What I believe is that video games have this artistic and cultural intention – that's actually how I got into games – but that side tends to get lost in a communication strategy that's 100% focused on new technologies, because they're different business models. A tech company often creates a practical product – a piece of software that helps with daily life, for example – whereas a video game is, generally speaking, an entertainment product, something creative and artistic."*

7.4.3 Role of neighbouring and proto-industries

Unlike many European gaming hubs, Fundão's gaming cluster did not emerge from traditional proto-industries such as arcade cabinet manufacturing, pinball production, or demoscene communities. Instead, its development relied on a constellation of neighbouring and adjacent industries that collectively fulfilled similar enabling functions. These sectors provided technical skills, creative competencies, legitimacy, training pathways, and entrepreneurial culture, compensating for the absence of a path-dependent entertainment electronics industry. Rather than organic evolution, the cluster reflects a process of deliberate institutional construction and cross-sectoral contamination.

7.4.3.1 Technology and IT Services Sector

The technology and IT services sector, particularly large companies like Altran (later Capgemini)²⁷, played a crucial, yet indirect role in enabling gaming development. Altran’s presence from 2014 provided multiple benefits. It demonstrated Fundão’s viability for serious technology operations, reducing perceived risks for other companies. It brought hundreds of technology professionals to the region, creating a talent pool from which gaming companies could recruit or from which individuals might transition to gaming ventures.

The IT services sector also provided practical knowledge transfer. Professionals working in enterprise software development possessed programming skills, project management experience, and professional discipline directly applicable to game development. While game development has distinctive characteristics, the foundational software engineering competencies transfer across domains. Individuals could potentially transition from IT services to gaming development, or work in IT services while pursuing gaming projects as side ventures. In this context, the technology and IT services sector functioned as a de facto proto-industry for gaming.

7.4.3.2 Creative Industries: Animation, Design, and Multimedia

The creative industries sector, though small in Fundão, provided important cross-pollination opportunities. Individuals with backgrounds in fine arts, animation, and design brought perspectives and skills complementary to programming-focused game development. One former industry professional exemplified this cross-pollination. They described their background: *“I finished my degree in Fine Arts back in 2013, and my first job – which gave me my first real taste of the games industry – was as an interactive designer at Leleh Land, a publisher of interactive books for children.”* They also explained their path into gaming: *“At the time, I didn’t really think of video games as part of the creative industries – I actually wanted to work in animation. But somewhere along the way, my first opportunities ended up being in that in-between space between games and illustration. Then I started to see how interactivity brought a different kind of creative freedom compared to other media, and eventually, I fell in love with the industry as a whole.”*

7.4.3.3 Traditional Sector Modernisation

Perhaps surprisingly, connections emerged between traditional sectors like agriculture and gaming/technology. The municipality’s efforts to modernise cherry production and other agricultural activities through technology created opportunities for visualisation, data platforms, simulation, and training applications. While these connections remained mostly potential rather than fully realised, they represented the kind of unexpected synergies that integrated innovation ecosystems can generate.

The recognition that gaming technologies might serve agricultural training, tourism experiences, cultural heritage interpretation, or environmental education created conceptual space for gaming

²⁷ <https://www.capgemini.com/pt-en/about-us/who-we-are/our-brands/capgemini-engineering/>.

within territorial development strategies, even when commercial entertainment game development remained the primary focus.

7.4.3.4 Education and Training Sectors

The professional education and training sectors provided crucial support to neighbouring industries. The Academia de Código²⁸ programming training programme, while not gaming-specific, brought individuals to Fundão who then became embedded in the emerging technology community. One former industry professional described: *“A personal opportunity came up to move to Fundão, because Fundão had that programme with the Academia de Código, which my husband at the time enrolled in. That changed our lives quite a lot – we made a professional and personal transition to Fundão.”* This example illustrates how adjacent educational programmes create pathways into the territory and community. Professional training centres focused on digital technologies, though serving broader technology sector needs, produced graduates with skills applicable to gaming. The municipality’s investment in training infrastructure – both formal programmes and informal learning opportunities through the Fab Lab and other facilities – created an environment conducive to continuous skill development essential in rapidly evolving technology sectors like gaming.

7.4.4 Factors that influenced the birth and development of local industry

7.4.4.1 Digital Infrastructure and Connectivity

Broadband connectivity and digital infrastructure development proved essential enabling factors. The early 2010s attempt to create the first digital village in Castelo Novo failed precisely because connectivity was insufficient, as one official recalled, *“We did extensive communications in technology magazines, both in Europe and worldwide, saying that Fundão had great conditions – Forget New York, forget Tokyo, Fundão is the destination.”* A year later, how many people did we attract? Zero. It was a complete communication failure because it was all too poetic and unrealistic; we didn’t fully understand what we would need to implement that idea. The digital infrastructure, particularly broadband connectivity, was simply insufficient to support remote knowledge workers in a remote mountain village.”

However, systematic investment in broadband infrastructure throughout the municipality during the mid-2010s progressively eliminated this constraint. By the late 2010s, connectivity had improved sufficiently to support remote work, cloud-based development tools, video conferencing, and large file transfers essential for modern game development. The municipality prioritised digital infrastructure as a foundational investment, recognising that without adequate connectivity, the entire innovation strategy would fail. This infrastructure investment was not gaming-specific but created conditions enabling technology-intensive activities generally, including gaming.

²⁸ <https://www.interregeurope.eu/good-practices/transformation-of-fundao-portugal-academia-de-codigo>.

7.4.4.2 Housing Policy and Quality of Life Infrastructure

The municipality developed programmes subsidising rent for newly arriving talent, making it economically viable for professionals to relocate. As one official explained: *“We created housing and space offerings at competitive prices with incentives for talent. Additionally, we leveraged one of our strengths: the quality of life in low-density regions, which can be very competitive when compared to other areas.”*

The Mayor described their distinctive approach: *“We were – and for years continued to be – the only municipality in the country with a housing programme that subsidised rent for qualified workers who wanted to settle here.”* Moreover, the strategy also focused on the quality of infrastructure – schools, healthcare, cultural amenities, and recreational opportunities. The mayor emphasised: *“We assist with school selection, healthcare, administrative processes, and also provide support to the most vulnerable, ensuring access to essential goods like food and housing.”* This comprehensive approach recognised that attracting talent required addressing family needs holistically, not merely offering jobs.

7.4.4.3 Family Support and Integration Services

Support services for families and comprehensive integration assistance distinguished Fundão’s approach. The municipality developed intercultural mediators supporting 77 nationalities, as the Mayor described: *“We have intercultural mediators, and we’re well known for that. We’ve hired mediators for different communities: for the Middle East, India, Pakistan, Nepal, South America, the United States, Central Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, among others. These mediators are fundamental, both for their linguistic and cultural knowledge.”* The municipality developed intensive training models with short modules enabling socio-professional autonomy. Crucially, as the Mayor noted, *“We don’t wait for people to learn Portuguese before adapting their skills to our labour market. We do this simultaneously, significantly reducing the time needed for autonomy. While in Europe, this process typically takes around five years, especially for vulnerable people like those in humanitarian boats or refugee camps along the Mediterranean coast, in Fundão, we’ve reduced it to 11 months, five times less”.*

7.4.4.4 Legal and Regulatory Frameworks

National and European legal and regulatory frameworks influenced development, though often indirectly. European Union labour mobility regulations enabled the recruitment of talent from across the EU without immigration complications. However, as the gaming workforce diversified to include talent from outside the EU – particularly from Brazil, India, and other countries – Portuguese immigration regulations and the municipality’s capacity to navigate these regulations became important. The municipality’s dedicated migration support services helped companies and individuals navigate legal requirements, reducing administrative burdens that might otherwise deter international recruitment. Entrepreneurship regulations and startup support frameworks at the national level provided some enabling structures, though not gaming-specific. Programmes like Startup Portugal, which Fundão’s incubator managed locally, provided recognition and minimal

resources for early-stage ventures. However, interviewees did not emphasise regulatory factors as particularly important, either as enablers or constraints, suggesting that the legal environment was reasonably permissive without being particularly facilitative. Tax policies received minimal discussion in interviews, suggesting neither significant incentives nor major constraints. The absence of gaming-specific tax relief (unlike the UK's VGTR) meant that Portuguese game development operated without the fiscal advantages some competing countries offered, but this affected all Portuguese developers equally and was not Fundão-specific.

7.4.4.5 Economic Stability and Investment Climate

The broader Portuguese economic context transitioned from a severe crisis during the early 2010s to a gradual recovery by the late 2010s. This improved economic stability created more favourable conditions for entrepreneurship and investment, though challenges remained. Access to capital for gaming ventures remained severely limited throughout the period. As the Mayor emphasised, this represented a critical constraint: *“We haven’t yet been able to attract capital-intensive structures, but we would like to. The video game industry is massive from a financial standpoint, and this is a gap we face – not just in the gaming sector but also in startup ecosystems in general. In terms of intensive knowledge, we’re relatively well-positioned, but in attracting capital, we are significantly lagging.”* He elaborated on the risk this posed: *“This has clearly become a highly competitive and capital-intensive sector. As such, we risk being left out – we could fall ‘off the rails.’ Getting into the last carriages of the train is effectively the same as being off the train entirely. We don’t have the money to stay on track, and that’s a very important factor.”* The limited investment climate meant that gaming ventures in Fundão relied primarily on bootstrapping, personal savings, municipal support programmes, and revenue from applied projects or services rather than venture capital or angel investment typical in larger gaming hubs.

7.4.5 Role of the territory for continuity/connection factors between before and after the birth of the cluster

7.4.5.1 Industrial and Production Transformations

Fundão's transformation from a traditional economy to innovation-driven development revealed both ruptures and continuities in industrial organisation and production modes. Physical production of tangible goods gave way to knowledge work, creating intangible digital products. Local and national markets were superseded by global digital markets accessed through online platforms. Traditional stable employment relationships transformed towards entrepreneurial, project-based, and flexible work arrangements characteristic of creative industries. However, beneath these ruptures, continuities persisted. The territory's historical experience with economic adaptation created cultural familiarity with economic change. Adaptive capacity, learned through managing previous transitions, proved valuable for navigating contemporary transformation. Community orientation and strong local identity persisted, providing social cohesion during economic upheaval. The practice of creatively repurposing resources – converting a cheese market into a Fab Lab, transforming abandoned buildings into coworking spaces – reflected continuity in resourcefulness and pragmatic adaptation. One official described this continuity through transformation: *“We tried to see ourselves as a startup, always trying to innovate and be dynamic, moving quickly, so we wouldn't fall behind the bigger players.”* This startup mentality applied to the municipality itself represented an adaptation of entrepreneurial thinking – historically present in small businesses and family enterprises – to the challenge of territorial development.

7.4.5.2 Institutional Evolution, Governance Transformation and Paradigm Shifts

Municipal governance underwent profound evolution while maintaining institutional continuity. The municipality as an institution persisted, but its role transformed from traditional service provision to innovation intermediation and economic development leadership. New functions emerged – talent attraction, business reception, innovation facilitation, international networking – alongside traditional responsibilities. The mayor's background in community development and participatory planning ensured that new approaches were built on established practices rather than completely replacing them.

The Living Lab governance model represented innovation in institutional form. As one official described, it brought together an informal consortium of about thirty local, national, and regional entities working collaboratively to help develop a new economic development strategy. This model formalised and scaled participatory approaches while creating new institutional architecture for multi-stakeholder coordination. Regional development structures such as Aldeias do Xisto also incorporated innovation elements – most notably the Fab Lab located within this network – while maintaining a focus on heritage valorisation and sustainable tourism. This institutional flexibility enabled evolution without complete rupture.

These institutional transformations reflected broader paradigm shifts in how territorial development was conceptualised and pursued. The shift from deficit-focused thinking to asset-

based approaches, emphasising distinctive advantages, represented a crucial reframing. The Mayor articulated this shift: *“We thought – and perhaps much earlier than others in Portugal – that if we could attract talent, the companies would follow. Why? Because, in technological areas, competition for human capital is both vital and intense.”*

This recognition that low-density territories could compete on quality of life, community, and lifestyle, rather than attempting to replicate metropolitan characteristics, transformed perceived weaknesses into potential strengths when positioned correctly for specific audiences. The concept of Fundão as “land of welcome” (*terra de acolhimento*) represented identity evolution from an agricultural municipality to a cosmopolitan innovation community, reframing the municipality’s essential character while maintaining cultural continuity in values of hospitality and inclusion.

The paradigm shift extended to relationships between public and private sectors, with the municipality positioning itself as an innovation intermediary actively shaping economic development rather than merely providing infrastructure and services. This more entrepreneurial approach represented a significant departure from conventional municipal administration while remaining grounded in existing institutional practices.

7.5 Detailed historical timeline before the birth of the cluster and continuity factors

7.5.1 ‘New’ historical timeline

Figure 17. New Historical Timeline of Fundão Gaming Cluster.

7.5.1.1 2008-2011: Financial Crisis Context

The European financial crisis and Portugal's subsequent intervention by the Troika created a paradoxical context that profoundly shaped Fundão's innovation strategy and, consequently, the conditions for the gaming cluster's eventual emergence, overlapping with the proto-cluster phase.

The negative pressures were substantial and undeniable, while simultaneously creating conditions that enabled unconventional thinking and experimental approaches that might have been rejected during more prosperous times. Severe fiscal constraints limited municipal budgets dramatically, forcing difficult choices about resource allocation and making large capital investments nearly impossible. As one official with experience in regional development described, *"the innovation strategy was clearly born in this context of crisis, with the country highly conditioned in terms of its investment capacity, in a strong context of restriction and a depressive climate from the point of view of confidence and investment."*

Yet paradoxically, these severe constraints created enabling conditions that made the Fundão Innovation Plan possible and perhaps even more likely to succeed than during prosperity. The crisis forced bold innovation and unconventional thinking precisely because conventional approaches had clearly failed. Municipal leaders felt liberated to try experimental policies because the alternative – continuing down the existing path – was obviously leading towards municipal extinction. This stark reality created urgency and necessity that overcame bureaucratic inertia and resistance to change. The necessity-driven character of the strategy gave it authenticity and urgency that resonated with potential supporters, collaborators, and eventually residents who chose to move to Fundão.

7.5.1.2 2012: Strategic Planning Phase and PechaKucha Events

The year 2012 marked the beginning of systematic strategic planning that would fundamentally reorient Fundão's development trajectory. As one official described, *"the new socio-economic strategy began to be developed in mid-2012 when Paulo Fernandes started his term, initially substituting the previous mayor. Even in that transitional year before the 2013 elections, the decision was made to design this new strategy called the innovation plan."* Events like the PechaKucha proved transformative for several reasons. First, they reconnected the diaspora with the territory, bringing back individuals who had left for education or careers but maintained emotional connections to Fundão. Second, they generated ideas and international perspectives that challenged conventional thinking about what was possible in a small interior municipality. Third, they created early momentum and visibility, signalling that something different was beginning to happen in Fundão. Fourth, they demonstrated the municipality's seriousness about innovation and openness to new ideas. The official recalled about seven or eight editions in a short space of time, and it was very important for collecting ideas and contributions for this strategy. The team presented the first draft of the plan in May 2012, remarkably quickly after starting the process in March or April.

From this planning phase emerged the fundamental insight that would guide the entire strategy: focusing on attracting talented individuals rather than companies. The Mayor explained this crucial inversion of conventional development logic. *“Many regions focus on attracting companies, offering land, buildings, and other physical factors to develop projects in their territories. But Fundão turned the game board around, thinking that if they could attract talent, the companies would follow.”* The reasoning was that in technological areas, competition for human capital is both vital and intense. This insight shaped everything that followed – the emphasis on housing, quality of life, family support, and community building rather than industrial parks and tax incentives.

7.5.1.3 2013: Creation of the First Infrastructure and Fab Lab

Following the 2013 elections that formally confirmed Paulo Fernandes as mayor, the implementation of the innovation plan accelerated. One of the first concrete actions was creating the municipality’s first incubator in a rehabilitated building. As one official described, when they created the first incubator, it was the rehabilitation of an old municipal square that was practically abandoned for ten years. Basically, what they did was replace the roof, which was destroyed, and remove all the rubble inside, clean it thoroughly, and paint the walls white. From there, they invited people they knew – It was really by invitation – doing projects at home or in garages or anywhere else, to come and help build the incubator. This approach demonstrated the strategy’s resourcefulness and participatory character, creating infrastructure on a minimal budget while building community engagement.

The creation of the Fab Lab Aldeias do Xisto²⁹ in 2013 represented a particularly significant symbolic and functional milestone. As one municipal architect recalled, they began creating some attraction tools, such as the Fab Lab in 2013, and trained people from the municipality in these areas. The Fab Lab remains strategic even today. At the time, it had an impact whenever a company came to Fundão, or when a political minister or visitors from other countries came – it was mandatory for them to visit the Fab Lab, which was once an old market where cheese was sold. Essentially, they turned a cheese shop into a digital manufacturing laboratory. One official remembered that at the time, they could have created a Fab Lab independently, but they decided they wanted to place it in the Global Network of Fab Labs;³⁰ this global connection was invaluable for a peripheral territory.

²⁹ <https://movetofundao2024.pt/fab-lab-aldeias-do-xisto/>.

³⁰ <https://fabfoundation.org/global-community/>.

7.5.1.4 2013/2014: Altran's Arrival as Critical Validation

Another transformative moment in late 2013/early 2014 was, as previously mentioned, the arrival of Altran (later acquired by Capgemini Engineering), the first major technology company to establish operations in Fundão. This arrival was somewhat accidental but proved crucial for validating the innovation strategy. The speed of implementation was remarkable; Altran started with sixty people in a space that the municipality had to adapt in just fifteen days to accommodate them in Fundão. This required the rapid mobilisation of resources and demonstrated the municipality's capacity for agile response. One official described how they then started to build and adapt their multi-purpose pavilion, which became their business centre, where eventually 400 people would work with four companies established.

Altran's presence served multiple crucial functions for the emerging ecosystem. First, it validated Fundão as a viable location for serious technology companies, demonstrating that major international firms would establish operations in the interior if conditions were right. Second, it brought a critical mass of technology professionals to the region, creating a pool of experienced workers who could potentially transition to startups or launch their own ventures. Third, it demonstrated to other companies that talent could be successfully recruited to Fundão, reducing perceived risks. Fourth, it created demand for housing, services, and amenities that benefited the broader community. Fifth, it provided learning opportunities about what companies needed in terms of infrastructure, support, and community resources. The Mayor emphasised his proactive approach to company attraction. He explained spending years travelling with a "suitcase in hand" to promote Fundão's advantages to companies. The strategy was to leverage Fundão's high quality of life and lower costs to attract tech companies that typically gravitate towards large urban centres.

7.5.1.5 2014: UBI Gaming Course Launch and Early Ecosystem Development

The year 2014 marked a crucial educational milestone with the launch of UBI's video game development course, the first such programme at a Portuguese university. As one academic expert later noted, this course had been an idea of Professor Abel Gomes for a long time. The programme combined game design and development, producing what interviewees characterised as "a factory of game developers." The timing of this launch, two years into the innovation strategy's implementation, was significant. By 2014, Fundão was beginning to demonstrate that it could offer opportunities for technology professionals, making it more plausible that gaming graduates might actually find local employment rather than necessarily emigrating.

However, 2014 also revealed limitations in the initial strategy, such as the previously mentioned early attempt to create the first digital village in Castelo Novo. Despite this failure, the broader ecosystem was developing. The municipality was building relationships and networks, learning what worked and what didn't, and refining its approach. The Living Lab Cova da Beira was functioning as a governance structure, bringing together diverse stakeholders. The first residents were beginning to arrive, attracted by the housing programmes and quality of life propositions. The innovation discourse was gaining credibility as early actions demonstrated commitment beyond mere rhetoric.

7.5.1.6 2015/2016: Awards, Recognition, and Gamification Initiatives

By 2015 and 2016, Fundão was already winning national and international awards for its innovative approach. As one official recalled, their initial forecast was to see results after a term and a half, but by 2015 and 2016, they were already winning awards. Everything happened much faster than anticipated. These recognitions served multiple purposes – they validated the strategy to sceptical local constituents, attracted media attention that brought Fundão to national consciousness, provided credibility when recruiting companies and talent, and created momentum that made further success more likely. In 2017, the municipality launched gamification programmes in sectors like education and civic engagement (Pinto et al., 2020), providing local professionals with hands-on experience in game development technologies. The Mayor explained that gamification was seen as a key model for creating relevant projects across various sectors, from health to data management. This cross-sector integration benefited the gaming cluster by providing opportunities for applied gamification and diversified funding sources. It also helped legitimise gaming technologies as valuable tools for serious purposes beyond entertainment, making gaming more comprehensible and acceptable to stakeholders who might have dismissed pure entertainment games as frivolous.

This period also saw the expansion of support services and infrastructure. The municipality created dedicated teams for business reception and talent attraction. Professional training programmes proliferated, housing programmes expanded, and the coworking network grew, eventually reaching eleven spaces across the municipality with over eighty daily users. The innovation ecosystem was maturing from initial concept to operational reality.

7.5.1.7 2018: Emergence of First Gaming Startups

Around 2018, the first gaming-specific companies began emerging in Fundão, approximately six years after the innovation strategy began and four years after UBI's gaming course launched. Studios like Digitality Game Studio³¹ represented early pioneers in what would become a recognisable gaming component within the broader technology ecosystem. One former industry professional who had moved to the region described that at the time, there were four game companies in that region. This emergence reflected the convergence of multiple factors that had been developing over previous years. UBI's gaming course had produced its first cohorts of graduates, some of whom chose to stay in or return to the region rather than migrating to Lisbon or Porto. The broader technology ecosystem provided infrastructure, support services, and a community of technology professionals that made launching a gaming startup more feasible. The municipality's innovation programmes offered incubation support, even if not specifically tailored to gaming. The quality of life and lower costs made bootstrapping a startup more economically

³¹ <https://digitalitygames.com/>.

viable than in expensive metropolitan centres. International connections were growing, making it possible to access markets and collaborators beyond Portugal. However, the gaming sector remained quite small during this period, but the emergence of even a handful of gaming companies signalled that the sector could potentially grow within Fundão’s ecosystem.

7.5.1.8 2019: Formalisation of Migration Support and European Recognition

In 2019, the municipality formalised its migration support services, creating a dedicated call centre and support structure for migrants with a wide range of responses, from social services to training and inclusion in housing. This reflected both the growing diversity of the population – the municipality was attracting professionals from around the world – and the strategic recognition that comprehensive integration support was essential for talent retention. Rather than treating migration as a problem to be managed, Fundão positioned it as an asset to be cultivated. The Mayor emphasised that Fundão is a welcoming place. Innovation was the initial strategy, but now they call Fundão a “land of welcome”, with intercultural mediators hired for different communities—for the Middle East, India, Pakistan, Nepal, South America, the United States, Central Europe, Sub-Saharan Africa, among others.

This comprehensive approach to inclusion would prove particularly relevant not only for the technological but also for the gaming sector. As the Mayor noted, in the gaming sector, internationalisation is total. It’s a completely globalised area where the ability to combine inclusion and talent is a key factor.

7.5.1.9 2020-2023: COVID-19 Pandemic and Remote Work Acceleration

The COVID-19 pandemic paradoxically benefited Fundão’s ecosystem while causing disruptions worldwide. The pandemic accelerated the adoption of remote work practices that Fundão had already been promoting for years. This allowed the cluster to attract professionals from Lisbon and other major cities, many of whom relocated to Fundão due to the region’s lower cost of living and more spacious environment. These professionals brought new expertise and helped expand the cluster’s capabilities, with several new game development projects emerging. By this time, gaming had become more of a central focus, with a growing number of game studios and tech companies becoming more specialised in the gaming sector. Fundão’s cluster began to clearly define itself as a gaming-focused subset within the broader technology ecosystem. The municipality increased its engagement with national industry dialogues to position Fundão as an important part of Portugal’s gaming sector. International collaboration grew, particularly with Brazilian game developers, as Fundão sought to build its reputation and presence within the global gaming community. One official described the partnership with Porto Digital³² in Recife and connections with entrepreneurs

³² <https://www.portodigital.org/>.

from Florianópolis, particularly in the AgroTech sector, as doors they had opened that could bring even more value to the municipality.

7.5.1.10 2024- Present: Gaming Cluster Maturation and Positioning

By 2024, Fundão’s innovation ecosystem included over 1,200 software engineers compared to just three in 2012, representing 77 nationalities. The gaming sector was increasingly visible within this broader ecosystem, though still representing a specialised subset rather than the dominant focus. The municipality launched the “Future Fundão” platform in beta version at the Web Summit, providing information and application processes for the virtual incubation programme. This platform represented the formalisation and scaling of support services that had previously operated more informally.

A significant milestone in 2024 was Fundão’s participation as a partner in the **GAME-ER** project. As a project partner, Fundão serves as one of the case study clusters for research while also functioning as a pilot site for implementing and validating recommendations emerging from the project. This dual role positioned the municipality at the forefront of evidence-based gaming cluster development strategies, providing both external validation of Fundão’s achievements and opportunities for knowledge exchange with other European gaming clusters, potentially addressing some of the isolation and limited networking that had previously challenged the cluster’s development. Moreover, within the municipality’s broader innovation ecosystem development strategy, supported by municipal and European funds, a new building was inaugurated in 2025, specifically designed to host technological companies and start-ups. Within this facility, the **GAME-ER** project funded the implementation of a dedicated gaming lab equipped with diverse gaming production equipment and virtual reality technology, designed to serve as a coworking space for gaming studios and game developers.

7.6 Conclusions

The historical development of Fundão’s gaming cluster represents an exceptional case of territorial transformation in interior Portugal, driven by deliberate policy intervention under conditions of existential demographic crisis. The identification of 2012 as “year zero” marks the beginning of the Fundão Innovation Plan, though gaming-specific development only emerged around 2018 within the broader technology ecosystem cultivated over the preceding six years. This temporal layering proved crucial – gaming benefited from infrastructure, support mechanisms, and community created for general technology development, demonstrating that gaming clusters in peripheral territories may require broader innovation ecosystem foundations rather than sector-specific initiatives from inception. Three determining factors stand out as essential: sustained political leadership providing continuity over 12+ years; the fundamental strategic insight of attracting talented individuals rather than companies, inverting conventional economic development logic;

and the 2008-2012 financial crisis that paradoxically enabled bold experimentation by creating political space for unconventional approaches when conventional methods had manifestly failed.

Despite achievements, significant challenges constrain the cluster's growth trajectory. Limited capital access, distance from major markets, small absolute numbers of gaming professionals, and limited international visibility represent ongoing obstacles. However, recent developments signal strategic efforts to address these limitations. Fundão's participation as a partner in the **GAME-ER** Horizon Europe project, which enabled the implementation of a dedicated gaming lab, the 2025 partnership with the Portuguese Electronic Sports Federation, which relocated its headquarters to Fundão, and systematic participation in international events demonstrate intensified efforts to overcome peripherality through proactive visibility creation and network building. The cluster's development pathway also demonstrates crucial continuities – key individuals embodied connections between traditional and innovative approaches, institutions adapted rather than being replaced, and core territorial values of hospitality and community persisted.

As of 2025, Fundão's gaming cluster remains fundamentally emergent rather than mature. The sector's sustainability depends substantially on whether it can transition from municipal-supported emergence to self-sustaining growth, overcome capital access limitations, and achieve adequate international visibility.

8 CROSS-CLUSTER HISTORICAL SYNTHESIS: RECURRING MECHANISMS OF REGIONAL GAME-CLUSTER FORMATION

This section synthesises recurrent historical mechanisms observed across the six regional case studies analysed in D4.3 (Dundee, Turin, Brno, Lyon, Bordeaux, Fundão). Rather than reiterating individual trajectories, it distils a limited set of transversal dynamics that repeatedly shaped cluster emergence, consolidation, and transformation over time. The synthesis is grounded exclusively in the empirical findings already documented in the preceding chapters and aims to clarify transferable historical insights that can inform subsequent comparative and policy-oriented work packages of the **GAME-ER** Horizon Europe project.

This synthesis process can therefore be articulated through the following recurring historical mechanisms:

1) Anchor Institutions as Long-Term Stabilising Forces

Across all cases, the presence of one or more anchor institutions emerges as a decisive continuity factor. These institutions – universities (Abertay in Dundee; Masaryk University in Brno), large firms or proto-firms (DMA Design in Dundee; Kalisto in France), or public innovation infrastructures (OGR in Turin; municipal leadership in Fundão) – provided temporal stability in otherwise volatile industrial environments. Their role was not limited to employment or infrastructure provision; rather, they functioned as repositories of skills, reputational capital, and coordination capacity. Furthermore, they have frequently become professional and symbolic spatial reference points, capable of attracting resources and attention from beyond the local context. Importantly, anchor institutions often predated the formal recognition of a “cluster” and only retrospectively became legible as such.

2) Crisis and Disruption as Catalytic Moments

Contrary to linear development models, cluster consolidation frequently followed periods of disruption. The collapse of dominant actors (e.g. Real Time Worlds in Dundee; Kalisto in France) or broader economic restructuring (post-industrial decline in Dundee; rural marginalisation in Fundão) acted as catalytic moments. These crises redistributed talent, lowered entry barriers, and legitimised alternative organisational forms (start-ups, collectives, micro-studios). Rather than interrupting development, disruption often marked a transition from concentration to diversification, corresponding to the empirically identified “Year Zero” moments in several cases.

3) Talent Pipelines and Informal Skill Ecologies

All clusters relied on sustained local skill reproduction, but formal education alone never constituted the initial driver. Instead, early phases were partly characterised by hybrid talent pipelines

combining informal practices (e.g., hobbyist cultures, demoscene activity, amateur programming, arcade and home-computer cultures) with later institutionalisation through higher education. Universities typically entered the ecosystem after industry practices were already established, formalising and scaling pre-existing competencies rather than inventing them *ex nihilo*. Private professional training institutions, conversely, emerged only later, in response to prevailing market dynamics. This sequencing is consistent across mature and emerging clusters alike.

4) Governance Continuity Beyond Organisational Change

Historical analysis reveals strong continuity in governance logics (when and if present) even when specific organisations disappeared. Individuals recurrently transitioned across roles – founders, educators, association leaders, investors – maintaining coordination capacity over decades. This personal continuity compensated for institutional fragility and explains why clusters often survived firm-level failure. Governance, in this sense, functioned less through stable organisations than through durable actor networks embedded locally but connected trans-locally.

5) Education–Industry Co-Evolution

Where education played a central role, it did so through co-evolution rather than top-down planning. Educational programmes adapted iteratively to industry needs, often shaped directly by practitioners. In Dundee and Brno, curricula were repeatedly recalibrated in response to technological shifts (from home computing to 3D graphics to mobile and indie production). In Fundão, training initiatives were embedded within a broader territorial redevelopment strategy. Across cases, education systems were most effective when structurally porous to industry input. By contrast, in contexts where such co-evolution and coordination were weaker or entirely lacking, clusters faced greater challenges and developed more slowly.

6) Limits of Path Dependency

While historical legacies mattered, none of the clusters followed a strictly path-dependent trajectory. Earlier industrial bases (textiles, electromechanics, manufacturing) provided transferable skills and infrastructures, but did not mechanically determine outcomes. Several cases (notably Turin and Fundão) demonstrate that clusters can emerge without strong sectoral continuity, provided that coordination mechanisms, external connectivity, and institutional experimentation are present. Path dependency thus appears conditional and mediated, not deterministic.

7) External Networks and Trans-Local Connectivity

Finally, all clusters were shaped by sustained engagement with external networks – national publishers, international markets, platform holders, conferences, and mobility circuits. These connections enabled access to capital, technologies, and symbolic recognition unavailable locally. Crucially, external linkages did not undermine local embeddedness; rather, clusters that combined strong local cohesion with outward-oriented networks proved more resilient over time.

Taken together, these mechanisms highlight that regional game clusters are historically assembled through non-linear processes combining continuity and rupture, local embeddedness and external connectivity, informal practices and institutionalisation. This synthesis clarifies how historically grounded patterns already identified in D4.3 can be rendered comparable across cases, providing an explicit bridge between empirical reconstruction and the forthcoming comparative and policy-focused deliverables within the **GAME-ER** project.

9 CONCLUSION

This deliverable provides a comprehensive analysis of the history and prehistory of the six video game clusters examined within the **GAME-ER** project. The analysis draws on established approaches in media history and video game historiography, thereby underscoring the importance of situating video game production within broader institutional, technological and cultural contexts. In addition, the diachronic trajectories that led to the emergence and consolidation of each cluster have been reconstructed, enabling the identification of the socio-technical, economic and cultural factors that shaped their development. This process involved, for instance, the identification of key turning points, including the founding of leading institutions, the emergence of cutting-edge research activities, and the impact of specific public interventions. Understanding these historical trajectories is essential for explaining how local conditions, institutional legacies and external influences have contributed to the clusters' current configurations.

The outcome of this task is a data-rich and narrative-driven analysis that has resulted in six robust historical datasets, each isolating the factors underpinning the formation of the clusters and their subsequent development, in line with the objectives initially set out for Task 4.3. Above all, D4.3 is fully consistent with the previous outputs of the project (D4.1 and D4.2), extending and enriching a conceptual and informational framework that has hitherto received limited scholarly attention. The resulting body of data and their reports constitute a further “starting point” for an evolving line of research, particularly in view of the comparative analysis and policy recommendations envisaged in the later stages of the **GAME-ER** project.

The analysis confirms that the six clusters are characterised by markedly different historical trajectories. In some cases, clusters display long-standing and continuous development paths, highlighting the importance of sustained and structured processes in the creation of competitive ecosystems aligned with global market standards. In other instances, sudden exogenous factors or, conversely, radical endogenous transformations driven by policy interventions – that were disruptive in relation to the original context – have catalysed the emergence of creative and productive environments with strong potential for competitive growth. The periods preceding what has been identified as the “Year Zero” of each cluster thus reveal differentiated evolutionary patterns that are not necessarily constrained by territorial path dependency. Rather, they demonstrate how varying institutional choices, as well as different forms of cultural and socio-technical continuity, can lead to comparatively promising outcomes.

Finally, in line with the iterative and integrative approach adopted for previous deliverables within Work Package 4, this task is designed to feed directly into the two parallel tasks that remain ongoing: T4.4 (*Actors Map for each Cluster*), and T4.5 (*Mapping of on Skills/Competencies*). Once the results of all analytical processes have been consolidated and integrated with the comparative work conducted in Work Package 3 – specifically in T3.3 (*Development of a Comparison Synthesis*) – the

project will be able to offer a multidimensional and interdisciplinary framework intended to serve as a reference point for future research initiatives and policy development. In particular, this framework will support the formulation of context-sensitive, evidence-based policy recommendations planned for D3.4 (*Finalised Recommendations*), which are aimed at fostering the sustainable development of video game clusters across diverse European settings. This approach is fully aligned with the overarching objective of the **GAME-ER** project, namely to enhance understanding of regional video game industry ecosystems and to provide actionable insights for policies that promote creative innovation, economic competitiveness and territorial development in non-capital cities and regions throughout Europe.

10 REFERENCES

- Abertay University (1996). *Minutes for the meeting of the Senate, 16 October 1996: Enclosure 4 – The Dearing committee of enquiry into higher education*. University of Abertay Dundee.
- Abertay University (1997a). *Minutes for the meeting of the Senate, 15 October 1997: Enclosure 13 – Homologation of Chairman’s actions*. University of Abertay Dundee.
- Abertay University (1997b). *Minutes for the meeting of the Senate, 15 October 1997: Submission to Mr Brian Wilson, Minister of Education and Industry, Scotland*. University of Abertay Dundee.
- Abertay University (n.d.). *Our heritage*. Retrieved October 20, 2025, from <https://www.abertay.ac.uk/about/the-university/archive/our-heritage/>
- Adamovič, I. (2017). In the grey zone of sci-fi. In M. Hroch (Ed.), *I shout “That’s me!”: Stories of the Czech fanzine from the ’80s till now*. Page Five.
- Addendum to: ‘20 Years of Computer Games Degree Programs: From Abertay in 1997 to York in 2017’. *Comput Game J* 8, 107 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40869-019-00078-0>
- Alberts, G., & Oldenziel, R. (Eds.) (2014). *Hacking Europe: From computer cultures to demoscenes*. Springer.
- Amatérské radio (1982). Svazarm a výpočetní technika. *Amatérské radio*, Řada A, 31(4), 140.
- AMIGA Star (1992). Re-setkání zima ’92. *AMIGA Star*, 1(11), 45.
- Bach, M. (2012). Historie českých a slovenských her a týmů. In J. Jirkovský (Ed.), *Game Industry 2* (pp. 229–240). D.A.M.O.
- Bækkelund, N. G. (2021). Change agency and reproductive agency in the course of industrial path evolution. *Regional Studies*, 55(4), 757–768. BBC (n.d.). *About the Computer Literacy Project (1980–1989)*. Computer Literacy Project. Retrieved October 6, 2025, from <https://clp.bbcrewind.co.uk/history>
- BBC News (2024, November 22). It was our rock’n’roll: How the ZX Spectrum became a 1980s icon. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cpvzp80jv07o>
- Beck, D. C. (1996). Divadlo Husa na Provázku and the “absence” of Czech community. *Theatre Journal*, 48(4), 419–441.
- Bernášek, J. (2023, November 12). Bonus 5: Stroj hrající hru Nim na brněnském veletrhu (1960). *Herní Archeolog*. <https://herniarcheolog.blogspot.com/2023/11/bonus-5-stroj-hrajici-hru-nim-na.html>
- Blanchet, A. (2022). *French Touche! Writing on video game local history in France* [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gaqEuDY2YZA>
- Blanchet, A. (2022). The production of video games in France: the history of a sector seeking to establish itself as an industry (1973-1991). *Entreprises et histoire*, 109(4), 36–46.

- Blatný, J. (1985). *Stručná historie katedry*. Fakulta informačních technologií VUT v Brně. <http://www.fit.vutbr.cz/FIT/history/history86.html.cs>
- Blyth, T. (2012). *The legacy of the BBC Micro: Effecting change in the UK's cultures of computing*. Nesta. https://media.nesta.org.uk/documents/the_legacy_of_bbc_micro.pdf
- Bozdog, M. (2022). Storywalking as transnational method: From Juteopolis to Sugaropolis. In *Scotland's transnational heritage: Legacies of empire and slavery* (pp. 157–170). Edinburgh University Press.
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77–101.
- #brnoregion (2025, April 9). Czech Semiconductor Centre Launches in Brno, Strengthening Europe's Chip Autonomy. #brnoregion. <https://brnoregion.com/en/news/czech-semiconductor-centre-launches-in-brno-streng>
- Browne, S., & Tomlinson, J. (2011). A woman's town? Dundee women on the public stage. In J. Tomlinson & C. A. Whatley (Eds.), *Jute no more: Transforming Dundee* (pp. 107–131). Edinburgh University Press.
- Carbone, M. B., & Fassone, R. (Eds.) (2020). *Il videogioco in Italia: Storie, rappresentazioni, contesti*. Mimesis.
- Casadei, P., Bloom, M., Camerani, R., Masucci, M., Siepel, J., & Vélez-Ospina, J. (2023). Mapping the state of the art of creative cluster research: A bibliometric and thematic analysis. *European Planning Studies*, 31(12), 2531–2551.
- Chapman, A. (2016). *Digital games as history: How videogames represent the past and offer access to historical practice*. Routledge.
- Chaudhary, S., Kaur, P., Ferraris, A., Bresciani, S., & Dhir, A. (2024). Connecting entrepreneurial ecosystem and innovation. *Technovation*, 130, 102942.
- Chia, A. (2019). The moral calculus of vocational passion in digital gaming. *Television & New Media*, 20(8), 767–777. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1527476419851079>
- Codr, L. (2001, November 6). Rozhovor s tvůrci Loco Commotion. *iDNES.cz*. https://www.idnes.cz/hry/magazin/rozhovor-s-tvurci-loco-commotion.A011105_lococommotionint_bw
- Cox, A. (2013). *Empire, industry and class: The imperial nexus of jute, 1840–1940*. Routledge.
- Dailly, M. (2006). *Lemmings – A complete history of Lemmings*. The Life of a Game Developer. Retrieved October 10, 2025, from <https://lemmings.info/lemmings-gamehistory/>
- Dailly, M. (2021a, June 29). And then there was Lemmings (1991). *The Life of a Game Developer*. Retrieved October 11, 2025, from <https://lemmings.info/lemmings-1991/>
- Dailly, M. (2021b, June 27). “KACC” to DMA (1986). *The Life of a Game Developer*. <https://lemmings.info/hello-world/>
- Dailly, M. (2021c, June 27). The birth of DMA (1989). *The Life of a Game Developer*. <https://lemmings.info/the-birth-of-dma-1989/>

- Danton, T. (2021). *The Computers that Made Britain: The Home Computer Revolution of the 1980s*. Raspberry Pi Press.
- Datapro (1970). *NCR's Century 100 & 200*. http://www.bitsavers.org/pdf/ncr/NCR_DataPro_Reports/70C-656-01_7008_NCR_Century_100_200.pdf
- De Paoli, S., Leça, L., Moreira, T., Švelch, J., Fassone, R., Costalunga, N., & Fousek Krobova, T. (2025). *D4.1 – Report on primary data collection*. GAME-ER. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535331>
- De Paoli, S., Švelch, J., Costalunga, N., Livesey-Stephens, B., Jayemanne, D., Leça, L., Mariana, S., Moreira, T., & Matilde, C. S. (2025). *GAME-ER documentary material for Task 4.2 (Version 1.0)* [Data set]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17440712>
- Deterding, N. M., & Waters, M. C. (2021). Flexible coding of in-depth interviews: A twenty-first-century approach. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 50(2), 708–739.
- Di Domenico, C., & Di Domenico, M. (2007). Heritage and urban renewal in Dundee: Learning from the past when planning for the future of a post-industrial city. *Journal of Retail & Leisure Property*, 6(4), 327–339.
- DJCAD (2000). *The School of Television and Imaging, Duncan of Jordanstone College of Art & Design. School Guide Session 2000-2001*.
- Dundee City Council (1990). *Change of use, renewal or deletion of imposed conditions pertaining to Amusement arcades*. Sourced from University of Dundee Archives.
- Dundee & Angus Chamber of Commerce (2017, June 27). Dundee and NCR – still the home of the ATM. <https://www.dundeeandanguschamber.co.uk/news/article/4422/dundee-and-ncr-still-the-home-of-the-atm>
- Dundee University Archive (2022). *Oral history Interview with Chris Van der Kuyle, Oral History Project*. Available at Dundee University Physical Archive.
- Evening Telegraph (1995, September 21). Fun and games, all in a day's work. *Evening Telegraph*.
- Feldman, M. P. (2003). The locational dynamics of the US biotech industry: knowledge externalities and the anchor hypothesis. *Industry and Innovation*, 10(3), 311–328.
- Feldman, M. P., Francis, J., & Bercovitz, J. (2005). Creating a cluster while building a firm: entrepreneurs and the formation of industrial clusters. *Regional Studies*, 39(1), 129–141.
- Findlay, R. (1997, July 27). Fury over horror hit-and-run game. *Sunday Mail*.
- Fry, M. (2001). *The Scottish Empire*. Tuckwell Press; Birlinn.
- Game Developers Session 2003 (2007, August 25). <https://web.archive.org/web/20070825152216/http://www.ceske-hry.cz/gds/gds2003.html>
- Gazzard, A. (2024). *Now the chips are down: The BBC Micro*. MIT Press.
- GDACZ (2023). *CR 2023 Gaming Industry [report]*. Czech Game Developers Association. <https://gda.cz/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/Infografika2023en.pdf>
- Gillen, K. (1999). Hidden & Dangerous [Review]. *PC Gamer (UK)*, 7(71), 74–77.

- Grospietsch, J. (1994). Nadace počítačových klubů. *Zpravodaj Sharp Club Brno*, 5(5), 16.
- Harding, J. (2013). *Qualitative data analysis from start to finish*. Sage.
- Harris, J. L., & Menzel, M.-P. (2023). Entrepreneurial ecosystems and clusters: How can economic geographers advance debates for regional development?. *Environment and Planning A*, 55(8).
- House of Commons Scottish Affairs Committee (2011a). *Video games industry in Scotland: First report of session 2010–11*. <https://committees.parliament.uk/work/4702/video-games-industry-in-scotland/publications/>
- House of Commons Scottish Affairs Committee (2011b). *Video games industry in Scotland: Second report of session 2010–11*. <https://committees.parliament.uk/work/4702/video-games-industry-in-scotland/publications/>
- Janesick, V. J. (2014). Oral History Interviewing: Issues and Possibilities. *The Oxford handbook of qualitative research* (pp. 300–314). Oxford University Press.
- Jašš, R., & Fňukal, M. (2009). *The German language islands of Brno, Olomouc and Jihlava during German-Austrian irredentism in the autumn of 1918*. Charles University. <https://dspace.cuni.cz/handle/20.500.11956/161711>
- Jeřábek, M. (2008). K ideové rovině Výstavy soudobé kultury v Československu v Brně roku 1928. *Brno v minulosti a dnes*, 21, 315–340.
- Keogh, B. (2021). The cultural field of video game production in Australia. *Games and Culture*, 16(1), 116–135.
- Keogh, B. (2023). *The videogame industry does not exist*. MIT Press.
- Lachtan [Martin Kalivoda] (1996). Come in Future aneb Brno, Brno, srandy plno... *Level*, 2(22), 8–9.
- (lh) (1960). Ukázka kybernetického zařízení na brněnský veletrh. *Rudé Právo*, 40(250), 2.
- Lowood, H., & Guins, R. (Eds.) (2024). *Debugging game history: A critical lexicon*. MIT Press.
- Lloyd, G., McCarthy, J., & Peel, D. (2006). The re-construction of a small Scottish city: re-discovering Dundee. In *Small Cities* (pp. 105–119). Routledge.
- Malý, O. (2010, September 23). Jan Kudera: Na mafii jsem dobře vydělal. *Hospodářské noviny*.
- Mančář, M., & Nouzová, P. (2025, September 11). Kvůli Kingdom Come jim odešel šéf a vývojáři. *CzechCrunch*. <https://cc.cz/zkrouhli-jim-rozpocet-vyvojari-odesli-kvuli-kingdom-come-presto-v-brne-tvori-novy-dil-stredoveke-hry/>
- Markusen, A. (1996). Sticky places in slippery space: a typology of industrial districts. *Economic Geography*, 72(3), 293–313.
- Marshall, A. (1920). *Principles of economics* (8th ed.). Macmillan.
- McGoldrick, J. (1998, September 15). Strategic Alignment and Development of the University of Abertay Dundee. Request for Strategic Change Grant. *University of Abertay Dundee*.
- Meades, A. (2022). *Arcade Britannia: A social history of the British amusement arcade*. MIT Press.
- Modrák, J. (2008). Made in Czech. *Score*, 15(169), 48–53.
- NCR (1970). *Annual report 1970*. Dundee City Archives.

- Ogston, G., & Goodwin, L. (2024, November 22). It was our rock'n'roll: How the ZX Spectrum became a 1980s icon. *BBC News*. <https://www.bbc.co.uk/news/articles/cpvzp80jv07o>
- Peterka, J. (2005, October 21). Internetová (pre)historie Invexu. *eArchiv.cz*. <https://www.earchiv.cz/b05/b1021001.php3>
- Petr, M. (2020a, February 23). FPI: Jarek Kolář I Vietcong, Pterodon, BadFly Interactive Visiongame. <https://visiongame.cz/fpi-jarek-kolar-i-badfly-interactive/>
- Petr, M. (2020b, December 18). FPI: Roman Hladík I 2K Czech/Hangar 13 | Visiongame. Visiongame. <https://visiongame.cz/fpi-roman-hladik-i-2k-czech-hangar-13/>
- Petr, M. (2023a, May 12). FPI: David Šemík I Mafia, Mafia 2, Monzo, Happy Game ... | Visiongame. Visiongame. <https://visiongame.cz/fpi-david-semik-i-mafia-mafia-2-monzo-happy-game/>
- Petr, M. (2023b, September 8). FPI: Radim „Rumun“ Křivánek I Altar Interactive, Fish Fillets, Original War, UFO trilogy, Vision ... | Visiongame. Visiongame. <https://visiongame.cz/fpi-radim-rumun-krivanek-i-altar-interactive-fish-fillets-original-war-ufo-trilogy-vision/>
- Petr, M. (2024a, March 8). FPI: Lukáš „Izmi“ Veselý I Altar Interactive, UFO, ARMA, Bohemia Interactive, Herní Klastř, Gamebaze Visiongame Visiongame. Visiongame. <https://visiongame.cz/fpi-lukas-izmi-vesely-i-altar-interactive-ufo-arma-bohemia-interactive-herni-klastr-gamebaze/>
- Petr, M. (2024b, July 19). FPI: Vláda Chvátíl 1/2 I Altar Interactive, Original War, Fish Fillets, Vision ... Visiongame Visiongame. Visiongame. <https://visiongame.cz/fpi-vlada-chvatil-1-2-i-altar-interactive-original-war-fish-fillets-vision>
- Petr, M. (2024c, August 30). FPI: Jaroslav Turna I Vietcong, Pterodon, Mafia II, Project C.A.R.S., Motorstorm, Crashday, Forza .. | Visiongame. Visiongame. <https://visiongame.cz/fpi-jaroslav-turna-i-vietcong-pterodon-mafia-ii-project-c-a-r-s-motorstorm-crashday-forza/>
- Phillips, N., & Hardy, C. (2002). *Discourse analysis: Investigating processes of social construction*. Sage.
- Picard, M. (2013). The foundation of geemu: A brief history of early Japanese video games. *Game Studies*, 13(2).
- Pinto, R., Filgueiras, E., & Moutinho, K. (2020, July 10). Emotional Design and Gamification in Educational Processes: Predictor Model to Increase Video Game Efficiency. In *Design, User Experience, and Usability. Case Studies in Public and Personal Interactive Systems*. Cham: Springer.
- Polách, Z. (2001, January 24). Petr Vochozka osvětloval vývoj her. *iDNES.cz*. https://www.idnes.cz/hry/magazin/petr-vochozka-osvetloval-vyvoj-her.A010123_petrvochozka010124_bw
- Porter, M. E. (2000). Location, competition, and economic development: Local clusters in a global economy. *Economic Development Quarterly*, 14(1), 15–34.
- Pospíšil, P. (2001, January 27). Mosty mezi starou a novou ekonomikou. *Živě.cz*. <https://www.zive.cz/clanky/mosty-mezi-starou-a-novou-ekonomikou/sc-3-a->

- 27051/default.aspxPress & Journal (1995, March 28). IBM contract will bring 42 jobs to Dundee. *Press & Journal*.
- Retro Dundee (2011, March 30). Bordermatics & Hynd Bros amusements – 70’s–80’s. <https://retrodundee.wordpress.com/>
- Reynolds, R. (2015). Play Britannia: The development of UK video game policy. In *Video Game Policy* (pp. 113–128). Routledge.
- Rohlík, J. (1998). České a slovenské hry: Část II. *Score*, 5(59), 34–35.
- Rohlík, J. (2002). Petr Vochozka. *Level*, 8(85), 22–25.
- Rohlík, J. (2003). Denis Černý. *Level*, 9(98), 42–45.
- Rubin, H. J., & Rubin, I. S. (2012). *Qualitative interviewing: The art of hearing data* (3rd ed.). Sage.
- Rybka, M. (2000). Jak se dělají hry po česku? *Level*, 6(67), 10–19.
- saver (2002, March 11). Illusion Softworks Slovakia—Interview. Sector.sk. <https://www.sector.sk/clanok/4026/illusion-softworks-slovakia.htm>
- Schneider, H., & Koller, W. (2024). *The Austrian game industry*. Fachverband Unternehmensberatung, Buchhaltung und IT. <https://www.wko.at/oe/information-consulting/unternehmensberatung-buchhaltung-informationstechnologie/it-dienstleistung/the-austrian-game-industry-2024.pdf>
- Scotsman (The Gavster, Games Guru) (1996, December 20). Have a blast with the lads from “Lemmings”. *The Scotsman*.
- Sdělovací technika. (1960). Viděli jsme v Brně. *Sdělovací Technika*, 8(12), 442–445.
- Selwyn, N. (2002). Learning to Love the Micro: The discursive construction of educational computing in the UK, 1979–89. *British journal of sociology of education*, 23(3), 427–443.
- Simonová, N. (2006). Vzdělanostní nerovnosti a vzdělanostní mobilita v období socialismu. In P. Matějů & J. Straková (Eds.), *Nerovné šance na vzdělání*. Academia.
- Simpson, A. (1997, July 30). Games Genius a loser in court. *Daily Express*.
- Skovajsa, P. (n.d.). Consul 2717. Retrieved July 28, 2025, from https://consul.odkaznik.cz/consul_2717
- Smolík, T. (1998). Illusion Softworks [Interview]. *Level*, 4(44), 24–25.
- Spigel, B., & Vinodrai, T. (2021). Meeting its Waterloo? Recycling in entrepreneurial ecosystems after anchor firm collapse. *Entrepreneurship & Regional Development*, 33(7-8), 599–620.
- Stephen, F. (1997). Car-theft computer game accused of glamorising violent crime. *Scotland on Sunday*.
- Stephens, A. M., & Sandberg, J. (2020). How the practice of clustering shapes cluster emergence. *Regional Studies*, 54(5), 596–609.
- Stewart, G. (2017). *Dundee at work: People and industries through the years*. Amberley Publishing.
- Sutherland, J. (2018). 20 Years of Computer Games Degree Programs: From Abertay in 1997 to York in 2017. *The Computer Games Journal*, 7(3), 149–152.

- Svoboda, V. (1983). *Milníky veletrhů*. BVV.
- Švelch, J. (2018). *Gaming the Iron Curtain: How teenagers and amateurs in Communist Czechoslovakia claimed the medium of computer games*. MIT Press.
- Švelch, J. (2023). *Gaming the Iron Curtain: How teenagers and amateurs in Communist Czechoslovakia claimed the medium of computer games* (2nd ed.). MIT Press.
- Swalwell, M. (Ed.) (2021). *Game history and the local*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Tarantino, M., & Tosoni, S. (2017). Il videogioco in Italia: dal gettone al coin-op. In A. Grasso (Ed.), *Storia della comunicazione e dello spettacolo in Italia. Vol. III: I media alla sfida della convergenza (1979–2012)* (pp. 235–246). Vita e Pensiero.
- Tarantino, M., & Tosoni, S. (2019). Playing in the grey zone: The development of the Italian video game industry. In F. Colombo (Ed.), *Media and communication in Italy: Historical and theoretical perspectives* (pp. 256–267). Vita e Pensiero.
- Telegraph and Post (1995, April 28). Nintendo's new game designed by Dundee firm. *Telegraph and Post*.
- The Courier (2021, December 1). NCR: 75 years in Dundee, told in 75 incredible pictures. <https://www.thecourier.co.uk/>
- The Courier (2022, June 11). NCR – 75 years in Dundee told in 75 incredible pictures. *The Courier*. <https://www.thecourier.co.uk/fp/business-environment/2756403/ncr-75-years-in-dundee-told-in-75-incredible-pictures/>
- The Herald (1995, March 28). Ex-Timex tycoon expands factory. *The Herald*.
- Timmermans, S., & Tavory, I. (2012). Theory Construction in Qualitative Research: From Grounded Theory to Abductive Analysis. *Sociological Theory*, 30(3), 167–186.
- Tomlinson, J. (2011). Managing decline: The case of jute. *Scottish Historical Review*, 90(2), 257–279.
- Tomlinson, J., Morelli, C., & Wright, V. (2011). *The decline of jute: Managing industrial change*. Pickering & Chatto.
- Tomlinson, J., Phillips, J., & Wright, V. (2019). *De-industrialization: A case study of Dundee, 1951–2001* [Manuscript]. University of Glasgow. <https://eprints.gla.ac.uk/198886/>
- Tomlinson, J., Phillips, J., & Wright, V. (2022). De-industrialization: A case study of Dundee, 1951–2001, and its broad implications. *Business History*, 64(1), 28–54.
- Tsang, D. (2021). Innovation in the British video game industry since 1978. *Business History Review*, 95(4), 705–732. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0007680521000398>
- University of Abertay Dundee (1998a). *Proposal for the introduction of a new course: BSc (Hons) in computer games technology and virtual environments*. Abertay University Archive.
- University of Abertay Dundee (1998b). *Report of the meeting of the CVAG, 22 June 1998*. Abertay University Archive.
- University of Dundee (1999). *AS7 proposal for master of science in electronic imaging*.

- Vaishar, A., Šťastná, M., & Zapletalová, J. (2025). From industry to cultural tourism: Structural transformation of the second-order city. Case Brno. *Cities*, 158, 105685. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2024.105685>
- Vision Game (2025a, June 6). *ALTAR #1: We make the rules* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NWyu2meQt5s>
- Vision Game (2025b, June 12). *ALTAR #2: Original War* [Video recording]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MglVoJgNqbk>
- Wade, A. (2016). *Playback: A genealogy of 1980s British videogames*. Bloomsbury Academic.
- Wallis, A. (2006). Playing catch up: GTA/Lemmings' Dave Jones. *Gamasutra*. https://archive.ph/20120526225205/http://www.gamasutra.com/php-bin/news_index.php
- Webber, N. (2020). The Britishness of “British video games.” *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 26(2), 135–149.
- Wright, V. (2011). Juteopolis and after: Women and work in twentieth-century Dundee. In *Jute No More: Transforming Dundee* (pp. 132–162). Edinburgh University Press.
- Zak, R. (2021). DMA Design: The chaotic N64 years that led to Rockstar North. *Retro Gamer*, 226, 78–83.
- Ženka, J., Novotný, J., Slach, O., & Ivan, I. (2017). Spatial distribution of knowledge-intensive business services in a small post-communist economy. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 8(2), 385–406. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-015-0260-9>